

On the zeros of Riemann's Xi Function

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Abstract

We consider Riemann's Xi function $\xi(s)$ which is evaluated at $s = \frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega$, given by $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega) = E_{p\omega}(\omega)$, where σ, ω are real and compute its inverse Fourier transform given by $E_p(t)$. We study the properties of $E_p(t)$ and a promising new method is presented which could be used to show that the Fourier Transform of $E_p(t)$ given by $E_{p\omega}(\omega) = \xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega)$ does not have zeros for finite and real ω when $0 < |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$, corresponding to the critical strip excluding the critical line.

Keywords: Riemann, Xi, zeros, Fourier, transform

1. Introduction

It is well known that Riemann's Zeta function given by $\zeta(s) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{m^s}$ converges in the half-plane where the real part of s is greater than 1. Riemann proved that $\zeta(s)$ has an analytic continuation to the whole s-plane apart from a simple pole at $s = 1$ and that $\zeta(s)$ satisfies a symmetric functional equation given by $\xi(s) = \xi(1-s) = \frac{1}{2}s(s-1)\pi^{-\frac{s}{2}}\Gamma(\frac{s}{2})\zeta(s)$ where $\Gamma(s) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-u}u^{s-1}du$ is the Gamma function.[4] [5] We can see that if Riemann's Xi function has a zero in the critical strip, then Riemann's Zeta function also has a zero at the same location. Riemann made his conjecture in his 1859 paper, that all of the non-trivial zeros of $\zeta(s)$ lie on the critical line with real part of $s = \frac{1}{2}$, which is called the Riemann Hypothesis.[1]

Hardy and Littlewood later proved that infinitely many of the zeros of $\zeta(s)$ are on the critical line with real part of $s = \frac{1}{2}$. [2] It is well known that $\zeta(s)$ does not have non-trivial zeros when real part of $s = \frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega$, given by $\frac{1}{2} + \sigma \geq 1$ and $\frac{1}{2} + \sigma \leq 0$. In this paper, **critical strip** $0 < \text{Re}[s] < 1$ corresponds to $0 \leq |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$.

In this paper, a **new method** is discussed and a specific solution is presented to prove Riemann's Hypothesis. If the specific solution presented in this paper is incorrect, it is **hoped** that the new method discussed in this paper will lead to a correct solution by other researchers.

In Section 2 to Section 6, we prove Riemann's hypothesis by taking the analytic continuation of Riemann's Zeta Function derived from Riemann's Xi function $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega) = E_{p\omega}(\omega)$ and compute inverse Fourier transform of $E_{p\omega}(\omega)$ given by $E_p(t)$ and show that its Fourier transform $E_{p\omega}(\omega)$ does not have zeros for finite and real ω when $0 < |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$, corresponding to the critical strip **excluding** the critical line.

In Section 7, it is shown that the new method is **not** applicable to Hurwitz zeta function and related functions and **does not** contradict the existence of their non-trivial zeros away from the

critical line with real part of $s = \frac{1}{2}$.

We present an **outline** of the new method below.

1.1. Step 1: Inverse Fourier Transform of $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + i\omega)$

Let us start with Riemann's Xi Function $\xi(s)$ evaluated at $s = \frac{1}{2} + i\omega$ given by $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + i\omega) = \Xi(\omega) = E_{0\omega}(\omega)$, where ω is real. Its inverse Fourier Transform is given by $E_0(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} E_{0\omega}(\omega) e^{i\omega t} d\omega$, where ω, t are real, as follows (link).[3] (Titchmarsh pp254-255) We take the term $e^{\frac{t}{2}}$ out of the bracket and rearrange the terms as follows.

$$E_0(t) = \Phi(t) = 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [2n^4 \pi^2 e^{\frac{9t}{2}} - 3n^2 \pi e^{\frac{5t}{2}}] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t}] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} \quad (1)$$

We see that $E_0(t) = E_0(-t)$ is a real and **even** function of t , given that $E_{0\omega}(\omega) = E_{0\omega}(-\omega)$ because $\xi(s) = \xi(1-s)$ (link) and hence $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + i\omega) = \xi(\frac{1}{2} - i\omega)$ when evaluated at $s = \frac{1}{2} + i\omega$. (Details in Appendix C.6)

The inverse Fourier Transform of $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega) = E_{p\omega}(\omega)$ is given by the real function $E_p(t)$. We can write $E_p(t)$ as follows for $0 < |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$ and this is shown in detail in Appendix A.

$$E_p(t) = E_0(t) e^{-\sigma t} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t}] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} e^{-\sigma t} \quad (2)$$

We can see that $E_p(t)$ is an analytic function for real t , given that the sum and product of exponential functions are analytic for real t and hence infinitely differentiable for real t .

1.2. Step 2: On the zeros of a related function $G(\omega, t_0)$

Statement 1: Let us assume that Riemann's Xi function $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega) = E_{p\omega}(\omega)$ has a zero at $\omega = \omega_0$ where ω_0 is real and $0 < |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$, corresponding to the critical strip excluding the critical line. We will prove that this assumption leads to a **contradiction**.

Let us consider $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$ at first. Let us consider a new function $g(t, t_0) = f(t, t_0) e^{-\sigma t} u(-t) + f(t, t_0) e^{\sigma t} u(t)$, where $f(t, t_0) = e^{-\sigma t_0} E_0(t+t_0) e^{-\sigma t} + e^{\sigma t_0} E_0(t-t_0) e^{-\sigma t} + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) E_p(t)$ and $f_1(t, t_0) = e^{\sigma t_0} E_p(t+t_0)$ and $f_2(t, t_0) = f_1(t, -t_0)$ and t_0 is real and $g(t, t_0)$ is a real function of variable t and $u(t)$ is Heaviside unit step function. We can see that $g(t, t_0) h(t) = f(t, t_0)$ where $h(t) = [e^{\sigma t} u(-t) + e^{-\sigma t} u(t)]$.

In Section 2.1, we show that the Fourier transform of the **even function** $g_{even}(t, t_0) = \frac{1}{2} [g(t, t_0) + g(-t, t_0)]$ given by $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ must have **at least one zero** at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0) \neq 0$, for every value of $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$, where $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ crosses the zero line to the opposite sign, to satisfy Statement 1, where $\omega_z(t_0)$ is real.

1.3. Step 3: On the zeros of the function $G_R(\omega, t_0)$

In Section 2.3, we compute the Fourier transform of the function $g(t, t_0)$ and compute its real part given by $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ and we can write as follows.

$$G_R(\omega, t_0) = \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0)(e^{-\sigma t_0} e^{-2\sigma\tau} + e^{\sigma t_0}) \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \\ + \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau - t_0)(e^{\sigma t_0} e^{-2\sigma\tau} + e^{-\sigma t_0}) \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \quad (3)$$

We require $G_R(\omega, t_0) = 0$ for $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ for every value of t_0 , to satisfy **Statement 1**. In general $\omega_z(t_0) \neq \omega_0$. Hence we can see that $P(t_0) = G_R(\omega_z(t_0), t_0) = 0$.

1.4. Step 4: Zero Crossing function $\omega_z(t_0)$ is an even function of variable t_0

In Section 2.4, we show the result in Eq. 4 and that $\omega_z(t_0) = \omega_z(-t_0)$. It is shown that $P(t_0) = G_R(\omega_z(t_0), t_0) = P_{odd}(t_0) + P_{odd}(-t_0) = 0$ and that $P_{odd}(t_0)$ is an **odd** function of t_0 , as follows.

$$P_{odd}(t_0) = \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0)(e^{-\sigma t_0} e^{-2\sigma\tau} + e^{\sigma t_0}) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau + \cosh(\sigma t_0) \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau \quad (4)$$

1.5. Step 5: Final Step

In Section 4, it is shown that $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a **continuous** function of variable t_0 , for $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$. In Section 6, it is shown that $E_0(t)$ is **strictly decreasing** for $t > 0$.

In Section 3, we set $t_0 = t_{0c}$, such that $\omega_z(t_{0c})t_{0c} = \pi$ and substitute in the equation for $P_{odd}(t_0)$ in Eq. 4 and show the result in Eq. 5.

$$A(t_{0c}) = \int_0^{t_{0c}} E_0(\tau)(\sinh(\sigma t_{0c}) - \sinh(2\sigma\tau - \sigma t_{0c})) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau = 0 \quad (5)$$

We show that **each** of the terms in the integrand in Eq. 5 are **positive**, in the interval $0 < \tau < t_{0c}$ where $t_{0c} > 0$.

Hence the result in Eq. 5 leads to a **contradiction** for $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$.

We show this result for $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$ and then use the property $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega) = \xi(\frac{1}{2} - \sigma - i\omega)$ to show the result for $-\frac{1}{2} < \sigma < 0$. Hence we produce a **contradiction** of **Statement 1** that the Fourier Transform of the function $E_p(t) = E_0(t)e^{-\sigma t}$ has a zero at $\omega = \omega_0$ for $0 < |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$.

2. An Approach towards Riemann's Hypothesis

Theorem 1: Riemann's Xi function $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega) = E_{p\omega}(\omega)$ does not have zeros for any real value of ω , for $0 < |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$, corresponding to the critical strip excluding the critical line,

given that $E_0(t) = E_0(-t)$ is an even function of variable t , where $E_p(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} E_{p\omega}(\omega) e^{i\omega t} d\omega$, $E_p(t) = E_0(t) e^{-\sigma t}$ and $E_0(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t}] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}}$.

Proof: We assume that Riemann Hypothesis is false and prove its truth using proof by contradiction.

Statement 1: Let us assume that Riemann's Xi function $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega) = E_{p\omega}(\omega)$ has a zero at $\omega = \omega_0$ where ω_0 is real and $0 < |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$, corresponding to the critical strip excluding the critical line. We will prove that this assumption leads to a **contradiction**.

We will prove it for $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$ first and then use the property $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega) = \xi(\frac{1}{2} - \sigma - i\omega)$ to show the result for $-\frac{1}{2} < \sigma < 0$ and hence show the result for $0 < |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$.

We know that $\omega_0 \neq 0$, because $\zeta(s)$ has no zeros on the real axis between 0 and 1, when $s = \frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega$ is real, $\omega = 0$ and $0 \leq |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$. [3] (Titchmarsh pp30-31). This is shown in detail in first two paragraphs in Appendix C.1.

2.1. New function $g(t, t_0)$

We consider the function $E_p(t) = E_0(t) e^{-\sigma t}$ whose Fourier transform $E_{p\omega}(\omega)$ has a zero at $\omega = \omega_0$, using Statement 1. We consider the function $f_1(t, t_0) = e^{\sigma t_0} E_p(t + t_0)$ where $t_0 \in \Re$ is real, and its Fourier transform is given by $F_1(\omega, t_0) = E_{p\omega}(\omega) e^{\sigma t_0} e^{i\omega t_0}$ using linearity and time shift properties of the Fourier transform (link). We consider $f_2(t, t_0) = f_1(t, -t_0)$ and its Fourier transform is given by $F_2(\omega, t_0) = F_1(\omega, -t_0) = E_{p\omega}(\omega) e^{-\sigma t_0} e^{-i\omega t_0}$. (We call this **Result 2.1.a**)

We consider $f(t, t_0) = e^{-\sigma t_0} f_1(t, t_0) + e^{\sigma t_0} f_2(t, t_0) + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) E_p(t)$ and the Fourier Transform of this function $F(\omega, t_0) = e^{-\sigma t_0} F_1(\omega, t_0) + e^{\sigma t_0} F_2(\omega, t_0) + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) E_{p\omega}(\omega) = E_{p\omega}(\omega) [e^{-\sigma t_0} e^{\sigma t_0} e^{i\omega t_0} + e^{\sigma t_0} e^{-\sigma t_0} e^{-i\omega t_0} + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0)] = E_{p\omega}(\omega) [e^{i\omega t_0} + e^{-i\omega t_0} + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0)]$, using Result 2.1.a and $e^{\sigma t_0} e^{-\sigma t_0} = 1$. Hence $F(\omega, t_0) = E_{p\omega}(\omega) [2 \cos(\omega t_0) + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0)]$ also has a zero at the **same** $\omega = \omega_0$, using Statement 1. (**Result 2.1.b**).

We can write the above equations as follows. We use $e^{\sigma t_0} e^{-\sigma t_0} = 1$ below. We see that $f_2(t, t_0) = f_1(t, -t_0)$ and $f(t, t_0) = f(t, -t_0)$ (**Result 2.1.c**) as shown below.

$$\begin{aligned} E_p(t) &= E_0(t) e^{-\sigma t} \\ f_1(t, t_0) &= e^{\sigma t_0} E_p(t + t_0) = e^{\sigma t_0} E_0(t + t_0) e^{-\sigma t} e^{-\sigma t_0} \\ f_2(t, t_0) &= f_1(t, -t_0) = e^{-\sigma t_0} E_0(t - t_0) e^{-\sigma t} e^{\sigma t_0} \\ f(t, t_0) &= e^{-\sigma t_0} f_1(t, t_0) + e^{\sigma t_0} f_2(t, t_0) + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) E_p(t) \\ f(t, t_0) &= e^{-\sigma t_0} E_0(t + t_0) e^{-\sigma t} + e^{\sigma t_0} E_0(t - t_0) e^{-\sigma t} + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) E_p(t) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

We consider a new function $g(t, t_0) = f(t, t_0) e^{-\sigma t} u(-t) + f(t, t_0) e^{\sigma t} u(t)$ where $g(t, t_0)$ is a real function of variable t and $u(t)$ is Heaviside unit step function. We see that $g(t, t_0) h(t) = f(t, t_0)$ where $h(t) = [e^{\sigma t} u(-t) + e^{-\sigma t} u(t)]$. We note that $f(0, t_0) = 4E_0(t) e^{-\sigma t}$ and $g(0, t_0) = f(0, t_0) e^{-\sigma t} u(-t) + f(0, t_0) e^{\sigma t} u(t)$ and hence $f(t, t_0)$ and $g(t, t_0)$ are **non-zero** at $t_0 = 0$.

$$\begin{aligned} g(t, t_0) &= [f(t, t_0) e^{-\sigma t}] u(-t) + [f(t, t_0) e^{\sigma t}] u(t) \\ g(t, t_0) h(t) &= f(t, t_0), \quad h(t) = e^{\sigma t} u(-t) + e^{-\sigma t} u(t) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

We can show that $E_p(t), h(t)$ are absolutely integrable functions and go to zero as $|t| \rightarrow \infty$. Hence their respective Fourier transforms given by $E_{p\omega}(\omega), H(\omega)$ are finite for real ω and go to zero as $|\omega| \rightarrow \infty$, as per Riemann Lebesgue Lemma (link). We can show that $E_0(t)$ and $E_0(t)e^{-2\sigma t}$ are absolutely **integrable** functions. These results are shown in Appendix C.1.

In Section 2.3 and Section 2.4, it is shown that $g(t, t_0) = e^{-\sigma t_0}g_1(t, t_0) + e^{\sigma t_0}g_2(t, t_0) + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0)g_3(t)$ is a Fourier transformable function and its Fourier transform given by $G(\omega, t_0) = e^{-\sigma t_0}G_1(\omega, t_0) + e^{\sigma t_0}G_2(\omega, t_0) + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0)G_3(\omega)$ converges. (Eq. 19 and Eq. 21)

We take the Fourier transform of the equation $g(t, t_0)h(t) = f(t, t_0)$ where $h(t) = e^{\sigma t}u(-t) + e^{-\sigma t}u(t)$ and get $\frac{1}{2\pi}[G(\omega, t_0) * H(\omega)] = F(\omega, t_0) = E_{p\omega}(\omega)[2 \cos(\omega t_0) + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0)] = F_R(\omega, t_0) + iF_I(\omega, t_0)$ as per **convolution theorem** (link), and Result 2.1.b, where $*$ denotes convolution operation given by $F(\omega, t_0) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} G(\omega', t_0)H(\omega - \omega')d\omega'$. (**Result 2.1.d**)

We see that $H(\omega) = H_R(\omega) = [\frac{1}{\sigma - i\omega} + \frac{1}{\sigma + i\omega}] = \frac{2\sigma}{(\sigma^2 + \omega^2)}$ is real and is the Fourier transform of the function $h(t)$ (link). $G(\omega, t_0) = G_R(\omega, t_0) + iG_I(\omega, t_0)$ is the Fourier transform of the function $g(t, t_0)$. We can write $g(t, t_0) = g_{even}(t, t_0) + g_{odd}(t, t_0)$ where $g_{even}(t, t_0)$ is an even function and $g_{odd}(t, t_0)$ is an odd function of variable t .

If Statement 1 is true, then we require the Fourier transform of the function $f(t, t_0)$ given by $F(\omega, t_0)$ to have a zero at $\omega = \omega_0$ for **every value** of t_0 , using Result 2.1.b. This implies that the **real part** of the Fourier transform of the **even function** $g_{even}(t, t_0) = \frac{1}{2}[g(t, t_0) + g(-t, t_0)]$ given by $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ (Details in Appendix D.2 and link) must have **at least one zero** at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0) \neq 0$ where $\omega_z(t_0)$ is real, where $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ crosses the zero line to the opposite sign, explained below. We note that $\omega_z(t_0)$ can be different from ω_0 in general.

Because $H(\omega) = \frac{2\sigma}{(\sigma^2 + \omega^2)}$ is real and does not have zeros for any finite value of ω , **if** $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ does not have at least one zero for some $\omega = \omega_z(t_0) \neq 0$, where $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ crosses the zero line to the opposite sign, **then the real part** of $F(\omega, t_0)$ given by $F_R(\omega, t_0) = \frac{1}{2\pi}[G_R(\omega, t_0) * H(\omega)]$, obtained by the convolution of $H(\omega)$ and $G_R(\omega, t_0)$, **cannot** possibly have zeros for any non-zero finite value of ω , which contradicts Result 2.1.b and **Statement 1**. This is shown in detail in Lemma 1.

The proof for Lemma 1 below is shown for **a fixed value** of $t_0 = t_{0f}$, for $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$ (**Interval A**). The proof continues to hold for our choice of **each fixed value** of t_0 in interval A.

Lemma 1: Let $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$ be fixed value and $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega) = E_{p\omega}(\omega)$ has a zero at $\omega = \omega_0$ using Statement 1. Then the real part of the Fourier transform of the **even function** $g_{even}(t, t_0)$ given by $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ must have **at least one zero** at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0) \neq 0$, where $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ crosses the zero line to the opposite sign and $\omega_z(t_0)$ is real.

Proof: If $E_{p\omega}(\omega)$ has a zero at $\omega = \omega_0$ to satisfy Statement 1, then $F(\omega, t_0)$ has a zero at $\omega = \omega_0$, using Result 2.1.b and its real part given by $F_R(\omega, t_0)$ has a zero at $\omega = \omega_0$ (**Result 2.1.e**). We see that $\omega_0 \neq 0$ in para 5 of Section 2.

We do not have a closed form solution for $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ and do not know the exact location of its zeros at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$. For a specific choice of t_0 , **only one** of the 2 cases is possible:

Case A: $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ does not have a zero crossing for any choice of $\omega \neq 0$ or

Case B: $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ has at least one zero crossing for a specific $\omega \neq 0$.

If Statement 1 is true, **then** Case B is the **only** possibility and Case A is **ruled out**, as shown below.

We want to show the **Result 2.1.h** that $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ **must have at least one** zero crossing at **some value** of $\omega = \omega_z(t_0) \neq 0$ (**Case B**), to satisfy **Statement 1**, for this choice of fixed t_0 .

To show Result 2.1.h, we **assume the opposite Case A**, that $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ **does not** have at least one zero for **any** value of $\omega \neq 0$, where $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ crosses the zero line to the opposite sign (zero crossing) and will show that $F_R(\omega, t_0)$ does not have at least one zero at finite $\omega \neq 0$ for this case, which **contradicts** Result 2.1.e and Statement 1 and hence we **rule out** Case A and arrive at Case B, in the following Proof of Lemma 1. (Case B is the same as Result 2.1.h).

This **does not** mean that, proof of Lemma 1 will work **only if** $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ does not have a zero crossing for any value of $\omega \neq 0$, for any choice of t_0 . The device **Proof by Contradiction** is used here to **rule out** Case A and arrive at Case B. (Details of other cases in Section 2.1.1 and Section 2.1.2)

It is noted that, for **Case B**, we **do not** use Eq. 8 to Eq. 11 and related arguments, because Case B is the desired Result 2.1.h. (**Result 2.1.f**)

The arguments above and following proof continue to hold for our choice of **each fixed value** of t_0 in interval A.

Given that $H(\omega)$ is real, using Result 2.1.d, we write the convolution theorem only for the real parts as follows.

$$F_R(\omega, t_0) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} G_R(\omega', t_0) H(\omega - \omega') d\omega' \quad (8)$$

We can show that the above integral converges for real ω , given that the integrand is absolutely integrable because $G_R(\omega', t_0) H(\omega - \omega')$ has a minimum fall-off rate of $\frac{1}{\omega^2}$ as $|\omega| \rightarrow \infty$ because the first derivative of $h(t)$ is discontinuous at $t = 0$. (Details in Appendix C.2 and Appendix C.4)

We substitute $H(\omega) = \frac{2\sigma}{(\sigma^2 + \omega^2)}$ in Eq. 8 and we get

$$F_R(\omega, t_0) = \frac{\sigma}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} G_R(\omega', t_0) \frac{1}{(\sigma^2 + (\omega - \omega')^2)} d\omega' \quad (9)$$

We can split the integral in Eq. 9 using $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} = \int_{-\infty}^0 + \int_0^{\infty}$, as follows.

$$F_R(\omega, t_0) = \frac{\sigma}{\pi} \left[\int_{-\infty}^0 G_R(\omega', t_0) \frac{1}{(\sigma^2 + (\omega - \omega')^2)} d\omega' + \int_0^{\infty} G_R(\omega', t_0) \frac{1}{(\sigma^2 + (\omega - \omega')^2)} d\omega' \right] \quad (10)$$

We see that $G_R(-\omega, t_0) = G_R(\omega, t_0)$ because $g(t, t_0)$ is a real function of variable t . (Details in Appendix D.1 and link) We substitute $\omega' = -\omega''$ and $d\omega' = -d\omega''$ in the first integral in Eq. 10 and substituting $\omega'' = \omega'$ in the result, we can write as follows.

$$F_R(\omega, t_0) = \frac{\sigma}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} G_R(\omega', t_0) \left[\frac{1}{(\sigma^2 + (\omega + \omega')^2)} + \frac{1}{(\sigma^2 + (\omega - \omega')^2)} \right] d\omega' \quad (11)$$

We note that $G_R(\omega', t_0)$ is a function of ω' **only**, for a given choice of t_0 and the integrand in Eq. 11 is integrated over the variable ω' **only**.

We see that $G_R(\omega', t_0)$ converges for real ω' (Eq. 19 and Eq. 22). As $\omega' \rightarrow \infty$, the term $\frac{1}{(\sigma^2+(\omega+\omega')^2)} + \frac{1}{(\sigma^2+(\omega-\omega')^2)}$ and the integrand in Eq. 11 goes to zero. For finite $\omega \geq 0$ and finite $\omega' \geq 0$, we can see that the term $\frac{1}{(\sigma^2+(\omega+\omega')^2)} + \frac{1}{(\sigma^2+(\omega-\omega')^2)} = \frac{2(\sigma^2+\omega^2+\omega'^2)}{(\sigma^2+(\omega+\omega')^2)(\sigma^2+(\omega-\omega')^2)} > 0$, for $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$. We see that $G_R(\omega', t_0)$ is **not** an all zero function of variable ω' (Details in Section 2.2). (**Result 2.1.g**)

- **Case 1:** $G_R(\omega', t_0) \geq 0$ for all finite $\omega' \geq 0$

We see that $F_R(\omega, t_0) > 0$ for all finite $\omega > 0$, using Result 2.1.g. We see that $F_R(-\omega, t_0) = F_R(\omega, t_0)$ because $f(t, t_0)$ is a real function (Appendix D.1) and link). Hence $F_R(\omega, t_0) > 0$ for all finite $\omega < 0$.

This **contradicts** Statement 1 and Result 2.1.e which requires $F_R(\omega, t_0)$ to have at least one zero at finite $\omega \neq 0$. Therefore $G_R(\omega', t_0)$ must have **at least one zero** at $\omega' = \omega_z(t_0) > 0$ where it crosses the zero line and becomes negative, where $\omega_z(t_0)$ is finite.

- **Case 2:** $G_R(\omega', t_0) \leq 0$ for all finite $\omega' \geq 0$

We see that $F_R(\omega, t_0) < 0$ for all finite $\omega > 0$, using Result 2.1.g. We see that $F_R(-\omega, t_0) = F_R(\omega, t_0)$ because $f(t, t_0)$ is a real function (Appendix D.1) and link). Hence $F_R(\omega, t_0) < 0$ for all finite $\omega < 0$.

This **contradicts** Statement 1 and Result 2.1.e which requires $F_R(\omega, t_0)$ to have at least one zero at finite $\omega \neq 0$. Therefore $G_R(\omega', t_0)$ must have **at least one zero** at $\omega' = \omega_z(t_0) > 0$, where it crosses the zero line and becomes positive, where $\omega_z(t_0)$ is finite.

We have shown that, $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ must have **at least one zero** at finite $\omega = \omega_z(t_0) \neq 0$ where it crosses the zero line to the opposite sign, to satisfy **Statement 1**, for specific choices of fixed t_0 . We call this **Result 2.1.h**.

Points to be Noted:

- The arguments above and the proof continue to hold for our choice of **each fixed value** of t_0 in Interval A ($t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$).

- We consider the case where zeros of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ come from t_0 alone, for specific choice of t_0 . For this case, $G_R(\omega, t_0) = 0$ for all ω , for that specific choice of t_0 . But we see that $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ is **not** an all zero function of variable ω , as shown in Section 2.2. It is shown in Note 1 in Section 4.7.1 that the zeros of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ are **isolated**. This **rules out** the case where zeros of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ come from t_0 alone. This means that, if Statement 1 is true, then $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ must have at least one zero crossing at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$, **due to a term** related to ω .

- Note that $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a **dependent** function of t_0 , given that $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ may be different for different choices of t_0 and hence the zero crossing point $\omega_z(t_0)$ may be different for different choices of t_0 .

This means that, we fix $t_0 = t_{0f}$ in Pass 1 and use Lemma 1 to show that $\omega_z(t_{0f}) \neq 0$ for **that specific** choice of t_0 and $G_R(\omega, t_{0f})$. In Pass 2, we use a **different choice** of $t_0 = t'_{0f}$ and use Lemma 1 to show that $\omega_z(t'_{0f}) \neq 0$ for that specific **different** choice of t_0 and $G_R(\omega, t'_{0f})$. In general, $G_R(\omega, t_{0f}) \neq G_R(\omega, t'_{0f})$ and hence the zero crossing point $\omega_z(t_{0f}) \neq \omega_z(t'_{0f})$. This argument holds for Pass 1, 2 to Pass N, for **each** value of t_0 in Interval A.

In general, $\omega_z(t_{0f}) \neq \omega_z(t'_{0f})$ in Lemma 1. But the specific case of $\omega_z(t_0)$ equals a constant for all t_0 is allowed in Lemma 1 and this constant $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a **continuous function** of t_0 and there is **no need** for using Implicit Function Theorem (IFT) in Section 4.

- We do not have a closed form solution for $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ and do not know the exact location of its zeros at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$, for each fixed choice of t_0 . This problem **exists** in the case of $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + i\omega) = \Xi(\omega) = E_{0\omega}(\omega)$ **also** (see Eq. B.1 in Appendix B) given that we **do not** have a closed form solution for $\Xi(\omega)$ and **do not** know the exact location of its zeros. **Despite** this problem, Hardy and Littlewood were able to prove that infinitely many of the zeros of $\xi(s)$ and $\zeta(s)$ are on the critical line with real part of $s = \frac{1}{2}$. [2]

Similarly, it is shown in proof of Lemma 1 that $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ must have **at least one zero** at finite $\omega = \omega_z(t_0) \neq 0$ where it crosses the zero line to the opposite sign, to satisfy **Statement 1** and this is sufficient to prove Theorem 1, **despite** this problem with $G_R(\omega, t_0)$.

- In the rest of the sections, we consider only the **first** zero crossing to the right of origin, where $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ crosses the zero line to the opposite sign. Hence $0 < \omega_z(t_0) < \infty$, for $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$, to satisfy **Statement 1**.

2.1.1. Discussion of Lemma 1

Result 2.1.h: $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ must have **at least one zero** at finite $\omega = \omega_z(t_0) \neq 0$ where it crosses the zero line to the opposite sign, to satisfy **Statement 1**.

For each **fixed** value of t_0 , only 2 cases are possible for $G_R(\omega, t_0)$. **Case A:** $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ does not have a zero crossing for any choice of $\omega \neq 0$. **Case B:** $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ has at least one zero crossing for a specific $\omega \neq 0$. Proof of Lemma 1 assumes Case A and uses **Proof by Contradiction** to rule out Case A and arrive at Case B, for each choice of fixed t_0 . This does not mean that Proof of Lemma 1 does not work for Case B. For Case B, we **do not** use Proof of Lemma 1 and jump to the end of the proof because we already have the desired Result 2.1.h which is the same as Case B.

The logic used in this proof is as follows: **If** Statement 1 is true (RH is false), **then** Result 2.1.h is true (Case B), for **each fixed** value of t_0 in interval A ($t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$) and hence Case A is **ruled out** and only Case B is possible for $G_R(\omega, t_0)$. Then we proceed with Result 2.1.h to Section 2.3, 2.4 and Section 3, to produce a **contradiction** of Statement 1 in Eq. 37 and thus prove the truth of RH.

2.1.2. Discussion of all possible cases of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$

We analyze all possible cases of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ below. We can arrive at Result 2.1.h in **Lemma 1** in Section 2.1, for **each fixed** value of t_0 in interval A ($t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$), using Proof of Lemma 1 for Case C

and Case D or using Case E, as explained below.

It is noted that $F_R(\omega, t_0)$ and $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ may have more zeros than $F(\omega, t_0)$ and $G(\omega, t_0)$ respectively. That **does not** affect the proof of Lemma 1, as explained below.

We consider 3 possible cases of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ below.

- **Case C:** We consider the case that $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ **does not** have a zero crossing, for any value of $\omega \neq 0$, for **each and every** choice of t_0 in Interval A and we assume Statement 1 and use Proof of Lemma 1 for each and every choice of t_0 , to show that it leads to a **contradiction** of Statement 1, and hence prove Result 2.1.h, for each and every choice of t_0 .

Hence Case C is **ruled out**, if Statement 1 is true. (**Result 2.1.2.c**)

- **Case D:** We consider the case $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ has at least one zero crossing at finite $\omega = \omega_z(t_0) \neq 0$, for **specific** choices of $t_0 = t'_0$, but **not** for all possible choices of t_0 .

For Case D, this means that $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ has **at least one zero crossing** at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$, for **specific** choices of $t_0 = t'_0$, which is the desired **Result 2.1.h** and hence we **do not** go through the arguments in this proof and we can jump to end of Proof of Lemma 1 (using Result 2.1.f in Proof of Lemma 1). In this case, we **have not** assumed Statement 1 and yet arrived at Result 2.1.h, for **specific** choices of $t_0 = t'_0$.

For Case D, there is **at least one** choice of $t_0 = t_{0f}$ for which $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ **does not** have a zero crossing, for any value of $\omega \neq 0$. For this choice of $t_0 = t_{0f}$, we assume Statement 1 and use Proof of Lemma 1 to show that it leads to a **contradiction** of Statement 1, and hence prove Result 2.1.h.

Hence Case D is **ruled out**, if Statement 1 is true. (**Result 2.1.2.d**)

- **Case E:** We consider the case $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ has at least one zero crossing at finite $\omega = \omega_z(t_0) \neq 0$, for **each and every** value of t_0 in Interval A. This is the same as Result 2.1.h, for **each and every** value of t_0 in Interval A.

There are **only 3** possible cases for $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ given by Case C,D and E. **If** Statement 1 is true, Case C and Case D have been **ruled out** using Result 2.1.2.c and Result 2.1.2.d. This leaves only Case E, which is the same as Result 2.1.h. Then we proceed with Result 2.1.h to Section 2.3, 2.4 and Section 3, to produce a **contradiction** of Statement 1 in Eq. 37.

Thus we have produced a **contradiction** of **Statement 1** that the Fourier Transform of the function $E_p(t) = E_0(t)e^{-\sigma t}$ has a zero at $\omega = \omega_0$ for $0 < |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$ and hence prove the truth of Riemann's Hypothesis.

- We can also consider Case E, **without** assuming Statement 1. This is the same as Result 2.1.h, for **each and every** value of t_0 in Interval A. Then we proceed with Result 2.1.h to Section 2.3, 2.4 and Section 3, to produce a **contradiction** of this Case E in Eq. 37. Hence this Case E is **ruled out**. (**Result 2.1.2.e**)

There are **only 3** possible cases for $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ given by Case C,D and E. We have ruled out Case

E using Result 2.1.2.e. This leaves only Case C and Case D for $G_R(\omega, t_0)$. **If** Statement 1 is true, Case C and Case D have been **ruled out** using Result 2.1.2.c and Result 2.1.2.d. Given that Case C,D and E are the **only 3** possible cases for $G_R(\omega, t_0)$, this means **Statement 1 is false**.

2.2. $G_R(\omega', t_0)$ is not an all zero function of variable ω'

If $G_R(\omega', t_0) = 0$ for all values of real ω' , for a **specific** choice of $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$ (**Statement 2**), then $F_R(\omega, t_0)$ in Eq. 8 is an all zero function of ω , for real ω . Hence $2f_{even}(t, t_0) = f(t, t_0) + f(-t, t_0) = 0$ for all values of real t , given that the Fourier transform of $f_{even}(t, t_0)$ is given by $F_R(\omega, t_0)$, using symmetry properties of Fourier transform(Appendix D.2) and link). Hence $f(t, t_0) = f_{even}(t, t_0) + f_{odd}(t, t_0) = f_{odd}(t, t_0)$ is an **odd function** of variable t and hence $f(t, t_0) = -f(-t, t_0)$. (**Result 2.2**)

We copy $f(t, t_0)$ from Eq. 6 and write as follows, using $E_p(t) = E_0(t)e^{-\sigma t}$.

$$f(t, t_0) = e^{-\sigma t_0} E_0(t + t_0) e^{-\sigma t} + e^{\sigma t_0} E_0(t - t_0) e^{-\sigma t} + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) E_0(t) e^{-\sigma t} \quad (12)$$

For $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$, it is shown that Result 2.2 is false. We will compute $f(t, t_0)$ in Eq. 12 at $t = 0$ and show that it does not equal zero.

We see that $f(0, t_0) = e^{-\sigma t_0} E_0(t_0) + e^{\sigma t_0} E_0(-t_0) + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) E_0(0) = 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) E_0(t_0) + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) E_0(0) = 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) [E_0(t_0) + E_0(0)]$. We use the fact that $E_0(t_0) = E_0(-t_0)$ (Details in Appendix C.6).

If Result 2.2 is true, then we require $f(0, t_0) = 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) [E_0(t_0) + E_0(0)] = 0$. For our choice of $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$ and $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$, we see that $E_0(t_0) > 0$ and $E_0(0) > 0$ using Appendix C.5 and hence $f(0, t_0) > 0$ for $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$. Hence Result 2.2 is false and Statement 2 is false, for any specific choice of $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$ and $G_R(\omega', t_0)$ is **not** an all zero function of variable ω' .

Hence $G_R(\omega', t_0)$ is **not** an all zero function of variable ω' , for any choice of $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$.

2.3. On the zeros of a related function $G(\omega, t_0)$

In this section, we compute the Fourier transform of the function $g_{even}(t, t_0) = \frac{1}{2}[g(t, t_0) + g(-t, t_0)]$ given by $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ (using Appendix D.2). We require $G_R(\omega, t_0) = 0$ for $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ for **every value** of t_0 , to satisfy **Statement 1**, using Lemma 1 in Section 2.1.

From Eq. 6, we see that $f(t, t_0) = e^{-\sigma t_0} f_1(t, t_0) + e^{\sigma t_0} f_2(t, t_0) + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) E_p(t)$ and $g(t, t_0) h(t) = f(t, t_0)$ where $h(t) = [e^{\sigma t} u(-t) + e^{-\sigma t} u(t)]$. We get $g(t, t_0) = \frac{f(t, t_0)}{h(t)} = e^{-\sigma t_0} \frac{f_1(t, t_0)}{h(t)} + e^{\sigma t_0} \frac{f_2(t, t_0)}{h(t)} + \frac{2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) E_p(t)}{h(t)}$. We **define** $g_1(t, t_0) = \frac{f_1(t, t_0)}{h(t)}$ and $g_2(t, t_0) = \frac{f_2(t, t_0)}{h(t)}$ and $g_3(t) = \frac{E_p(t)}{h(t)}$ and get $g(t, t_0) = e^{-\sigma t_0} g_1(t, t_0) + e^{\sigma t_0} g_2(t, t_0) + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) g_3(t)$. (**Result 2.3.a**)

We get $g_3(t) = E_p(t) e^{-\sigma t} u(-t) + E_p(t) e^{\sigma t} u(t)$. We compute the Fourier transform of the function

$g_3(t)$ given by $G_3(\omega) = G_{3R}(\omega) + iG_{3I}(\omega)$ as follows. We use $E_p(t) = E_0(t)e^{-\sigma t}$.

$$\begin{aligned} G_3(\omega) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g_3(t)e^{-i\omega t} dt = \int_{-\infty}^0 g_3(t)e^{-i\omega t} dt + \int_0^{\infty} g_3(t)e^{-i\omega t} dt \\ G_3(\omega) &= \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(t)e^{-\sigma t}e^{-\sigma t}e^{-i\omega t} dt + \int_0^{\infty} E_0(t)e^{-\sigma t}e^{\sigma t}e^{-i\omega t} dt \\ G_3(\omega) &= \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(t)e^{-2\sigma t}e^{-i\omega t} dt + \int_0^{\infty} E_0(t)e^{-i\omega t} dt \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

We substitute $t = -t$ in the second integral in Eq. 13. We use $-\int_0^{-\infty} = \int_{-\infty}^0$.

$$G_3(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(t)e^{-2\sigma t}e^{-i\omega t} dt + \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(-t)e^{i\omega t} dt \quad (14)$$

We use $E_0(t) = E_0(-t)$ from Appendix C.6 and write Eq. 14 as follows. The integral in Eq. 15 converges, given that $E_0(t)e^{-2\sigma t}$ is an absolutely **integrable** function. (Details in Appendix C.1)

$$G_3(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(t)e^{-2\sigma t}e^{-i\omega t} dt + \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(t)e^{i\omega t} dt = G_{3R}(\omega) + iG_{3I}(\omega) \quad (15)$$

The above equations can be expanded as follows using the identity $e^{i\omega t} = \cos(\omega t) + i\sin(\omega t)$. Comparing the **real parts** of $G_3(\omega)$, we have

$$G_{3R}(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(t)e^{-2\sigma t} \cos(\omega t) dt + \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(t) \cos(\omega t) dt = \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(t)(e^{-2\sigma t} + 1) \cos(\omega t) dt \quad (16)$$

2.3.1. **Fourier transform of $g_1(t, t_0)$**

Using $g_1(t, t_0) = \frac{f_1(t, t_0)}{h(t)}$ in Result 2.3.a, we get $g_1(t, t_0) = f_1(t, t_0)e^{-\sigma t}u(-t) + f_1(t, t_0)e^{\sigma t}u(t)$, where $f_1(t, t_0) = E_0(t + t_0)e^{-\sigma t}$, using Eq. 6. Then we compute the Fourier transform of the function $g_1(t, t_0)$ given by $G_1(\omega, t_0) = G_{1R}(\omega, t_0) + iG_{1I}(\omega, t_0)$ as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} G_1(\omega, t_0) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g_1(t, t_0)e^{-i\omega t} dt = \int_{-\infty}^0 g_1(t, t_0)e^{-i\omega t} dt + \int_0^{\infty} g_1(t, t_0)e^{-i\omega t} dt \\ G_1(\omega, t_0) &= \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(t + t_0)e^{-\sigma t}e^{-\sigma t}e^{-i\omega t} dt + \int_0^{\infty} E_0(t + t_0)e^{-\sigma t}e^{\sigma t}e^{-i\omega t} dt \\ G_1(\omega, t_0) &= \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(t + t_0)e^{-2\sigma t}e^{-i\omega t} dt + \int_0^{\infty} E_0(t + t_0)e^{-i\omega t} dt \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

We substitute $t = -t$ in the second integral in Eq. 17. We use $-\int_0^{-\infty} = \int_{-\infty}^0$.

$$G_1(\omega, t_0) = \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(t + t_0)e^{-2\sigma t}e^{-i\omega t} dt + \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(-t + t_0)e^{i\omega t} dt \quad (18)$$

We use $E_0(t) = E_0(-t)$ from Appendix C.6 and get $E_0(-t + t_0) = E_0(t - t_0)$ and write Eq. 18 as follows. The integral in Eq. 19 converges, given that $E_0(t)e^{-2\sigma t}$ is an absolutely **integrable** function and its t_0 shifted versions are absolutely **integrable**. (Details in Appendix C.1)

$$G_1(\omega, t_0) = \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(t + t_0)e^{-2\sigma t}e^{-i\omega t} dt + \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(t - t_0)e^{i\omega t} dt = G_{1R}(\omega, t_0) + iG_{1I}(\omega, t_0) \quad (19)$$

The above equations can be expanded as follows using the identity $e^{i\omega t} = \cos(\omega t) + i \sin(\omega t)$. Comparing the **real parts** of $G_1(\omega, t_0)$, we have

$$G_{1_R}(\omega, t_0) = \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(t + t_0)e^{-2\sigma t} \cos(\omega t)dt + \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(t - t_0) \cos(\omega t)dt \quad (20)$$

2.4. Zero crossing function $\omega_z(t_0)$ is an even function of variable t_0

Using $g_2(t, t_0) = \frac{f_2(t, t_0)}{h(t)}$ in Result 2.3.a, we get $g_2(t, t_0) = f_2(t, t_0)e^{-\sigma t}u(-t) + f_2(t, t_0)e^{\sigma t}u(t)$ (**Result 2.4.a**), where $f_2(t, t_0) = f_1(t, -t_0) = E_0(t - t_0)e^{-\sigma t}$, using Eq. 6 and Result 2.1.c in Section 2.1. We compute the Fourier transform of the function $g_2(t, t_0)$ given by $G_2(\omega, t_0) = G_1(\omega, -t_0)$, given that $f_2(t, t_0) = f_1(t, -t_0)$ using Result 2.1.c in Section 2.1 and hence $g_2(t, t_0) = g_1(t, -t_0)$ using Result 2.4.a and hence $G_2(\omega, t_0) = G_1(\omega, -t_0)$.

We compute the Fourier transform of the function $g(t, t_0) = e^{-\sigma t_0}g_1(t, t_0) + e^{\sigma t_0}g_2(t, t_0) + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0)g_3(t)$ in Result 2.3.a, given by $G(\omega, t_0)$, and compute its real part $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ using the procedure in Section 2.3, similar to Eq. 16 and Eq. 20 and we can write as follows in Eq. 21. We substitute $t = \tau$ in the equation for $G_{3_R}(\omega)$ and $G_{1_R}(\omega, t_0)$ below, copied from Eq. 16 and Eq. 20.

$$\begin{aligned} G_R(\omega, t_0) &= e^{-\sigma t_0}G_{1_R}(\omega, t_0) + e^{\sigma t_0}G_{2_R}(\omega, t_0) + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0)G_{3_R}(\omega) \\ &= e^{-\sigma t_0}G_{1_R}(\omega, t_0) + e^{\sigma t_0}G_{1_R}(\omega, -t_0) + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0)G_{3_R}(\omega) \\ G_{3_R}(\omega) &= \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega\tau)d\tau \\ G_{1_R}(\omega, t_0) &= \left[\int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0)e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau)d\tau + \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau - t_0) \cos(\omega\tau)d\tau \right] \\ G_R(\omega, t_0) &= e^{-\sigma t_0} \left[\int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0)e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau)d\tau + \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau - t_0) \cos(\omega\tau)d\tau \right] \\ &\quad + e^{\sigma t_0} \left[\int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau - t_0)e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau)d\tau + \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0) \cos(\omega\tau)d\tau \right] \\ &\quad + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega\tau)d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

We combine first and fourth integrals and then combine third and second integrals in $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ in Eq. 21, as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} G_R(\omega, t_0) &= \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0)(e^{-\sigma t_0}e^{-2\sigma\tau} + e^{\sigma t_0}) \cos(\omega\tau)d\tau \\ &\quad + \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau - t_0)(e^{\sigma t_0}e^{-2\sigma\tau} + e^{-\sigma t_0}) \cos(\omega\tau)d\tau + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega\tau)d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

We require $G_R(\omega, t_0) = 0$ for $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ for every value of t_0 , to satisfy **Statement 1**, using Lemma 1 in Section 2.1. Hence we write $P(t_0) = G_R(\omega_z(t_0), t_0) = 0$ as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} P(t_0) &= \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0)(e^{-\sigma t_0}e^{-2\sigma\tau} + e^{\sigma t_0}) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)d\tau \\ &\quad + \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau - t_0)(e^{\sigma t_0}e^{-2\sigma\tau} + e^{-\sigma t_0}) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)d\tau + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)d\tau = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

We use the fact that $f(t, t_0) = e^{-\sigma t_0} E_0(t + t_0) e^{-\sigma t} + e^{\sigma t_0} E_0(t - t_0) e^{-\sigma t} + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) E_p(t) = f(t, -t_0)$ in Eq. 6, is **unchanged** by the substitution $t_0 = -t_0$. **If** $f(t, t_0) = f(t, -t_0)$ is unchanged by the substitution $t_0 = -t_0$, **then** $g(t, t_0) = g(t, -t_0)$ is unchanged by the substitution $t_0 = -t_0$, using the fact that $g(t, t_0)h(t) = f(t, t_0)$ and $h(t) = [e^{\sigma t} u(-t) + e^{-\sigma t} u(t)]$ in Eq. 6.

Hence the Fourier transform of $g(t, t_0)$ given by $G(\omega, t_0) = G(\omega, -t_0)$ and its real part given by $G_R(\omega, t_0) = G_R(\omega, -t_0)$ is **unchanged** by the substitution $t_0 = -t_0$ and the zero crossing in $G_R(\omega, -t_0)$ given by $\omega_z(-t_0)$ is the **same** as the zero crossing in $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ given by $\omega_z(t_0)$ and we get $\omega_z(t_0) = \omega_z(-t_0)$ and hence $\omega_z(t_0)$ is an **even** function of variable t_0 . (**Result 2.4.b**)

We can write Eq. 23 as follows, where $P_{odd}(t_0)$ is an **odd** function of variable t_0 . We use $\omega_z(t_0) = \omega_z(-t_0)$ and $D(t_0) = D(-t_0) = \cosh(\sigma t_0) \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau) (e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau$. (**Result 2.4.c**)

$$P(t_0) = P_{odd}(t_0) + P_{odd}(-t_0) = 0$$

$$P_{odd}(t_0) = \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0) (e^{-\sigma t_0} e^{-2\sigma\tau} + e^{\sigma t_0}) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau + D(t_0) \quad (24)$$

3. Final Step

We expand $P_{odd}(t_0)$ in Eq. 24 as follows, using the substitution $\tau + t_0 = \tau'$. We get $\tau = \tau' - t_0$ and $d\tau = d\tau'$ and substitute back $\tau' = \tau$ in the second line below. We use $e^{-\sigma t_0} e^{2\sigma t_0} = e^{\sigma t_0}$ and use the identity $\cos(\omega_z(t_0)(\tau - t_0)) = \cos(\omega_z(t_0)t_0) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) + \sin(\omega_z(t_0)t_0) \sin(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)$ below.

$$P_{odd}(t_0) = \int_{-\infty}^{t_0} E_0(\tau') [e^{-\sigma t_0} e^{-2\sigma\tau'} e^{2\sigma t_0} + e^{\sigma t_0}] \cos(\omega_z(t_0)(\tau' - t_0)) d\tau' + D(t_0)$$

$$P_{odd}(t_0) = [\cos(\omega_z(t_0)t_0) \int_{-\infty}^{t_0} E_0(\tau) (e^{\sigma t_0} e^{-2\sigma\tau} + e^{\sigma t_0}) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau$$

$$+ \sin(\omega_z(t_0)t_0) \int_{-\infty}^{t_0} E_0(\tau) (e^{\sigma t_0} e^{-2\sigma\tau} + e^{\sigma t_0}) \sin(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau] + D(t_0) \quad (25)$$

In Lemma 1 in Section 2.1, it is shown that $0 < \omega_z(t_0) < \infty$, for $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$.

In Section 4, it is shown that $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a **continuous** function of variable t_0 , for $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$.

In Section 6, it is shown that $E_0(t)$ is **strictly decreasing** for $t > 0$.

Given that $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a continuous function of t_0 and given that t_0 is a continuous function, we see that the **product** of two continuous functions $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ is a **continuous** function and is positive for $t_0 > 0$ because $0 < \omega_z(t_0) < \infty$.

It is shown in Section 5 that $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ starts from zero and increases to a larger and larger positive value, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds and that $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ does not go to zero and does not approach a constant, as t_0 increases. Hence $\omega_z(t_0)t_0 = \pi$, can be reached for specific values of t_0 , as finite t_0 increases without bounds. As t_0 increases from 0, to a larger and larger finite value without bounds, the continuous function $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ starts from 0 and will pass

We denote the right hand side of Eq. 31 as *RHS*. We can substitute $\tau = -\tau$ in the second integral in the left hand side (LHS) of Eq. 31 as follows. We use $E_0(-\tau) = E_0(\tau)$.

$$LHS = - \int_0^{t_{0c}} E_0(\tau)(e^{\sigma t_{0c}} e^{-2\sigma\tau} + e^{\sigma t_{0c}}) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau + \int_0^{t_{0c}} E_0(\tau)(e^{-\sigma t_{0c}} e^{2\sigma\tau} + e^{-\sigma t_{0c}}) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau \quad (32)$$

We combine the integrals in Eq. 32 as follows.

$$LHS = \int_0^{t_{0c}} E_0(\tau)(-e^{\sigma t_{0c}} e^{-2\sigma\tau} - e^{\sigma t_{0c}} + e^{-\sigma t_{0c}} e^{2\sigma\tau} + e^{-\sigma t_{0c}}) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau \quad (33)$$

We substitute $2 \sinh(\sigma\tau) = e^{\sigma\tau} - e^{-\sigma\tau}$ and $2 \sinh(\sigma t_{0c}) = e^{\sigma t_{0c}} - e^{-\sigma t_{0c}}$ in Eq. 33 as follows.

$$LHS = -2 \int_0^{t_{0c}} E_0(\tau)(\sinh(\sigma t_{0c} - 2\sigma\tau) + \sinh(\sigma t_{0c})) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau \quad (34)$$

We substitute $\tau = -\tau$ in the integrals in the right hand side of Eq. 31 as follows. We use $E_0(\tau) = E_0(-\tau)$ and $-\int_\infty^0 = \int_0^\infty$.

$$\begin{aligned} RHS &= -2 \cosh(\sigma t_{0c}) \int_0^0 E_0(\tau) e^{2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau - 2 \cosh(\sigma t_{0c}) \int_0^0 E_0(\tau) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau - 2D(t_{0c}) \\ RHS &= 2 \cosh(\sigma t_{0c}) \int_0^\infty E_0(\tau) e^{2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_{0c}) \int_0^\infty E_0(\tau) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau - 2D(t_{0c}) \\ RHS &= 2 \cosh(\sigma t_{0c}) \int_0^\infty E_0(\tau)[e^{2\sigma\tau} + 1] \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau - 2D(t_{0c}) \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

We equate Eq. 34 and Eq. 35 after dividing by a factor of 2, as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} & - \int_0^{t_{0c}} E_0(\tau)(\sinh(\sigma t_{0c} - 2\sigma\tau) + \sinh(\sigma t_{0c})) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau \\ & = \cosh(\sigma t_{0c}) \int_0^\infty E_0(\tau)[e^{2\sigma\tau} + 1] \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau - D(t_{0c}) \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

We use $D(t_0) = \cosh(\sigma t_0) \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau$ using Result 2.4.c in Section 2.4 and we substitute $\tau = -\tau$ in the integrand and $t_0 = t_{0c}$ and we get $D(t_{0c}) = \cosh(\sigma t_{0c}) \int_0^\infty E_0(\tau)(e^{2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau$ using $E_0(\tau) = E_0(-\tau)$ and $-\int_\infty^0 = \int_0^\infty$. Hence we can cancel RHS terms in Eq. 36 as follows. We multiply the equation by a factor of -1 in the second line below.

$$\begin{aligned} -A(t_{0c}) &= - \int_0^{t_{0c}} E_0(\tau)(\sinh(\sigma t_{0c} - 2\sigma\tau) + \sinh(\sigma t_{0c})) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau = 0 \\ A(t_{0c}) &= \int_0^{t_{0c}} E_0(\tau)(\sinh(\sigma t_{0c}) - \sinh(2\sigma\tau - \sigma t_{0c})) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

Eq. 37 leads to contradiction:

We will show that $A(t_{0c}) > 0$ and Eq. 37 leads to a contradiction for $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$.

We see that $E_0(\tau) > 0$ for real τ (Appendix C.5). We see that $E_0(\tau)$ is a **strictly decreasing** function for $\tau > 0$ as shown in Section 6. (**Result 3.0.a**)

The first derivative of $B(\tau, t_{0c}) = \sinh(\sigma t_{0c}) - \sinh(2\sigma\tau - \sigma t_{0c})$ in Eq. 37, given by $\frac{\partial B(\tau, t_{0c})}{\partial \tau} = -2\sigma \cosh(2\sigma\tau - \sigma t_{0c}) < 0$, for $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$ and hence $B(\tau, t_{0c}) = \sinh(\sigma t_{0c}) - \sinh(2\sigma\tau - \sigma t_{0c})$ is a **strictly decreasing function** of τ in the interval $0 < \tau < t_{0c}$. (**Result 3.0.b**)

We see that $B(\tau, t_{0c}) = 2 \sinh(\sigma t_{0c}) > 0$ at $\tau = 0$ and $B(\tau, t_{0c}) = 0$ at $\tau = t_{0c}$. Given that $B(\tau, t_{0c})$ is a **strictly decreasing function** of τ in the interval $0 < \tau < t_{0c}$, we see that $B(\tau, t_{0c}) > 0$ in the interval $0 < \tau < t_{0c}$. (**Result 3.0.c**)

Using Result 3.0.a, Result 3.0.b and Result 3.0.c, we see that the term $C(\tau, t_{0c}) = E_0(\tau)B(\tau, t_{0c})$ in Eq. 37, is a **strictly decreasing function** of τ , given that the product of two strictly decreasing functions, which are positive in the interval $0 < \tau < t_{0c}$, is also a strictly decreasing function, because $C(\tau, t_{0c}) - C(\tau + d\tau, t_{0c}) = E_0(\tau)B(\tau, t_{0c}) - E_0(\tau + d\tau)B(\tau + d\tau, t_{0c}) > 0$, given that $E_0(\tau) > E_0(\tau + d\tau)$ and $B(\tau, t_{0c}) > B(\tau + d\tau, t_{0c})$, for $d\tau > 0$, in the interval $0 < \tau < t_{0c}$ and $0 < \tau + d\tau < t_{0c}$. (**Result 3.0.d**)

Using Result 3.0.a, Result 3.0.b, Result 3.0.c and Result 3.0.d and $C(\tau, t_{0c}) = E_0(\tau)(\sinh(\sigma t_{0c}) - \sinh(2\sigma\tau - \sigma t_{0c}))$, we can split Eq. 37 to 2 integrals, as follows.

$$A(t_{0c}) = \int_0^{t_{0c}} C(\tau, t_{0c}) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau = \int_0^{\frac{t_{0c}}{2}} C(\tau, t_{0c}) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau + \int_{\frac{t_{0c}}{2}}^{t_{0c}} C(\tau, t_{0c}) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau \quad (38)$$

We substitute $t_{0c} - \tau = \tau'$ and hence $\tau = t_{0c} - \tau'$ and $d\tau = -d\tau'$ in the second integral in the right hand side of Eq. 38 and substitute back $\tau' = \tau$ in the second line below and write as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} A(t_{0c}) &= \int_0^{\frac{t_{0c}}{2}} C(\tau, t_{0c}) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau - \int_{\frac{t_{0c}}{2}}^0 C(t_{0c} - \tau', t_{0c}) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})(t_{0c} - \tau')) d\tau' \\ A(t_{0c}) &= \int_0^{\frac{t_{0c}}{2}} C(\tau, t_{0c}) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau - \int_{\frac{t_{0c}}{2}}^0 C(t_{0c} - \tau, t_{0c}) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})(t_{0c} - \tau)) d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

We expand above equation using $\cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})(t_{0c} - \tau)) = \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})t_{0c}) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) + \sin(\omega_z(t_{0c})t_{0c}) \sin(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau)$ and use $\omega_z(t_{0c})t_{0c} = \pi$ and hence $\sin(\omega_z(t_{0c})t_{0c}) = 0$ and $\cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})t_{0c}) = -1$. We use $-\int_{\frac{t_{0c}}{2}}^0 = \int_0^{\frac{t_{0c}}{2}}$ below.

$$\begin{aligned} A(t_{0c}) &= \int_0^{\frac{t_{0c}}{2}} C(\tau, t_{0c}) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau - \int_0^{\frac{t_{0c}}{2}} C(t_{0c} - \tau, t_{0c}) \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau \\ A(t_{0c}) &= \int_0^{\frac{t_{0c}}{2}} [C(\tau, t_{0c}) - C(t_{0c} - \tau, t_{0c})] \cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

At $\tau = 0$, the term $C(\tau, t_{0c}) = E_0(\tau)B(\tau, t_{0c}) > 0$, given that $E_0(0) > 0$ and $B(\tau, t_{0c}) = \sinh(\sigma t_{0c}) - \sinh(2\sigma\tau - \sigma t_{0c}) = 2 \sinh(\sigma t_{0c}) > 0$ at $\tau = 0$. We see that $C(t_{0c} - \tau, t_{0c}) = 0$ at $\tau = 0$, given that $C(t_{0c} - \tau, t_{0c}) = E_0(t_{0c} - \tau)B(t_{0c} - \tau, t_{0c})$ and $B(t_{0c} - \tau, t_{0c}) = \sinh(\sigma t_{0c}) - \sinh(2\sigma(t_{0c} - \tau) - \sigma t_{0c}) = 0$ at $\tau = 0$. Hence $I(\tau, t_{0c}) = C(\tau, t_{0c}) - C(t_{0c} - \tau, t_{0c}) > 0$ at $\tau = 0$ in Eq. 40. At $\tau = \frac{t_{0c}}{2}$, we see that

$$I(\frac{t_{0c}}{2}, t_{0c}) = C(\frac{t_{0c}}{2}, t_{0c}) - C(\frac{t_{0c}}{2}, t_{0c}) = 0.$$

Using **strictly decreasing** property of $C(\tau, t_{0c})$ in Result 3.0.d, we see that $C(\tau, t_{0c}) - C(t_{0c} - \tau, t_{0c}) > 0$ in the interval $0 < \tau < \frac{t_{0c}}{2}$. The term $\cos(\omega_z(t_{0c})\tau) > 0$ in the interval $0 < \tau < \frac{t_{0c}}{2}$ using $\omega_z(t_{0c})\frac{t_{0c}}{2} = \frac{\pi}{2}$. Hence the integral for $A(t_{0c})$ in Eq. 40 and in LHS of Eq. 37 is > 0 . (**Result 3.0.e**)

We require $A(t_{0c}) = 0$ in Eq. 37. Hence this leads to a **contradiction**, for $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$.

For $\sigma = 0$, both sides of Eq. 37 is zero, given the term $\sinh(\sigma t_{0c}) - \sinh(2\sigma\tau - \sigma t_{0c}) = 0$ and **does not** lead to a contradiction.

We have shown this result for $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$. **If** the Fourier transform of $E_p(t) = E_0(t)e^{-\sigma t}$ given by $E_{p\omega}(\omega) = E_{pR\omega}(\omega) + iE_{pI\omega}(\omega)$ has a zero at $\omega = \omega_0$, to satisfy Statement 1, **then** the real part $E_{pR\omega}(\omega)$ and the imaginary part $E_{pI\omega}(\omega)$ **also** have a zero at $\omega = \omega_0$. (**Result 3.b**)

Given that $E_p(t) = E_0(t)e^{-\sigma t}$ is real, its Fourier transform $E_{p\omega}(\omega) = \xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega)$ has symmetry properties and hence $E_{pR\omega}(-\omega) = E_{pR\omega}(\omega)$ and $E_{pI\omega}(-\omega) = -E_{pI\omega}(\omega)$ (Symmetry property) and hence $E_{p\omega}(-\omega) = \xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma - i\omega) = E_{pR\omega}(-\omega) + iE_{pI\omega}(-\omega) = E_{pR\omega}(\omega) - iE_{pI\omega}(\omega)$ **also** has a zero at $\omega = \omega_0$ to satisfy Statement 1, using Result 3.b. (**Result 3.c**)

Using the property $\xi(s) = \xi(1 - s)$, we get $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma - i\omega) = \xi(\frac{1}{2} - \sigma + i\omega)$ at $s = \frac{1}{2} + \sigma - i\omega$ and hence $E_{q\omega}(\omega) = \xi(\frac{1}{2} - \sigma + i\omega)$ **also** has a zero at $\omega = \omega_0$ to satisfy Statement 1, using Result 3.c. We see that $E_{q\omega}(\omega) = \xi(\frac{1}{2} - \sigma + i\omega)$ is obtained by replacing σ in $E_{p\omega}(\omega) = \xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega)$ by $-\sigma$. Hence the results in above sections hold for $-\frac{1}{2} < \sigma < 0$ and hence for $0 < |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$.

Hence we have produced a **contradiction** of **Statement 1** that the Fourier Transform of the function $E_p(t) = E_0(t)e^{-\sigma t}$ has a zero at $\omega = \omega_0$ for $0 < |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$.

Hence the assumption in **Statement 1** that Riemann's Xi Function given by $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega) = E_{p\omega}(\omega)$ has a zero at $\omega = \omega_0$, where ω_0 is real, leads to a **contradiction** for the region $0 < |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$ which corresponds to the critical strip excluding the critical line. Hence $\zeta(s)$ does not have non-trivial zeros in the critical strip excluding the critical line and we have proved Riemann's Hypothesis.

4. $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a continuous function of t_0

It is shown in **Lemma 1** in Section 2.1 that $G_R(\omega, t_0) = 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ where it crosses the zero line to the opposite sign, if Statement 1 is true, and that $\omega_z(t_0)$ is **finite and non-zero** for all $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$ and that $\omega_z(t_0)$ is an even function of variable t_0 (Result 2.4.b in Section 2.4). For a given t_0 , $\omega_z(t_0)$ can have more than one value, corresponding to multiple zero crossings in $G_R(\omega, t_0)$, but we consider only the first zero crossing to the right of origin in the section below, where $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ crosses the zero line to the opposite sign, as detailed in **Lemma 1** in Section 2.1.

We consider the Fourier transform of the even part of $g(t, t_0)$ given by $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ in the section below and show that, under this Fourier transformation, as we change t_0 , the zero crossing in $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ given by $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a continuous function of t_0 , for $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$. This is shown in the steps below using **Implicit Function Theorem**.

- It is shown in Section 4.1 that $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ and $G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0) = \frac{\partial^{2r} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r}}$ are partially differentiable at least twice with respect to ω , for some value of $r \in W$ (element of set of whole numbers including zero.)

- It is shown in Section 4.4 that $G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)$ is partially differentiable at least twice with respect to t_0 .

- In Section 4.6, it is shown that, **if** $G_R(\omega, t_0) = 0$ at $\omega = \pm\omega_z(t_0)$, for each fixed choice of $t_0 \in \Re$ and $(2r + 1)$ is the highest order of the zero at $\omega = \pm\omega_z(t_0)$ for some value of $r \in W$ (element of set of whole numbers including zero), **then** $G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0) = \frac{\partial^{2r} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r}} = 0$ at $\omega = \pm\omega_z(t_0)$ and $\frac{\partial G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega} = \frac{\partial^{2r+1} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r+1}} \neq 0$ at $\omega = \pm\omega_z(t_0)$.

- It is shown in Section 4.5 that $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a **continuous** function of t_0 , for $t_0 \in \Re$, using **Implicit Function Theorem** in \Re^2 .

4.1. $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ and $G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)$ are partially differentiable twice as a function of ω

$G_R(\omega, t_0)$ in Eq. 21 is copied below.

$$\begin{aligned}
G_R(\omega, t_0) = & e^{-\sigma t_0} \left[\int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0) e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau + \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau - t_0) \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \right] \\
& + e^{\sigma t_0} \left[\int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau - t_0) e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau + \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0) \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \right] \\
& + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau) (e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \quad (41)
\end{aligned}$$

We write it succinctly as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
G_R(\omega, t_0) &= \int_{-\infty}^0 A(\tau, t_0) \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \\
A(\tau, t_0) &= e^{-\sigma t_0} A_1(\tau, t_0) + e^{\sigma t_0} A_1(\tau, -t_0) + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) E_0(\tau) (e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \\
A_1(\tau, t_0) &= E_0(\tau + t_0) e^{-2\sigma\tau} + E_0(\tau - t_0) \quad (42)
\end{aligned}$$

We see that $E_0(\tau)$ in Eq. 1 and its t_0 shifted versions are analytic functions of τ and t_0 , given that the sum and product of exponential functions are analytic and hence infinitely differentiable. (**Result 4.1**)

In Eq. 42, $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ is partially differentiable at least twice with respect to ω and the integrals converge in Eq. 42 to Eq. 44 for $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$, because the term $\tau^r E_0(\tau + Mt_0) e^{-2\sigma\tau}$ has **exponential** asymptotic fall-off rate as $|\tau| \rightarrow \infty$, for $r \in W$ (Details in Section 4.2). The integrands in Eq. 42 to Eq. 44 are analytic functions of variables ω, t_0 (using Result 4.1 in this section and given that the terms $\cos(\omega\tau), \sin(\omega\tau)$ and $e^{-2\sigma\tau}$ are analytic functions). The integrands are finite and have **exponential** asymptotic fall-off rate (Details in Section 4.2) and absolutely integrable and we can find a suitable dominating function with exponential asymptotic fall-off rate which is absolutely integrable. (Details in Section 4.3) The partial derivative of the integrands in the equation for $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ in Eq. 42, with respect to ω exists, as shown in the integrands in Eq. 43 and Eq. 44. Hence we can interchange the

order of partial differentiation and integration in Eq. 43 and Eq. 44 using theorem of differentiability of functions defined by Lebesgue integrals and theorem of dominated convergence, recursively as follows.(theorem) (**Result 4.1.A**)

$$\frac{\partial G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega} = - \int_{-\infty}^0 \tau A(\tau, t_0) \sin(\omega\tau) d\tau \quad (43)$$

We write the second derivative $\frac{\partial^2 G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^2}$ as follows.

$$\frac{\partial^2 G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^2} = - \int_{-\infty}^0 \tau^2 A(\tau, t_0) \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \quad (44)$$

We can use the arguments in the above paras and derive the $(2r)^{th}$ derivative of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$, for $r \in W$, which is differentiable at least twice, as follows.

$$G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0) = \frac{\partial^{2r} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r}} = (-1)^r \int_{-\infty}^0 \tau^{2r} A(\tau, t_0) \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \quad (45)$$

We can prove Eq. 45 using induction. We use Eq. 45 as Induction Hypothesis. We take the first and second derivative of Eq. 45 and we interchange the order of differentiation and integration, using the arguments used to derive Eq. 44 as follows.

$$\frac{\partial^{2r+1} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r+1}} = (-1)^{r+1} \int_{-\infty}^0 \tau^{2r+1} A(\tau, t_0) \sin(\omega\tau) d\tau \quad (46)$$

$$\frac{\partial^{2r+2} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r+2}} = (-1)^{r+1} \int_{-\infty}^0 \tau^{2r+2} A(\tau, t_0) \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \quad (47)$$

We see that the equation in Eq. 47 is the same as the equation obtained by setting $r = r + 1$ in Eq. 45. Thus we have proved Eq. 45 using mathematical induction.

4.2. **Exponential Fall off rate of $B(t) = t^r E_0(t + Mt_0)e^{-2\sigma t}$ for $r \in W$**

In this section, it is shown that the term $B(t) = t^r E_0(t + Mt_0)e^{-2\sigma t}$, for integer M , has exponential asymptotic fall-off rate as $|t| \rightarrow \infty$, for $r \in W$. (**Result 4.2.1**).

We consider $C(t) = t^r E_0(t + t_a)e^{-2\sigma t}$ for real t_a . We see that $C(t - t_a) = (t - t_a)^r e^{2\sigma t_a} E_0(t)e^{-2\sigma t}$. We see that $E_0(t)e^{-2\sigma t}$ is an absolutely integrable function, for $0 \leq |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$ given that it has exponential fall-off rates as $|t| \rightarrow \infty$. (Details in Appendix C.3 and Appendix C.4).

Hence $C(t - t_a) = (t - t_a)^r e^{2\sigma t_a} E_0(t)e^{-2\sigma t}$ also has exponential fall-off rates as $|t| \rightarrow \infty$, for $r \in W$ and finite t_a and is an absolutely integrable function.

Hence $C(t) = t^r E_0(t + t_a)e^{-2\sigma t}$ has exponential fall-off rates as $|t| \rightarrow \infty$, for finite t_a and is an absolutely integrable function. We set $t_a = Mt_0$ and see that $B(t)$ in Result 4.2.1, has **exponential fall-off rates** as $|t| \rightarrow \infty$, for finite t_0 and is an absolutely integrable function.

4.3. Dominating function

We consider $x(t) = E_0(t)e^{-2\sigma t}$ which has asymptotic exponential fall-off rate of $o[e^{-0.5|t|}]$. (Details in Appendix C.3) We see that $x(t + t_a)$ also has the same asymptotic exponential fall-off rate, for finite shift of $t_a = Mt_0$ for integer M and $y(t, t_a) = t^r x(t + t_a)e^{2\sigma t_a}$ also has the same asymptotic exponential fall-off rate, for $r \in W$. We consider the intervals $0 \leq t_0 \leq t_{0_{max}}$ and $0 \leq t_a \leq t_{a_{max}}$ where $t_{0_{max}}, t_{a_{max}}$ are finite.

We consider finite $t_d \gg t_{a_{max}}$ where $y(t, t_a) = t^r x(t + t_a)e^{2\sigma t_a}$ falls off at the rate of $o[e^{0.5t}]$ for $t \ll -t_d$. We consider $f(t, t_a, \omega) = y(t, t_a) \cos(\omega t)$ and we get $\frac{\partial f(t, t_a, \omega)}{\partial \omega} = -ty(t, t_a) \sin(\omega t)$ which falls off at the rate of $o[e^{0.5t}]$ for $t \ll -t_d$. We see that $x(t) = E_0(t)e^{-2\sigma t} > 0$ and finite, for $|t| < \infty$ (Details in Appendix C.1). Let $0 < f_{max} < \infty$ be the maximum value of $|\frac{\partial f(t, t_a, \omega)}{\partial \omega}|$ in the interval $-\infty < t < \infty$.

We can find a suitable **dominating function** $D(t) = e^{-K|t|} f_{max} e^{Kt_d} > 0$ with a fall off rate of $O[e^{-K|t|}]$ where $0 < K < 0.5$ and hence $D(t)$ has a slower fall off rate than $\frac{\partial f(t, t_a, \omega)}{\partial \omega}$ and $D(t) = f_{max}$ at $t = -t_d$ and hence $D(t) > |\frac{\partial f(t, t_a, \omega)}{\partial \omega}|$ for $-\infty < t \leq 0$ and hence $|\frac{\partial f(t, t_a, \omega)}{\partial \omega}| \leq D(t)$ in the interval $(-\infty, 0]$ and $\int_{-\infty}^0 |D(t)| dt = \int_{-\infty}^0 e^{Kt} f_{max} e^{Kt_d} dt = \frac{1}{K} f_{max} e^{Kt_d} [e^{Kt}]_{-\infty}^0 = \frac{1}{K} f_{max} e^{Kt_d}$ is finite. (**Result 4.3.1**)

The terms in Eq. 44 are given by $B(t) = t^r e^{-2\sigma t} E_0(t + Mt_0)$ using Eq. 42 and Result 4.2.1 in Section 4.2. We set $t_a = Mt_0$ and get $B(t) = t^r e^{-2\sigma t} E_0(t + t_a)$. Hence $y(t, t_a) = t^r x(t + t_a)e^{2\sigma t_a} = t^r E_0(t + t_a)e^{-2\sigma t}$ in the second para, corresponds to $B(t) = t^r e^{-2\sigma t} E_0(t + t_a)$ and Result 4.3.1 holds for this term. We see that Result 4.3.1 holds for the terms in Eq. 44 and Eq. 42 using arguments in above paragraphs and setting $M = 1, -1$ and setting $\sigma = 0$ as needed.

As $t_{0_{max}}, t_{a_{max}}$ increase to a larger and larger **finite value** without bounds, we consider larger intervals $0 \leq t_0 \leq t_{0_{max}}$ and $0 \leq t_a \leq t_{a_{max}}$ and f_{max} and t_d also increase correspondingly and the results in above paragraphs are valid in these intervals.

Similarly, we consider $f(t, t_a, \omega) = y(t, t_a) \sin(\omega t) = t^r E_0(t + t_a)e^{-2\sigma t} \sin(\omega t) = t^r E_0(t + Mt_0)e^{-2\sigma t} \sin(\omega t)$ and we see that $\frac{\partial f(t, t_a, \omega)}{\partial t_0}$ which falls off at the rate of $o[e^{0.5t}]$ for $t \ll -t_d$, using Eq. 51 and $E_0(t) = E_0(-t)$ and due to the term $e^{-\pi n^2 e^{-2t}}$ and we can use arguments in above paragraphs to get a result similar to Result 4.3.1 for the terms in Eq. 49. We can use these arguments to get a result similar to Result 4.3.1 for the second derivative terms $\frac{\partial^2 f(t, t_a, \omega)}{\partial t_0^2}$ in Eq. 53.

4.4. $G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)$ are partially differentiable twice as a function of t_0 , $r \in W$

We copy Eq. 45 and Eq. 42 as follows.

$$G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0) = \frac{\partial^{2r} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r}} = (-1)^r \int_{-\infty}^0 \tau^{2r} A(\tau, t_0) \cos(\omega \tau) d\tau$$

$$A(\tau, t_0) = e^{-\sigma t_0} A_1(\tau, t_0) + e^{\sigma t_0} A_1(\tau, -t_0) + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) E_0(\tau) (e^{-2\sigma \tau} + 1)$$

$$A_1(\tau, t_0) = E_0(\tau + t_0) e^{-2\sigma \tau} + E_0(\tau - t_0) \quad (48)$$

In Eq. 48, $G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)$ is partially differentiable at least twice as a function of t_0 and the integrals converge in Eq. 49 shown as follows. Using Result 4.1.A in Section 4.1, we can interchange the order of partial differentiation and integration in Eq. 48 as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)}{\partial t_0} &= (-1)^r \int_{-\infty}^0 \tau^{2r} \frac{\partial A(\tau, t_0)}{\partial t_0} \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \\ \frac{\partial A(\tau, t_0)}{\partial t_0} &= -\sigma e^{-\sigma t_0} A_1(\tau, t_0) + e^{-\sigma t_0} \frac{\partial A_1(\tau, t_0)}{\partial t_0} + \sigma e^{\sigma t_0} A_1(\tau, -t_0) + e^{\sigma t_0} \frac{\partial A_1(\tau, -t_0)}{\partial t_0} \\ &\quad + 2\sigma \sinh(\sigma t_0) E_0(\tau) (e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

We show that the integrals in Eq. 49 converge, as follows. We see that the integrals for the first and third terms in Eq. 49 converge because the terms $\tau^{2r} E_0(\tau + Mt_0) e^{-2\sigma\tau}$ and $\tau^{2r} E_0(\tau + Mt_0)$ in Eq. 48, for integer M , have exponential asymptotic fall-off rate as $|\tau| \rightarrow \infty$ (Details in Section 4.2).

We consider the integrand $\frac{\partial A_1(\tau, t_0)}{\partial t_0}$ in Eq. 49 first. We consider the term $E_0(\tau + Mt_0)$ for integer M in Eq. 48 and can show that the corresponding integrals converge in Eq. 49, as follows. We take the factor of 2 out of the summation in $E_0(\tau)$ in Eq. 1 copied below.

$$\begin{aligned} E_0(\tau) &= 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [2\pi^2 n^4 e^{4\tau} - 3\pi n^2 e^{2\tau}] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2\tau}} e^{\frac{\tau}{2}} \\ E_0(\tau + Mt_0) &= 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [2\pi^2 n^4 e^{4\tau} e^{4Mt_0} - 3\pi n^2 e^{2\tau} e^{2Mt_0}] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2\tau} e^{2Mt_0}} e^{\frac{\tau}{2}} e^{\frac{Mt_0}{2}} \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

We can show that $\frac{\partial}{\partial t_0} E_0(\tau + Mt_0) = M \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} E_0(\tau + Mt_0)$ as follows, given that the equation for $E_0(\tau + Mt_0)$ in Eq. 50 has terms of the form $e^{\tau + Mt_0}$ and the equation is **invariant** if we interchange the variables τ and Mt_0 . (**Result 4.4.A**)

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} E_0(\tau + Mt_0) &= 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2\tau} e^{2Mt_0}} e^{\frac{\tau}{2}} e^{\frac{Mt_0}{2}} [8\pi^2 n^4 e^{4\tau} e^{4Mt_0} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2\tau} e^{2Mt_0} \\ &\quad + (\frac{1}{2} - 2\pi n^2 e^{2\tau} e^{2Mt_0}) (2\pi^2 n^4 e^{4\tau} e^{4Mt_0} - 3\pi n^2 e^{2\tau} e^{2Mt_0})] \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t_0} E_0(\tau + Mt_0) &= 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2\tau} e^{2Mt_0}} e^{\frac{\tau}{2}} e^{\frac{Mt_0}{2}} [8M\pi^2 n^4 e^{4\tau} e^{4Mt_0} - 6M\pi n^2 e^{2\tau} e^{2Mt_0} \\ &\quad + (\frac{M}{2} - 2M\pi n^2 e^{2\tau} e^{2Mt_0}) (2\pi^2 n^4 e^{4\tau} e^{4Mt_0} - 3\pi n^2 e^{2\tau} e^{2Mt_0})] = M \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} E_0(\tau + Mt_0) \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

We can write the integral corresponding to the term $E_0(\tau + Mt_0) e^{-2\sigma\tau}$ in Eq. 48, in the equation for $\frac{\partial A_1(\tau, t_0)}{\partial t_0}$ in Eq. 49, using $M = 1$ in Result 4.4.A, as follows. We use the fact that $\int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{dA(\tau)}{d\tau} B(\tau) d\tau = \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{d(A(\tau)B(\tau))}{d\tau} d\tau - \int_{-\infty}^0 A(\tau) \frac{dB(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau$.

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial(E_0(\tau + t_0))}{\partial t_0} \tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau = \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial(E_0(\tau + t_0))}{\partial \tau} \tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial(E_0(\tau + t_0) \tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau))}{\partial \tau} d\tau - \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0) \frac{\partial(\tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau))}{\partial \tau} d\tau \\ &= [E_0(\tau + t_0) \tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau)]_{-\infty}^0 + \omega \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0) \tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \sin(\omega\tau) d\tau \\ &+ 2\sigma \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0) \tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau - 2r \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0) \tau^{2r-1} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

We see that the integrals in Eq. 52 converge because the integrands are absolutely integrable because the terms $E_0(\tau + t_0)\tau^{2r}e^{-2\sigma\tau}\sin(\omega\tau)$, $E_0(\tau + t_0)\tau^{2r}e^{-2\sigma\tau}\cos(\omega\tau)$ and $E_0(\tau + t_0)\tau^{2r-1}e^{-2\sigma\tau}\cos(\omega\tau)$ have exponential asymptotic fall-off rate as $|\tau| \rightarrow \infty$ (Details in Section 4.2). The term $[E_0(\tau + t_0)\tau^{2r}e^{-2\sigma\tau}\cos(\omega\tau)]_{-\infty}^0$ is finite, given that $\tau^{2r}E_0(\tau)e^{-2\sigma\tau}$ and its shifted versions go to zero as $t \rightarrow -\infty$ (Details in Appendix C.3). Hence the integral $\int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial(E_0(\tau+t_0)\tau^{2r}e^{-2\sigma\tau})}{\partial t_0} \cos(\omega\tau)d\tau$ in Eq. 52 and in Eq. 49 corresponding to the term $E_0(\tau + t_0)e^{-2\sigma\tau}$, converges.

We set $\sigma = 0$ and $M = -1$ in the term $E_0(\tau + Mt_0)e^{-2\sigma\tau}$ and see that the integral $\int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial(E_0(\tau-t_0))}{\partial t_0} \tau^{2r} \cos(\omega\tau)d\tau$ in Eq. 49 corresponding to the term $E_0(\tau - t_0)$ also converges, using Result 4.4.A and the procedure used in Eq. 50 to Eq. 52. Hence the integral for the second term $\frac{\partial A_1(\tau, t_0)}{\partial t_0}$ in Eq. 49 converges.

We set $M = -1$ in the term $E_0(\tau + Mt_0)e^{-2\sigma\tau}$ in Eq. 50 to Eq. 52 and see that the integral $\int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial(E_0(\tau-t_0)e^{-2\sigma\tau})}{\partial t_0} \tau^{2r} \cos(\omega\tau)d\tau$ in Eq. 49 corresponding to the term $E_0(\tau - t_0)e^{-2\sigma\tau}$ also converges, using Result 4.4.A.

We set $\sigma = 0$ and set $M = 1$ in the term $E_0(\tau + Mt_0)e^{-2\sigma\tau}$ and see that the integral $\int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial(E_0(\tau+t_0))}{\partial t_0} \tau^{2r} \cos(\omega\tau)d\tau$ in Eq. 49 corresponding to the term $E_0(\tau + t_0)$ also converges, using Result 4.4.A and the procedure used in Eq. 50 to Eq. 52. Hence the integral for the fourth term $\frac{\partial A_1(\tau, -t_0)}{\partial t_0}$ in Eq. 49 converges.

The integral corresponding to the last term $E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)$ in Eq. 49 converges. Hence all the integrals in $\frac{\partial G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)}{\partial t_0}$ in Eq. 49 converge.

4.4.1. *Second Partial Derivative of $G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)$ with respect to t_0*

The second partial derivative of $G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)$ with respect to t_0 is given by $\frac{\partial^2 G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)}{\partial t_0^2} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t_0} \frac{\partial G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)}{\partial t_0}$ as follows. We use the result in Eq. 49 and using Result 4.1.A in Section 4.1, we can interchange the order of partial differentiation and integration in Eq. 49 as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)}{\partial t_0^2} &= (-1)^r \int_{-\infty}^0 \tau^{2r} \frac{\partial^2 A(\tau, t_0)}{\partial t_0^2} \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \\ \frac{\partial^2 A(\tau, t_0)}{\partial t_0^2} &= \sigma^2 e^{-\sigma t_0} A_1(\tau, t_0) - 2\sigma e^{-\sigma t_0} \frac{\partial A_1(\tau, t_0)}{\partial t_0} + e^{-\sigma t_0} \frac{\partial^2 A_1(\tau, t_0)}{\partial t_0^2} \\ &\quad + \sigma^2 e^{\sigma t_0} A_1(\tau, -t_0) + 2\sigma e^{\sigma t_0} \frac{\partial A_1(\tau, -t_0)}{\partial t_0} + e^{\sigma t_0} \frac{\partial^2 A_1(\tau, -t_0)}{\partial t_0^2} \\ &\quad + 2\sigma^2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

The first two terms and fourth, fifth and seventh terms in $\frac{\partial^2 A(\tau, t_0)}{\partial t_0^2}$ in Eq. 53 are similar to those in the equation for $\frac{\partial G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)}{\partial t_0}$ in Eq. 49 and their corresponding integrals have been shown to converge in Section 4.4. We will show that the integrals for third and sixth terms in Eq. 53 converge, as follows. We consider the integrand in the third term in Eq. 53 first. We consider the term $E_0(\tau + Mt_0)$ first

in Eq. 48 and copy Eq. 50 below.

$$E_0(\tau) = 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [2\pi^2 n^4 e^{4\tau} - 3\pi n^2 e^{2\tau}] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2\tau}} e^{\frac{\tau}{2}}$$

$$E_0(\tau + Mt_0) = 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [2\pi^2 n^4 e^{4\tau} e^{4Mt_0} - 3\pi n^2 e^{2\tau} e^{2Mt_0}] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2\tau} e^{2Mt_0}} e^{\frac{\tau}{2}} e^{\frac{Mt_0}{2}} \quad (54)$$

We showed in Result 4.4.A that $\frac{\partial}{\partial t_0} E_0(\tau + Mt_0) = M \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} E_0(\tau + Mt_0)$, given that the equation has terms of the form $e^{\tau + Mt_0}$ and the equation is **invariant** if we interchange the variables τ and Mt_0 .

We use $t'_0 = Mt_0$ in Eq. 54 and see that $\frac{\partial^2}{\partial (t'_0)^2} E_0(\tau + t'_0) = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \tau^2} E_0(\tau + t'_0)$ (**Result 4.4.1.E'**) given that the equation has terms of the form $e^{\tau + t'_0}$ and the equation is **invariant** if we interchange the variables τ and t'_0 .

Given that $\frac{\partial}{\partial t_0} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t'_0} \frac{\partial t'_0}{\partial t_0} = M \frac{\partial}{\partial t'_0}$, we get $\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t_0^2} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t_0} (\frac{\partial}{\partial t_0}) = M \frac{\partial}{\partial t_0} (\frac{\partial}{\partial t'_0}) = M^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial t'_0} (\frac{\partial}{\partial t'_0}) = M^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial (t'_0)^2}$, we substitute it in Result 4.4.1.E' and get $\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t_0^2} E_0(\tau + Mt_0) = M^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \tau^2} E_0(\tau + Mt_0)$. (**Result 4.4.1.A'**)

We can write the third term $\frac{\partial^2 A_1(\tau, t_0)}{\partial t_0^2}$ in Eq. 53, corresponding to the term $E_0(\tau + t_0) e^{-2\sigma\tau}$, using $M = 1$ in Result 4.4.1.A', as follows. We use the fact that $\int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{dA(\tau)}{d\tau} B(\tau) d\tau = \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{d(A(\tau)B(\tau))}{d\tau} d\tau - \int_{-\infty}^0 A(\tau) \frac{dB(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau$.

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial^2 (E_0(\tau + t_0))}{\partial t_0^2} \tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau = \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial^2 (E_0(\tau + t_0))}{\partial \tau^2} \tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial (\frac{\partial E_0(\tau + t_0)}{\partial \tau} \tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau))}{\partial \tau} d\tau - \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial E_0(\tau + t_0)}{\partial \tau} \frac{\partial (\tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau))}{\partial \tau} d\tau \\ &= \left[\frac{\partial E_0(\tau + t_0)}{\partial \tau} \tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau) \right]_{-\infty}^0 + \omega \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial E_0(\tau + t_0)}{\partial \tau} \tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \sin(\omega\tau) d\tau \\ &+ 2\sigma \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial E_0(\tau + t_0)}{\partial \tau} \tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau - 2r \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial E_0(\tau + t_0)}{\partial \tau} \tau^{2r-1} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \quad (55) \end{aligned}$$

We see that the integrals $\int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial E_0(\tau + t_0)}{\partial \tau} \tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau$ and $\int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial E_0(\tau + t_0)}{\partial \tau} \tau^{2r-1} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau$ in Eq. 55 converge, using Eq. 52 in the previous subsection. We see the term $\left[\frac{\partial E_0(\tau + t_0)}{\partial \tau} \tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau) \right]_{-\infty}^0$ also converges, given that $E_0(\tau) = E_0(-\tau)$ and $E_0(\tau + t_0) = E_0(-\tau - t_0)$ and we consider $\frac{\partial E_0(\tau + t_0)}{\partial \tau} \tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} = \frac{\partial E_0(-\tau - t_0)}{\partial \tau} \tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau}$ using Eq. 51 and see that the term $e^{-\pi n^2 e^{-2\tau}}$ goes to zero faster than the rising term $\tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} e^{-6\tau} e^{-\frac{\tau}{2}}$, as $\tau \rightarrow -\infty$. (**Result 4.4.1.1**)

It is shown below that the term $\int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial E_0(\tau+t_0)}{\partial \tau} \tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \sin(\omega\tau) d\tau$ in Eq. 55 also converges.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial(E_0(\tau+t_0))}{\partial \tau} \tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \sin(\omega\tau) d\tau \\
&= \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial(E_0(\tau+t_0)\tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \sin(\omega\tau))}{\partial \tau} d\tau - \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau+t_0) \frac{\partial(\tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \sin(\omega\tau))}{\partial \tau} d\tau \\
&= [E_0(\tau+t_0)\tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \sin(\omega\tau)]_{-\infty}^0 - \omega \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau+t_0)\tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \\
&+ 2\sigma \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau+t_0)\tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \sin(\omega\tau) d\tau - 2r \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau+t_0)\tau^{2r-1} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \sin(\omega\tau) d\tau \quad (56)
\end{aligned}$$

We see that the integrals in Eq. 56 converge because the integrands are absolutely integrable because the terms $E_0(\tau+t_0)\tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \sin(\omega\tau)$, $E_0(\tau+t_0)\tau^{2r-1} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \sin(\omega\tau)$ and $E_0(\tau+t_0)\tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega\tau)$ have exponential asymptotic fall-off rate as $|\tau| \rightarrow \infty$ (Details in Section 4.2). The term $[E_0(\tau+t_0)\tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau} \sin(\omega\tau)]_{-\infty}^0$ is finite, given that $\tau^{2r} E_0(\tau) e^{-2\sigma\tau}$ and its shifted versions go to zero as $t \rightarrow -\infty$ (Details in Appendix C.3). Hence the integral $\int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial^2(E_0(\tau+t_0)\tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau})}{\partial t_0^2} \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau$ in Eq. 55 and in Eq. 53 corresponding to the term $E_0(\tau+t_0)e^{-2\sigma\tau}$, also converges.

We set $\sigma = 0$ and set $M = -1$ in the term $E_0(\tau + Mt_0)e^{-2\sigma\tau}$ and see that the integral $\int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial^2(E_0(\tau-t_0))}{\partial t_0^2} \tau^{2r} \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau$ in Eq. 53 corresponding to the term $E_0(\tau - t_0)$ also converges, using Result 4.4.1.A' and the procedure used in Eq. 54 to Eq. 56. Hence the third integral corresponding to the term $\frac{\partial^2 A_1(\tau, t_0)}{\partial t_0^2}$ in Eq. 53, also converges.

We set $M = -1$ in the term $E_0(\tau + Mt_0)e^{-2\sigma\tau}$ in Eq. 54 to Eq. 56 and see that the integral $\int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial^2(E_0(\tau-t_0)\tau^{2r} e^{-2\sigma\tau})}{\partial t_0^2} \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau$ in Eq. 53 corresponding to the term $E_0(\tau - t_0)e^{-2\sigma\tau}$ also converges, using Result 4.4.1.A'.

We set $\sigma = 0$ and set $M = 1$ in the term $E_0(\tau + Mt_0)e^{-2\sigma\tau}$ and see that the integral $\int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{\partial^2(E_0(\tau+t_0))}{\partial t_0^2} \tau^{2r} \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau$ in Eq. 53 corresponding to the term $E_0(\tau + t_0)$ also converges, using Result 4.4.1.A' and the procedure used in Eq. 54 to Eq. 56. Hence the sixth integral corresponding to the term $\frac{\partial^2 A_1(\tau, -t_0)}{\partial t_0^2}$ converges in Eq. 53.

Hence all the integrals in Eq. 53 converge.

4.5. Zero Crossings in $G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)$ move continuously as a function of t_0 , for $r \in W$

Result 4.5.1: It is shown in Lemma 1 in Section 2.1 that $G_R(\omega, t_0) = 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ where it crosses the zero line to the opposite sign, if Statement 1 is true. It is shown in Section 4.6 that $G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0) = 0$ and $\frac{\partial G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega} \neq 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$, for some value of $r \in W$, where $(2r + 1)$ is the highest order of the zero of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$. (example plot)

We use **Implicit Function Theorem** for the two dimensional case \mathfrak{R}^2 (link and link). Given that $G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)$ is partially differentiable with respect to ω and t_0 , with continuous partial derivatives, for $r \in W$ (Details in Section 4.1, Section 4.4) and given that $G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0) = 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ and $\frac{\partial G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega} \neq 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$, for some value of $r \in W$, where $(2r + 1)$ is the highest order of the

zero of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ (using Result 4.5.1 in this section and using Section 4.6), we see that $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a differentiable function of t_0 in the neighbourhood around t_0 .

We use Algorithm A in Section 4.7 and show that $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a **continuous** function of t_0 , for $t_0 \geq 0$.

We use the fact that $\omega_z(-t_0) = \omega_z(t_0)$ using Result 2.4.b in Section 2.4 and hence $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a **continuous** function of t_0 , for $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$.

4.6. Order of the zero in $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ is finite.

It is shown in this section that, **if** $G_R(\omega, t_0) = 0$ at $\omega = \pm\omega_z(t_0)$ to satisfy Statement 1, for each fixed choice of $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$, **then** $G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0) = \frac{\partial^{2r} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r}} = 0$ at $\omega = \pm\omega_z(t_0)$ and $\frac{\partial G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega} = \frac{\partial^{2r+1} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r+1}} \neq 0$ at $\omega = \pm\omega_z(t_0)$ for some value of $r \in W$ (element of set of whole numbers including zero) and $(2r + 1)$ is the highest order of the zero of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ at $\omega = \pm\omega_z(t_0)$ which is finite.

This is shown using Proof by Contradiction by assuming the **opposite** case that $\frac{\partial^{2r} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r}} = 0$ and $\frac{\partial^{2r+1} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r+1}} = 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$, for $r = 0, 1, \dots$, as $r \rightarrow \infty$ (**Statement D**) and show that it leads to a **contradiction**.

$G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)$ in Eq. 48 is copied below. It is shown in **Lemma 1** in Section 2.1 that $G_R(\omega, t_0) = 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ where it crosses the zero line to the opposite sign, **if** Statement 1 is true.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0) &= \frac{\partial^{2r} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r}} = (-1)^r \int_{-\infty}^0 \tau^{2r} A(\tau, t_0) \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \\ A(\tau, t_0) &= e^{-\sigma t_0} A_1(\tau, t_0) + e^{\sigma t_0} A_1(\tau, -t_0) + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) E_0(\tau) (e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \\ A_1(\tau, t_0) &= E_0(\tau + t_0) e^{-2\sigma\tau} + E_0(\tau - t_0) \end{aligned} \quad (57)$$

We compute the $(2r + 1)^{th}$ and $(2r + 2)^{th}$ derivative of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ and copy Eq. 46 and Eq. 47 below.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^{2r+1} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r+1}} &= (-1)^{r+1} \int_{-\infty}^0 \tau^{2r+1} A(\tau, t_0) \sin(\omega\tau) d\tau \\ \frac{\partial^{2r+2} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r+2}} &= (-1)^{r+1} \int_{-\infty}^0 \tau^{2r+2} A(\tau, t_0) \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (58)$$

We compute $C(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\delta\omega)^{2r}}{!(2r)} \frac{\partial^{2r} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r}}$ and $S(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\delta\omega)^{2r+1}}{!(2r+1)} \frac{\partial^{2r+1} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r+1}}$ below, using Eq. 57 and Eq. 58, where $\delta\omega$ is real. It is noted that the integrals below converge, as $r \rightarrow \infty$, by taking the terms $\frac{1}{!(2r)}$ and $\frac{1}{!(2r+1)}$ inside the integrals.

$$\begin{aligned} C(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) &= \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} (-1)^r \frac{(\delta\omega)^{2r}}{!(2r)} \left[\int_{-\infty}^0 \tau^{2r} A(\tau, t_0) \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \right. \\ S(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) &= \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} (-1)^{r+1} \frac{(\delta\omega)^{2r+1}}{!(2r+1)} \int_{-\infty}^0 \tau^{2r+1} A(\tau, t_0) \sin(\omega\tau) d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

We consider the integrals $C'(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega)$ and $S'(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega)$ obtained by interchanging the order of integration and summation in Eq. 59 as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} C'(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) &= \int_{-\infty}^0 \left[\sum_{r=0}^{\infty} (-1)^r \frac{(\delta\omega)^{2r}}{(2r)!} \tau^{2r} \right] A(\tau, t_0) \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \\ S'(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) &= \int_{-\infty}^0 \left[\sum_{r=0}^{\infty} (-1)^{r+1} \frac{(\delta\omega)^{2r+1}}{(2r+1)!} \tau^{2r+1} \right] A(\tau, t_0) \sin(\omega\tau) d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (60)$$

We use $\sum_{r=0}^{\infty} (-1)^r \frac{(\delta\omega)^{2r}}{(2r)!} \tau^{2r} = \cos((\delta\omega)\tau)$ and $\sum_{r=0}^{\infty} (-1)^{r+1} \frac{(\delta\omega)^{2r+1}}{(2r+1)!} \tau^{2r+1} = -\sin((\delta\omega)\tau)$ and write Eq. 60 as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} C'(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) &= \int_{-\infty}^0 A(\tau, t_0) \cos((\delta\omega)\tau) \cos(\omega\tau) d\tau \\ S'(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) &= - \int_{-\infty}^0 A(\tau, t_0) \sin((\delta\omega)\tau) \sin(\omega\tau) d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (61)$$

The integrands in Eq. 61 are absolutely integrable because the terms $E_0(\tau + Mt_0)e^{-2\sigma\tau}$ and $E_0(\tau + Mt_0)$ in $A(\tau, t_0)$ in Eq. 57, for integer M , have **exponential** asymptotic fall-off rate as $|\tau| \rightarrow \infty$ (Details in Section 4.2) and the integrals $C'(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega)$ and $S'(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega)$ converge. Hence we can interchange the order of integration and summation in the integrals for $C'(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega)$ and $S'(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega)$ in Eq. 60 using **Fubini's theorem** and we get $C(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega)$ and $S(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega)$ in Eq. 59 respectively. (link)

Hence we see that $C(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) = C'(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega)$ and $S(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) = S'(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega)$ and interchanging the order of integration and summation in Eq. 59 is justified.

We compute $C_S(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) = C(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) + S(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) = C'(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) + S'(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega)$ using Eq. 61 as follows, using the identity $\cos((\omega + \delta\omega)\tau) = \cos(\omega\tau) \cos((\delta\omega)\tau) - \sin(\omega\tau) \sin((\delta\omega)\tau)$.

$$C_S(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^0 A(\tau, t_0) \cos((\omega + \delta\omega)\tau) d\tau \quad (62)$$

If Statement D is true, **then** $\frac{\partial^{2r} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r}} = 0$ and $\frac{\partial^{2r+1} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r+1}} = 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ in Eq. 57 and Eq. 58, for $r = 0, 1, \dots$, as $r \rightarrow \infty$, and $C(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\delta\omega)^{2r}}{(2r)!} \frac{\partial^{2r} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r}} = 0$ and

$$S(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\delta\omega)^{2r+1}}{(2r+1)!} \frac{\partial^{2r+1} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r+1}} = 0 \text{ at } \omega = \omega_z(t_0) \text{ in Eq. 59 and hence}$$

$C_S(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) = C(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) + S(\omega, t_0, \delta\omega) = 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ in Eq. 62, shown as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} C_S(\omega_z(t_0), t_0, \delta\omega) &= \int_{-\infty}^0 A(\tau, t_0) \cos((\omega_z(t_0) + \delta\omega)\tau) d\tau = 0 \\ A(\tau, t_0) &= e^{-\sigma t_0} A_1(\tau, t_0) + e^{\sigma t_0} A_1(\tau, -t_0) + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) E_0(\tau) (e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \\ A_1(\tau, t_0) &= E_0(\tau + t_0) e^{-2\sigma\tau} + E_0(\tau - t_0) \end{aligned} \quad (63)$$

We expand Eq. 63 as follows, substituting $A(\tau, t_0)$ in the equation for $C_S(\omega_z(t_0), t_0, \delta\omega)$.

$$\begin{aligned}
C_S(\omega_z(t_0), t_0, \delta\omega) &= e^{-\sigma t_0} \left[\int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0) e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos((\omega_z(t_0) + \delta\omega)\tau) d\tau \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau - t_0) \cos((\omega_z(t_0) + \delta\omega)\tau) d\tau \right] \\
&+ e^{\sigma t_0} \left[\int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau - t_0) e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos((\omega_z(t_0) + \delta\omega)\tau) d\tau + \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0) \cos((\omega_z(t_0) + \delta\omega)\tau) d\tau \right] \\
&\quad + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau) (e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos((\omega_z(t_0) + \delta\omega)\tau) d\tau = 0 \quad (64)
\end{aligned}$$

Eq. 64 is similar to the equation for $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ in Eq. 21 in Section 2.4, evaluated at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ and equated to zero, to satisfy Statement 1, with $\omega_z(t_0)$ replaced by $\omega_z(t_0) + \delta\omega$.

Eq. 64 holds for all real $\delta\omega$, including the case, as $\delta\omega \rightarrow 0$, **if** Statement D is true. This **contradicts** Result 2.1.h in Lemma 1 in Section 2.1 which requires $G_R(\omega, t_0) = 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ where it **crosses** the zero line to the **opposite sign**, to satisfy Statement 1.

Hence we see that, **if** Statement 1 is true, **then** Statement D is false and hence there exists **at least one finite** $s \in N$ (element of set of natural numbers excluding zero) for which the $(s)^{th}$ derivative of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ given by $G_{R,s}(\omega, t_0) = \frac{\partial^s G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^s} \neq 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$, where $s = 2r$ is even or $s = 2r + 1$ is odd, for $r \in W$, for each fixed $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$.

We choose the **minimum** value of $s \in N$, for which $G_{R,s}(\omega, t_0) = \frac{\partial^s G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^s} \neq 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ and hence $G_{R,s-1}(\omega, t_0) = \frac{\partial^{s-1} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{s-1}} = 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ (**Result 4.6**). The first $(s - 1)$ derivatives of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ equal zero at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ and hence s is the order of the zero of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$, and the order of this zero is **finite**. (**Result 4.6.1**)

We see that $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ is an **even** function of ω because $g(t, t_0)$ is a real function of variable t (Details in Appendix D.1) and hence **if** $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ has a zero at $\omega = +\omega_z(t_0)$, **then** it also has a zero at $\omega = -\omega_z(t_0)$. (**Result 4.6.2**)

Using Result 4.6.1 and Result 4.6.2, we can write $G_R(\omega, t_0) = (\omega_z(t_0)^2 - \omega^2)^s N'(\omega, t_0)$ (**Eq.4.6**), for $s \in N$, where $N'(\omega, t_0) \neq 0$ at $\omega = \pm\omega_z(t_0)$, for each fixed $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$ and s is the highest order of the zero at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ which is finite. (It is noted that $\omega_z(t_0)$ represents the **zero crossing** in $G_R(\omega, t_0)$, for each fixed $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$. It is noted that $N'(\omega, t_0)$ may or may not be zero at $\omega \neq \pm\omega_z(t_0)$ and we **do not** claim otherwise.)

The case of $s = 2r$ in $G_R(\omega, t_0) = (\omega_z(t_0)^2 - \omega^2)^s N'(\omega, t_0)$ in Eq.4.6, is **ruled out** because $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ **changes sign** at $\omega = \pm\omega_z(t_0)$ (using Result 2.1.h in Lemma 1 in Section 2.1), while $N'(\omega, t_0) \neq 0$ at $\omega = \pm\omega_z(t_0)$, **does not** change sign at $\omega = \pm\omega_z(t_0)$ and $(\omega_z(t_0)^2 - \omega^2)^{2r} \geq 0$ for real ω , also **does not** change sign at $\omega = \pm\omega_z(t_0)$. (**Result 4.6.a**)

Hence $G_R(\omega, t_0) = (\omega_z(t_0)^2 - \omega^2)^{2r+1} N'(\omega, t_0)$ in Eq.4.6 and $s = 2r + 1$ is the order of the zero of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ and hence $G_{R,2r+1}(\omega, t_0) = \frac{\partial^{2r+1} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r+1}} \neq 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ and $G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0) = \frac{\partial^{2r} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r}} = 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$, using Result 4.6.

As an example, for the case $r = 0$, we get $G_R(\omega, t_0) = (\omega_z(t_0)^2 - \omega^2)N'(\omega, t_0)$ in Eq.4.6 and the order of the zero is $2r + 1 = 1$ and we get $\frac{\partial G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega} = (\omega_z(t_0)^2 - \omega^2)\frac{\partial N'(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega} + N'(\omega, t_0)(-2\omega) \neq 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$, given that the first term is zero and the second term is not zero at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ because $N'(\omega, t_0) \neq 0$ at $\omega = \pm\omega_z(t_0)$ and $\omega_z(t_0) \neq 0$. The above results hold for $r \in W$.

We have shown that, **if** $G_R(\omega, t_0) = 0$ at $\omega = \pm\omega_z(t_0)$ to satisfy Statement 1, for each fixed choice of $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$, **then** $G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0) = \frac{\partial^{2r} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r}} = 0$ at $\omega = \pm\omega_z(t_0)$ and $\frac{\partial G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega} = \frac{\partial^{2r+1} G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r+1}} \neq 0$ at $\omega = \pm\omega_z(t_0)$ for some value of $r \in W$ and $(2r + 1)$ is the highest order of the zero of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ at $\omega = \pm\omega_z(t_0)$ which is finite.

4.7. Algorithm A to find and track unique zero crossing function $\omega_z(t_0)$, for $t_0 \geq 0$

It is shown in **Lemma 1** in Section 2.1 that $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ has **at least one** zero crossing at finite $\omega = \omega_z(t_0) > 0$, where it crosses the zero line to the opposite sign, **if** Statement 1 is true. We see that $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ is an **even** function of ω , because $g(t, t_0)$ is a real function of variable t (link). If $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ has only one zero crossing to the right of origin, we get **at least two** zero crossings for $-\infty < \omega < \infty$. The algorithm below applies to $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ with one or more zero crossing to the right of origin.

- **Step A:** We consider the function $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ in the interval $-\omega_{max} \leq \omega \leq \omega_{max}$ and $0 \leq t_0 \leq t_{0,max}$, where $t_{0,max}, \omega_{max}$ are real and arbitrarily large and finite.

We choose ω_{max} larger than the first zero crossing to the right of origin. We see that the zeros of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ are isolated. (Details in Note 1 in Section 4.7.1) We compute the **minimum** separation between adjacent zero crossings in $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ given by $\delta_{\omega_{min}}$, in the interval $-\omega_{max} \leq \omega \leq \omega_{max}$, for **all possible** combinations of t_0 in the intervals $0 \leq t_0 \leq t_{0,max}$. (**Result 1**)

We see that $\delta_{\omega_{min}} > 0$, given that the zeros of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ are isolated (Details in Note 1 in Section 4.7.1). It is shown in Lemma 1 in Section 2.1 that $G_R(\omega, t_0) = 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ where it **crosses** the zero line to the opposite sign, **if** Statement 1 is true. So, adjacent zero crossings in $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ are separated by a **positive** value, for $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$. (**Result 2**)

- **Step 0:** We choose **Segment** S_0 in $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ around the **first zero crossing** to the right of origin at $\omega_z(t_0)$, in the interval $\omega_z(t_0) - \delta_\omega \leq \omega \leq \omega_z(t_0) + \delta_\omega$, **evaluated at** $t_0 = 0$, where $0 < \delta_\omega < \delta_{\omega_{min}}$.

We choose an arbitrarily small positive values of $\delta_{t_0} \ll 1$ such that Implicit Function Theorem (IFT) can be used with this choice, to track this zero crossing at $\omega_z(t_0)$, in the intervals $0 \leq t_0 \leq t_{0,max}$, as detailed below. (See Note 2 in in Section 4.7.1 for choice of δ_{t_0})

We note that $\omega_z(0) = \omega_{z_0} > 0$ using Lemma 1. We define $\omega_z(\delta_{t_0}) = \omega_{z_1} > 0$. We see that $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ has **only one** zero crossing in Segment S_0 , using Result 1 and 2 and $0 < \delta_\omega < \delta_{\omega_{min}}$ in previous paras and we **back-off** and set $\delta_\omega = \frac{\delta_{\omega_{min}}}{4}$. (**Result A₀**)

In this Segment S_0 , we can apply IFT because there is **only one** zero crossing in this segment and $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ satisfies all criteria for IFT (link), as shown in Section 4.1, Section 4.4 and Section 4.6 and hence $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a continuous function of t_0 in the neighbourhood around $t_0 = 0$. (**Result B₀**)

We note that $|\omega_{z_0} - \omega_{z_1}| \leq \delta_\omega$ and $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ has **only one** zero crossing in Segment S_0 for all values of $0 \leq t_0 \leq \delta_{t_0}$, using Result 1 and Result A_0 . As we increase t_0 , from 0, over above intervals, at every infinitesimal step, we use Result B_0 and show that $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a continuous function of t_0 in the neighbourhood around that infinitesimal step. (**Result C_0**)

We use IFT and see that $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a **continuous** function of t_0 , in the interval $0 \leq t_0 \leq \delta_{t_0}$, using Result C_0 . Hence we are able to **track** the unique first zero crossing, as it moves from ω_{z_0} to ω_{z_1} . (**Result D_0**)

• **Step n:** In Step 1 to N, we set $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$ and we **track** the zero crossing ω_{z_1} specified in Step 0, which is **unique**. We choose **Segment S_n** in $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ around the **unique zero crossing** at ω_{z_n} , in the interval $\omega_{z_n} - \delta_\omega \leq \omega \leq \omega_{z_n} + \delta_\omega$.

We note that $\omega_z(n\delta_{t_0}) = \omega_{z_n} > 0$ and $\omega_z((n+1)\delta_{t_0}) = \omega_{z_{n+1}} > 0$ using Lemma 1. We see that $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ has **only one** zero crossing in Segment S_n , using Result 1 and 2 and $\delta_\omega = \frac{\delta_{\omega_{min}}}{4}$. (**Result A_n**)

In Step 0, we chose δ_{t_0} such that we can use IFT to track this unique zero crossing at $\omega_z(t_0)$ in the intervals $0 \leq t_0 \leq t_{0_{max}}$, as detailed below. (Details in Note 2 in Section 4.7.1)

In this Segment S_n , we can apply Implicit Function Theorem (IFT) because there is **only one** zero crossing in this segment and $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ satisfies all criteria for IFT (link), as shown in Section 4.1, Section 4.4 and Section 4.6 and hence $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a continuous function of t_0 in the neighbourhood around $t_0 = n\delta_{t_0}$. (**Result B_n**)

We note that $|\omega_{z_n} - \omega_{z_{n+1}}| \leq \delta_\omega$ and $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ has **only one** zero crossing in Segment S_n for all values of $n\delta_{t_0} \leq t_0 \leq (n+1)\delta_{t_0}$, using Result 1 and Result A_n . As we increase t_0 , from $n\delta_{t_0}$, over above intervals, at every infinitesimal step, we use Result B_n and show that $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a continuous function of t_0 in the neighbourhood around that infinitesimal step. (**Result C_n**)

We use IFT and see that $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a **continuous** function of t_0 , in the interval $n\delta_{t_0} \leq t_0 \leq (n+1)\delta_{t_0}$, using Result C_n . Hence we are able to **track** the unique first zero crossing, as it moves from ω_{z_n} to $\omega_{z_{n+1}}$. (**Result D_n**)

• We do not need to use induction hypothesis and induction step for Step n , given that in this algorithm, Step n from $n=1,2,\dots,N$ has statements which use Result 1 and 2 derived before Step 1 and uses results derived within the **same** step n and **not** previous steps $1, 2, \dots, n-1$.

• We use Step A and Step n for $n = 1, 2, \dots, N$ where $N = \lceil \frac{t_{0_{max}}}{\delta_{t_0}} \rceil - 1$.

As an example, we choose $t_{0_{max}} = 10^{100}$ and $\omega_{max} = 10^{100}$ and $\delta_{t_0} = 10^{-100}$, where δ_{t_0} satisfies the conditions in Note 2. We use Step A and Step n for $n = 1, 2, \dots, N$, and using IFT, we see that $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a **continuous** function of t_0 , for $0 \leq t_0 \leq t_{0_{max}}$.

We can increase $t_{0_{max}} = 10^{1000}$ and $\omega_{max} = 10^{1000}$ and $\delta_{t_0} = 10^{-1000}$. Result 1 and 2 continue to hold and $\delta_{\omega_{min}} > 0$. We use Step A and Step n for $n = 1, 2, \dots, N$ and using IFT, we see that $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a **continuous** function of t_0 , for $0 \leq t_0 \leq t_{0_{max}}$.

As $t_{0_{max}}$ and ω_{max} increase to a larger and larger finite value without bounds, and δ_{t_0} decreases to a smaller and smaller positive value without bounds tending towards zero, Result 1 and 2 continue to hold and $\delta_{\omega_{min}} > 0$ and hence t_0 spans the real interval $[0, \infty)$. Hence $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a continuous function of t_0 , for $t_0 \geq 0$.

In case the unique zero crossing reaches $\omega = 0$, where $\omega_z(t_0) = 0$, this case is detailed in Note 3 in Section 4.7.1.

4.7.1. *Note 1, 2 and 3.*

• **Note 1:** It is shown in Section 4.6 that $\frac{\partial^{2r+1}G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r+1}} \neq 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$, for some value of $r \in W$ where $(2r + 1)$ is the highest order of the zero of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$, if Statement 1 is true. This holds for every zero in $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ and $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$ (**Result 4.7.1.1**). If $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ had non-isolated zeros for some $\omega = \omega_z(t'_0)$, **then** we require $\frac{\partial^{2r+1}G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^{2r+1}} = 0$ at that $\omega = \omega_z(t'_0)$, for all $r \in W$, which produces a **contradiction** of Result 4.7.1.1. Hence the zeros of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ are **isolated**.

• **Note 2: Choice of δ_{t_0} :** $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ satisfies all criteria for IFT (link), as shown in Section 4.1, Section 4.4 Section 4.6 and hence we can apply IFT at each zero crossing $\omega_z(t_0)$, for each choice of t_0 in the intervals $0 \leq t_0 \leq t_{0_{max}}$. For each choice of t_0 in the above intervals, we consider each of the zero crossings at $\omega_z(t_0)$, and compute the **maximum** value of the neighbourhood intervals around that choice of t_0 , given by $\delta_{t_0}(k)$, for which IFT is valid. (δ_1 in IFT proof for 2-D case corresponds to the interval around t_0 given by $\delta_{t_0}(k)$ in our case and is small and positive. $\delta_1 \leq \delta_2$ in Point 2 in Line 5 of Proof section in Link to IFT proof, where δ_2 corresponds to the interval around ω in our case.) We clarify this point in next 2 paras, as follows.

In the 2-D case for IFT, we consider a function $f(x, y)$ which is partially differentiable with continuous partial derivatives and $f(x_0, y_0) = 0$ and $a := \frac{\partial f(x_0, y_0)}{\partial y} \neq 0$ at the zero crossing point at $y = y_0$ for $x = x_0$. We choose an open interval $I \times J := (x_0 - \delta_1, x_0 + \delta_1) \times (y_0 - \delta_2, y_0 + \delta_2)$, where δ_2 and δ_1 are positive and small, satisfying the following conditions: Link to IFT proof

- 1) We choose δ_2 such that $\frac{\partial f(x, y)}{\partial y} \in (\frac{a}{2}, \frac{3a}{2})$ for all $\| (x, y) - (x_0, y_0) \| < 2\delta_2$.
- 2) For the above δ_2 , we choose $\delta_1 \leq \delta_2$ such that, for all $x \in (x_0 - \delta_1, x_0 + \delta_1)$, we satisfy $|\frac{2f(x, y_0)}{a}| < \delta_2$.

For any given k , we replace $\delta_{t_0}(k)$ by δ_{t_0} to illustrate our 2-D case, similar to the 2-D case in above para. Let $a := \frac{\partial G_R(t_{0f}, \omega_z(t_{0f}))}{\partial \omega} \neq 0$ at the zero crossing point at $\omega = \omega_z(t_{0f})$ for $t_0 = t_{0f}$. We choose an open interval $I \times J := (t_{0f} - \delta_{t_0}, t_{0f} + \delta_{t_0}) \times (\omega_z(t_{0f}) - \delta_2, \omega_z(t_{0f}) + \delta_2)$, where δ_{t_0} is small and positive and using conditions 1 and 2 similar to 2-D case in above para, we get $0 < \delta_{t_0} \leq \delta_{t_{0_{max}}}$. We choose the **maximum** value of δ_{t_0} given by $\delta_{t_{0_{max}}}$.

Using above para, we compute $\delta_{t_{0_{max}}}(k)$ for $k = 1, 2, \dots$, over all possible zero crossings and for all choices of t_0 , in the intervals $0 \leq t_0 \leq t_{0_{max}}$ and compute the **minimum** value of $\delta_{t_{0_{max}}}(k)$, over all k , given by $\delta_{t_{0_{min}}}$. We choose $0 < \delta_{t_0} \leq \delta_{t_{0_{min}}}$, for Algorithm A.

We can show that the minimum values given by $\delta_{t_{0_{min}}}$ is **non-zero** as follows, using proof by contradiction. We assume that $\delta_{t_{0_{min}}} = 0$. This means that there is at least one value of $t_0 = t_{0_{min}}$ in the interval $0 \leq t_0 \leq t_{0_{max}}$, for one of the zero crossings, for which $\delta_{t_0}(k) = 0$, for a specific $k = k'$,

using IFT. ($\delta_{t_0}(k)$ is the interval over which IFT results apply regarding differentiability of $\omega_z(t_0)$.) This **contradicts** Point 2 in Line 5 of Proof section in Page 1 of IFT proof, which says $\delta_{t_0}(k)$ is small and positive and hence non-zero. (δ_1 in 2-D IFT proof corresponds to $\delta_{t_0}(k)$ in this section. Link to IFT proof) Therefore, $\delta_{t_{0,min}}$ is **not** zero.

• **Note 3:** Algorithm A to find and track unique first zero crossing to the right of origin given by $\omega_z(t_0)$, for real t_0 is shown in this section in above paras. **In case** this unique zero crossing reaches $\omega = 0$ for $t_0 = t_{00}$, where $\omega_z(t_0) = 0$, the algorithm **works till that point** and $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a continuous function of t_0 , for $0 \leq t_0 < t_{00}$. (**Result 4.7.1.2**)

It is shown in Section 4.6 that $\frac{\partial^s G_R(\omega, t_0)}{\partial \omega^s} \neq 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$, for some $s \in N$, for each choice of t_0 , **if** $G_R(\omega, t_0) = 0$ at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$. This result holds even if Lemma 1 is not used and the result holds for $\omega_z(t_0) = 0$ also. (Eq. 63 in Section 4.6 holds for $\omega_z(t_0) = 0$ and all real $\delta\omega$, including the case, as $\delta\omega \rightarrow 0$, **if** Statement D is true. This **contradicts** the fact that the zeros of $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ are **isolated**, shown in Note 1, given that $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ is **not** an all zero function of variable ω shown in Section 2.2. Hence Statement D is false.) More details in Note 3.2.

It is shown in Section 4.1, Section 4.4 that $G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_0)$ is partially differentiable at least twice with respect to ω, t_0 respectively.

Hence **if** the unique zero crossing $\omega_z(t_0)$ in Algorithm A reaches $\omega = 0$ for $t_0 = t_{00}$, where $\omega_z(t_0) = 0$, we **can** use IFT in the interval $t_{00} \leq t_0 \leq t_{00} + \delta_{t_0}$, using the results in above 2 paras and show that $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a continuous function of t_0 , in that interval. (**Result 4.7.1.3**)

Now we proceed with the Algorithm A detailed in this section for $t_0 > t_{00} + \delta_{t_0}$. In case the unique zero crossing $\omega_z(t_0)$ goes to negative side, we choose the positive value, given that $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ is an even function of ω . In case the unique zero crossing $\omega_z(t_0)$ reaches $\omega = 0$ several more times, we use the argument in this Note 3, and show that $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a continuous function of t_0 , for $t_0 \geq 0$ using Result 4.7.1.2, Result 4.7.1.3 and this para.

Note 3.1: We note that it is shown in Lemma 1 in Section 2.1 that $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ must have **at least one zero** at finite $\omega = \omega_z(t_0) \neq 0$ where it **crosses** the zero line to the opposite sign, for each $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$, to satisfy **Statement 1**. In Algorithm A, we start with $t_0 = 0$ and take the **first** zero crossing to the right of origin given by $\omega_z(t_0)$ and **track** it, as it moves along $0 \leq \omega < \infty$, for $t_0 \geq 0$ and show that this $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a continuous function of t_0 , which is required to set $\omega_z(t_{0c})t_{0c} = \pi$ in Section 3.

In case this unique zero crossing reaches $\omega = 0$ for $t_0 = t_{00}$, where $\omega_z(t_0) = 0$, it **does not** contradict the result $\omega_z(t_0) \neq 0$ in Lemma 1, given that we **do not** use Lemma 1 to get this result and instead $\omega_z(t_0) = 0$ is obtained during tracking of the first zero crossing to the right of origin, using Algorithm A.

It is shown in Section 5 that $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ increases, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds and $\omega_z(t_0)t_0 = \pi$ can be reached, for specific $t_0 = t_{0c}$, as finite t_0 increases without bounds. Hence $\omega_z(t_0)$ and $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ **do not** get stuck at zero, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds.

Note 3.2: In the last 4 paras in Section 4.6, it is stated that "The case of $s = 2r$ in $G_R(\omega, t_0) = (\omega_z(t_0)^2 - \omega^2)^s N'(\omega, t_0)$ is **ruled out** because $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ **changes sign** at $\omega = \pm\omega_z(t_0)$ (using Result

2.1.h in Lemma 1 in Section 2.1)”. This statement holds for the choice of $\omega_z(t_0) \neq 0$ only. For the case this unique first zero crossing reaches $\omega = 0$, for some t_0 , where $\omega_z(t_0) = 0$, during tracking in Algorithm A, Lemma 1 is not used to derive $\omega_z(t_0) = 0$ and the zero crossing requirement vanishes and hence $s = 2r$ is possible.

For the case this unique first zero crossing reaches $\omega = 0$, for some $t_0 = t_{00}$, $G_R(\omega, t_{00})$ and its even derivatives $G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_{00}) = \frac{\partial^{2r} G_R(\omega, t_{00})}{\partial \omega^{2r}}$ are **even** function of ω and its odd derivatives $G_{R,2r+1}(\omega, t_{00}) = \frac{\partial^{2r+1} G_R(\omega, t_{00})}{\partial \omega^{2r+1}}$ are **odd** function of ω , for all $r \in W$, given that $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ is real and even function of ω . Hence $G_{R,2r+1}(\omega, t_{00}) = 0$ at $\omega = 0$, for all $r \in W$.

In general, $G_{R,2r}(\omega, t_{00}) = \frac{\partial^{2r} G_R(\omega, t_{00})}{\partial \omega^{2r}}$ may be non-zero, at $\omega = 0$, for some $r \in W$, given that $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ is **not** an all zero function of variable ω , as shown in Section 2.2. This property enables us to use IFT at $\omega = 0$, for the case this unique first zero crossing reaches $\omega = 0$.

5. $\omega_z(t_0)t_0 = \pi$ can be reached for specific t_0

In Lemma 1 in Section 2.1, it is shown that $0 < \omega_z(t_0) < \infty$, for all $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$. For $t_0 > 0$, we see that $\omega_z(t_0)t_0 > 0$. In Section 4, it is shown that $\omega_z(t_0)$ is a **continuous** function of variable t_0 , for $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$. Hence $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ is a positive continuous function for $t_0 > 0$.

We **require** $\omega_z(t_0)t_0 = \pi$, in Section 3, for a specific $t_0 = t_{0c}$. In the section below, we consider $t_0 > 0$ and it is shown that $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ increases to a larger and larger finite value, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds. Hence, as we increase t_0 , from zero, we can find a specific $t_0 = t_{0c}$, for which $\omega_z(t_0)t_0 = \pi$ is reached, using the method in Section 5.1.

Hence $\omega_z(t_0)t_0 = \pi$ can be reached, for specific $t_0 = t_{0c}$, as finite t_0 increases from zero, without bounds, given that $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ is a **continuous** function of variable t_0 , for all $t_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$, using Intermediate Value Theorem.

In the section below, it is shown that, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds, $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ does not go to zero (Case 1) and does not approach a constant (Case 2) and instead, $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ increases to a larger and larger finite value.

5.1. Method 1

We consider $G_R(\omega, t_0)$ in Eq. 21 and set it to zero at $\omega = \omega_z(t_0)$ below.

$$\begin{aligned}
G_R(\omega_z(t_0), t_0) &= e^{-\sigma t_0} \left[\int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0) e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau + \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau - t_0) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau \right] \\
&\quad + e^{\sigma t_0} \left[\int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau - t_0) e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau + \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau \right] \\
&\quad + 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau) (e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau = 0 \quad (65)
\end{aligned}$$

We combine first and fourth integrals in Eq. 65 and write in the first line in Eq. 66. We combine third and second integrals in Eq. 65 and write in the second line in Eq. 66 as follows. We use $D(t_0) = D(-t_0) = \cosh(\sigma t_0) \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)d\tau$ using Result 2.4.c in Section 2.4.

$$\begin{aligned} G_R(\omega_z(t_0), t_0) &= e^{-\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0) e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau + e^{\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau + t_0) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau \\ &+ e^{\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau - t_0) e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau + e^{-\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau - t_0) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau + 2D(t_0) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (66)$$

We substitute $\tau + t_0 = t$ in the first two integrals in Eq. 66 and get $\tau = t - t_0$ and $d\tau = dt$ and we substitute back $t = \tau$ and write in the first line in Eq. 67. We substitute $\tau - t_0 = t$ in the third and fourth integrals in Eq. 66 and get $\tau = t + t_0$ and $d\tau = dt$ and we substitute back $t = \tau$ and write in the second line in Eq. 67 as follows. We use $e^{-\sigma t_0} e^{2\sigma t_0} = e^{\sigma t_0}$ in the first integral and $e^{\sigma t_0} e^{-2\sigma t_0} = e^{-\sigma t_0}$ in the third integral, similar to the substitution in Eq. 25.

$$\begin{aligned} G_R(\omega_z(t_0), t_0) &= e^{\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^{t_0} E_0(\tau) e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega_z(t_0)(\tau - t_0)) d\tau + e^{\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^{t_0} E_0(\tau) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)(\tau - t_0)) d\tau \\ &+ e^{-\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^{-t_0} E_0(\tau) e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega_z(t_0)(\tau + t_0)) d\tau + e^{-\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^{-t_0} E_0(\tau) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)(\tau + t_0)) d\tau + 2D(t_0) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (67)$$

We split the range of integration $\int_{-\infty}^{t_0} = \int_{-\infty}^{-t_0} + \int_{-t_0}^{t_0}$. We compute the maximum value of $E_0(\tau)e^{-2\sigma\tau}$, given by E_{max} , for real τ and $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$ and compute the minimum value $Min(E_{max}, 1)$ given by E_{min} . We choose sufficiently large $t_0 > 0$ such that $E_0(\tau)e^{-2\sigma\tau} \ll E_{min}$ and $E_0(\tau) \ll E_{min}$ in the interval $|\tau| \geq t_0$.

We take the $\int_{-t_0}^{t_0}$ part of first and second integrals in Eq. 67 and combine them to get the **dominant** term $F(t_0)$ in Eq. 68. We use $2D(t_0) = 2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)d\tau$ in Result 2.4.c in Section 2.4 and use $2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) = e^{\sigma t_0} + e^{-\sigma t_0}$ and get $2D(t_0) = (e^{\sigma t_0} + e^{-\sigma t_0}) \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)d\tau$ and then split it into two integrals $\int_{-\infty}^0 = \int_{-\infty}^{-t_0} + \int_{-t_0}^0$ and take the integral $e^{\sigma t_0} \int_{-t_0}^0$ in $2D(t_0)$ and combine it with the **dominant** term $F(t_0)$ in Eq. 68.

Then we club the rest of the integrals in Eq. 67 in the **negligible** term $X(t_0)$ and write as follows. It is shown in Section 5.2 that $|X(t_0)| \ll |F(t_0)|$ and $|X(t_0)| \ll 1$, as t_0 increases.

$$\begin{aligned} G_R(\omega_z(t_0), t_0) &= F_X(t_0) = F(t_0) + X(t_0) = 0 \\ F(t_0) &= e^{\sigma t_0} \left[\int_{-t_0}^{t_0} E_0(\tau) [e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1] \cos(\omega_z(t_0)(\tau - t_0)) d\tau + \int_{-t_0}^0 E_0(\tau) (e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau \right] \\ X(t_0) &= e^{\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^{-t_0} E_0(\tau) [e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1] \cos(\omega_z(t_0)(\tau - t_0)) d\tau \\ &+ e^{-\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^{-t_0} E_0(\tau) e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega_z(t_0)(\tau + t_0)) d\tau + e^{-\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^{-t_0} E_0(\tau) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)(\tau + t_0)) d\tau \\ &+ e^{\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^{-t_0} E_0(\tau) (e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau + e^{-\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau) (e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (68)$$

It is noted that Eq. 68 and the equations in Section 5.1.1 and Section 5.1.2 below, apply to any real t_0 . In Section 5.1.1 and Section 5.1.2, it is shown that, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds, $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ does not approach zero (Case 1) and does not approach a constant (Case 2). We **rule out** Case 1 and Case 2, by showing that $|F(t_0)| > 0$ and $|X(t_0)| \ll |F(t_0)|$ and that $F_X(t_0) = F(t_0) + X(t_0)$ in Eq. 68 increases **exponentially**, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger value, while the right hand side in $F_X(t_0)$ in Eq. 68 remains zero, producing a **contradiction**. Hence we conclude that $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ increases to a larger and larger finite value, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds.

5.1.1. $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ *does not approach zero, as t_0 increases*

Case 1: We assume that $\omega_z(t_0) = o[\frac{1}{t_0}]$ ((Little o Notation)) (**Statement E**) and hence becomes smaller and smaller approaching zero and $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ becomes smaller and smaller approaching zero, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds(**Result 5.1.1.a**). It is shown in this section that Statement E is false, if Statement 1 is true. We copy Eq. 68 below.

$$F_X(t_0) = F(t_0) + X(t_0) = 0$$

$$F(t_0) = e^{\sigma t_0} \left[\int_{-t_0}^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)(\tau - t_0))d\tau + \int_{-t_0}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)d\tau \right] \quad (69)$$

We find the **minimum** value of $F(t_0)$ as follows. We use $\omega_z(t_0) = o[\frac{1}{t_0}]$ in Eq. 69. For sufficiently large t_0 , we get $\omega_z(t_0)\tau \ll 1$ in the interval $|\tau| \leq t_0$ and hence $\cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)$ very close to unity. We use $\cos(x) \geq 1 - \frac{x^2}{2}$ for $x \in \Re$ (link) and use a loose bound. Hence $\cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) > \frac{1}{2}$ (**Result 5.1.1.b**).

We use $|\omega_z(t_0)(\tau - t_0)| = |\omega_z(t_0)t_0(\frac{\tau}{t_0} - 1)| = |\omega_z(t_0)t_0(1 - \frac{\tau}{t_0})| \ll 1$, for sufficiently large t_0 , in the interval $|\tau| \leq t_0$ and hence $\cos(\omega_z(t_0)(\tau - t_0))$ very close to unity and hence $\cos(\omega_z(t_0)(\tau - t_0)) > \frac{1}{2}$. (**Result 5.1.1.c**)

For sufficiently large t_0 , we write Eq. 69 as follows, using Result 5.1.1.b and Result 5.1.1.c. We use $\int_{-t_0}^{t_0} = \int_{-t_0}^0 + \int_0^{t_0}$ below.

$$F(t_0) > \frac{1}{2}e^{\sigma t_0} \left[\int_{-t_0}^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau + \int_{-t_0}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau \right]$$

$$F(t_0) > \frac{1}{2}e^{\sigma t_0} \left[\int_{-t_0}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau + \int_0^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau + \int_{-t_0}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau \right] \quad (70)$$

We substitute $\tau = -\tau$ in the integral $\int_{-t_0}^0$ and use $E_0(-\tau) = E_0(\tau)$ and $-\int_{-t_0}^0 = \int_0^{t_0}$ as follows.

$$F(t_0) > \frac{1}{2}e^{\sigma t_0} \left[- \int_{t_0}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau + \int_0^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau - \int_{t_0}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau \right]$$

$$F(t_0) > \frac{1}{2}e^{\sigma t_0} \left[\int_0^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(e^{2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau + \int_0^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau + \int_0^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(e^{2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau \right]$$

$$F(t_0) > \frac{1}{2}e^{\sigma t_0} \int_0^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(3 + 2 \cosh(2\sigma\tau) + e^{2\sigma\tau})d\tau = F_{min}(t_0) \quad (71)$$

We see that $F(t_0) > F_{min}(t_0)$ converges to a **finite positive** value, which increases exponentially, given that the integrand is positive, for positive t_0 and $E_0(\tau)e^{\pm 2\sigma\tau} > 0$ (Details in Appendix C.1) and the integral converges as t_0 increases to $t'_0 \gg t_0$, as shown in Section 5.3. (**Result 5.1.1.d**)

We choose sufficiently large t_0 such that $|X(t_0)| \ll F_{min}(t_0)$ is arbitrarily small. As we increase t_0 to $t'_0 \gg t_0$, we see that $F_{min}(t'_0) > F_{min}(t_0)$ and $|X(t'_0)| \ll |X(t_0)| \ll F_{min}(t'_0)$ (**Result 5.1.1.e**)

Hence $F_X(t_0) = F(t_0) + X(t_0) = 0$ is **not** possible in Eq. 69, which is required by Statement E. Hence Statement E is **false**, if Statement 1 is true and $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ **does not** approach zero, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds.

5.1.2. $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ **does not approach a non-zero constant, as t_0 increases**

Case 2: We assume that $\omega_z(t_0) = O[\frac{1}{t_0}]$ (Big O Notation), and hence approaches zero and $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ approaches a constant $K_w \neq 0$, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds (**Statement F**). It is shown in this section that Statement F is false, if Statement 1 is true. (**Result 5.1.2.a**)

We expand $F(t_0)$ in Eq. 68 using the identity $\cos(\omega_z(t_0)(\tau - t_0)) = \cos(\omega_z(t_0)t_0)\cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) + \sin(\omega_z(t_0)t_0)\sin(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)$ and show that it converges to a finite positive value. We use $2 \cosh(\sigma t_0) = e^{\sigma t_0} + e^{-\sigma t_0}$ and rearrange terms.

$$\begin{aligned}
F_X(t_0) &= F(t_0) + X(t_0) = 0 \\
F(t_0) &= e^{\sigma t_0} [\cos(\omega_z(t_0)t_0) \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} E_0(\tau) [e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1] \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau \\
&+ \sin(\omega_z(t_0)t_0) \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} E_0(\tau) [e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1] \sin(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau + \int_{-t_0}^0 E_0(\tau) (e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau] \quad (72)
\end{aligned}$$

We write succinctly as follows, using $\theta_{t_0} = \omega_z(t_0)t_0$.

$$\begin{aligned}
F(t_0) &= e^{\sigma t_0} [\cos(\theta_{t_0})F_c(t_0) + \sin(\theta_{t_0})F_s(t_0) + D_1(t_0)] \\
D_1(t_0) &= \int_{-t_0}^0 E_0(\tau) (e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau \\
F_c(t_0) &= \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} E_0(\tau) [e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1] \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau, \quad F_s(t_0) = \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} E_0(\tau) [e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1] \sin(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) d\tau \quad (73)
\end{aligned}$$

We consider the general case $\theta_{t_0} = \omega_z(t_0)t_0 \neq m\pi$ and $\theta_{t_0} \neq (2m+1)\frac{\pi}{2}$, for integer m , where both $\cos(\omega_z(t_0)t_0)$ and $\sin(\omega_z(t_0)t_0)$ are **non-zero**.

We take the term $\cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)$ in the interval $|\tau| \leq t_0$ and hence $\omega_z(t_0)\tau \leq 1$ using Statement F. We write $\cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) = 1 + d_c(\tau, t_0)$ where $d_c(\tau, t_0) = -\frac{(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)^2}{12} + \frac{(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)^4}{14} + \dots$. We take the term $\sin(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)$ in the interval $|\tau| \leq t_0$ and write $\sin(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) = \omega_z(t_0)\tau + d_s(\tau, t_0)$ where

$d_s(\tau, t_0) = -\frac{(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)^3}{13} + \frac{(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)^5}{15} + \dots$ and write Eq. 73 as follows. (**Result 5.1.2.b**)

$$\begin{aligned}
F_c(t_0) &= F_0(t_0) + F_{d_c}(t_0), & F_s(t_0) &= F_{s_1}(t_0) + F_{d_s}(t_0), & D_1(t_0) &= D_0(t_0) + D_{d_c}(t_0) \\
F_0(t_0) &= \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} E_0(\tau)[e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1]d\tau, & F_{d_c}(t_0) &= \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} E_0(\tau)[e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1]d_c(\tau, t_0)d\tau \\
F_{s_1}(t_0) &= \omega_z(t_0) \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} \tau E_0(\tau)[e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1]d\tau, & F_{d_s}(t_0) &= \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} E_0(\tau)[e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1]d_s(\tau, t_0)d\tau \\
D_0(t_0) &= \int_{-t_0}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau, & D_{d_c}(t_0) &= \int_{-t_0}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d_c(\tau, t_0)d\tau
\end{aligned} \tag{74}$$

We see that $F_0(t_0) = \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau = 2 \int_0^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(\cosh(2\sigma\tau) + 1)d\tau$ and $D_0(t_0) = \int_{-t_0}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau = \int_0^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(e^{2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau$ converge to a **non-zero** positive finite value, as t_0 increases, as shown in Section 5.3. (**Result 5.1.2.c**) We write Eq. 73 as follows using Eq. 74.

$$\begin{aligned}
F(t_0) &= e^{\sigma t_0} [F_A(t_0) + F_B(t_0)], & F_A(t_0) &= \cos(\theta_{t_0})F_0(t_0) + D_0(t_0) \\
F_B(t_0) &= \cos(\theta_{t_0})F_{d_c}(t_0) + \sin(\theta_{t_0})(F_{s_1}(t_0) + F_{d_s}(t_0)) + D_{d_c}(t_0)
\end{aligned} \tag{75}$$

We will show that, **compared** to $F_0(t_0)$ and $D_0(t_0)$ in $F_A(t_0)$, rest of the terms in $F_B(t_0)$ becomes smaller and smaller approaching zero, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds, using Statement F and Result 5.1.2.b. We consider 4 cases below.

Case 2A: We consider the case $F_A(t_0) = \cos(\theta_{t_0})F_0(t_0) + D_0(t_0)$ in Eq. 75, approaches a **non-zero** constant $F_{A_{min}}$, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds, using Statement F and Result 5.1.2.c and $\theta_{t_0} = \omega_z(t_0)t_0 \neq m\pi$ and $\theta_{t_0} \neq (2m+1)\frac{\pi}{2}$, for integer m , where both $\cos(\theta_{t_0})$ and $\sin(\theta_{t_0})$ are **non-zero**. (**Result 5.1.2.d**)

As we increase t_0 to t'_0 , we see that $F_0(t'_0) > F_0(t_0) > 0$ and $D_0(t'_0) > D_0(t_0) > 0$ using Result 5.1.2.c (Details in Section 5.3).

We see that the first term in $F_B(t_0)$ in Eq. 75, given by $F_{d_c}(t_0) = \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d_c(\tau, t_0)d\tau$ in Eq. 74, can be written as $F_{d_c}(t_0) = -\frac{(\omega_z(t_0))^2}{12} \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} (\tau)^2 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d'_c(\tau, t_0)d\tau$, using $d_c(\tau, t_0) = -\frac{(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)^2}{12} + \frac{(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)^4}{14} + \dots = -\frac{(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)^2}{12}d'_c(\tau, t_0)d\tau$, where $d'_c(\tau, t_0) = [1 - (!2)\frac{(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)^2}{14} + \dots]$, in the interval $|\tau| \leq t_0$, using Result 5.1.2.b and the terms in $d'_c(\tau, t_0)$ converge, given $\omega_z(t_0) = O[\frac{1}{t_0}]$ and $\omega_z(t_0)\tau \leq 1$.

We see that the integral in $F_{d_c}(t_0) = -\frac{(\omega_z(t_0))^2}{12}I(t_0)$ given by $I(t_0) = \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} (\tau)^2 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d'_c(\tau, t_0)d\tau$ converges to a finite value, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds (Details in Section 5.3) and hence $F_{d_c}(t_0) = -\frac{(\omega_z(t_0))^2}{12}I(t_0)$ becomes smaller and smaller approaching zero, due to the term $(\omega_z(t_0))^2$ where $\omega_z(t_0) = O[\frac{1}{t_0}]$, as t_0 increases. Hence $|F_{d_c}(t_0) \cos(\theta_{t_0})| \ll |F_{A_{min}}|$ (**Result 5.1.2.e**)

We see that the third term in $F_B(t_0)$ in Eq. 75, is given by $D_{d_c}(t_0) = \int_{-t_0}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d_c(\tau, t_0)d\tau$ in Eq. 74, and $|D_{d_c}(t_0)| \ll |F_{A_{min}}|$ using arguments in Result 5.1.2.e. (**Result 5.1.2.f**)

We see that the second term in in $F_B(t_0)$ in Eq. 75, given by $F_s(t_0) = F_{s_1}(t_0) + F_{d_s}(t_0) = \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)\sin(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)d\tau = \omega_z(t_0) \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} \tau E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d'_s(\tau, t_0)d\tau$, where $\sin(\omega_z(t_0)\tau) =$

$\omega_z(t_0)\tau - \frac{(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)^3}{!3} + \frac{(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)^5}{!5} + \dots = (\omega_z(t_0)\tau)d'_s(\tau, t_0)$ where $d'_s(\tau, t_0) = [1 - \frac{(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)^2}{!3} + \dots]$, in the interval $|\tau| \leq t_0$, using Result 5.1.2.b and the terms in $d'_s(\tau, t_0)$ converge, given $\omega_z(t_0) = O[\frac{1}{t_0}]$ and $\omega_z(t_0)\tau \leq 1$.

We see that the integral in $F_s(t_0) = \omega_z(t_0)J(t_0)$ given by $J(t_0) = \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} \tau E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d'_s(\tau, t_0)d\tau$ converges to a finite value, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds (Details in Section 5.3) and hence $F_s(t_0) = \omega_z(t_0)J(t_0)$ becomes smaller and smaller approaching zero, due to the term $\omega_z(t_0)$ where $\omega_z(t_0) = O[\frac{1}{t_0}]$, as t_0 increases. Hence $|F_s(t_0) \sin(\theta_{t_0})|$ is $\ll |F_{A_{min}}|$ (**Result 5.1.2.g**)

We use Result 5.1.2.d, Result 5.1.2.e, Result 5.1.2.f and Result 5.1.2.g and see that $|F_B(t_0)| \leq |\cos(\theta_{t_0})F_{d_c}(t_0)| + |\sin(\theta_{t_0})(F_{s_1}(t_0) + F_{d_s}(t_0))| + |D_{d_c}(t_0)| \ll |F_{A_{min}}|$ and hence $|F(t_0)| = e^{\sigma t_0}|F_A(t_0) + F_B(t_0)|$ in Eq. 75 approaches $e^{\sigma t_0}|F_{A_{min}}| \neq 0$, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds.

We see that $|X(t_0)| \ll 1$ in Section 5.2 and we can choose $|X(t_0)| \ll |F(t_0)|$ by increasing t_0 to $t'_0 \gg t_0$ and hence $F(t_0)$ does not cancel $X(t_0)$ in Eq. 72 (**Result 5.1.2.h**). Hence we see that $F_X(t_0) = F(t_0) + X(t_0)$ **cannot** equal zero in Eq. 72, using Result 5.1.2.h and hence Statement F is **false** for Case 2A.

Hence Statement F is **false** for Case 2A and $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ **does not** approach a constant, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds and hence $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ increases with t_0 , as t_0 increases.

Case 2B: We consider the case $F_A(t_0) = \cos(\theta_{t_0})F_0(t_0) + D_0(t_0)$ in Eq. 75, becomes smaller and smaller approaching **zero**, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds, using Statement F and Result 5.1.2.c and $\theta_{t_0} = \omega_z(t_0)t_0 \neq m\pi$ and $\theta_{t_0} \neq (2m+1)\frac{\pi}{2}$, for integer m , where both $\cos(\theta_{t_0})$ and $\sin(\theta_{t_0})$ are **non-zero**. (**Result 5.1.2.i**)

We take $F_B(t_0) = \cos(\theta_{t_0})F_{d_c}(t_0) + \sin(\theta_{t_0})(F_{s_1}(t_0) + F_{d_s}(t_0)) + D_{d_c}(t_0)$ in Eq. 75 and we can show that, compared to the second term $F_{s_1}(t_0) = \omega_z(t_0) \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} \tau E_0(\tau)[e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1]d\tau$, the other terms have **faster** fall-off rate as t_0 increases, due to terms $(\omega_z(t_0))^r$ where $r > 1$ and $\omega_z(t_0) = O[\frac{1}{t_0}]$ and hence **negligible**, as shown below.

In Eq. 73, Eq. 74 and Eq. 75, we consider the integral $F_s(t_0) = \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \sin(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)d\tau = F_{s_1}(t_0) + F_{d_s}(t_0) = \omega_z(t_0) \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} \tau E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau + \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d_s(\tau, t_0)d\tau$, using $d_s(\tau, t_0) = -\frac{(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)^3}{!3} + \frac{(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)^5}{!5} + \dots$ where $d_s(\tau, t_0) = -\frac{(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)^3}{!3}d'_s(\tau, t_0)$ and $d'_s(\tau, t_0) = [1 - (!3)\frac{(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)^2}{!5} + \dots]$, in the interval $|\tau| \leq t_0$, using Result 5.1.2.b and the terms in $d'_s(\tau, t_0)$ converge, given $\omega_z(t_0) = O[\frac{1}{t_0}]$ and $\omega_z(t_0)\tau \leq 1$. We see that $F_{s_1}(t_0) = \omega_z(t_0)K(t_0)$ with $K(t_0) = \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} \tau E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau$ and $K(t_0)$ converges to a **non-zero** and finite value, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds, as shown in Section 5.3. (**Result 5.1.2.j**)

The second integral in $F_s(t_0)$ in above para, given by $F_{d_s}(t_0) = \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d_s(\tau, t_0)d\tau = -\frac{(\omega_z(t_0))^3}{!3} \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} \tau^3 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d'_s(\tau, t_0)d\tau$ with the **term** $(\omega_z(t_0))^3$, becomes smaller and smaller approaching zero **faster than** the first integral $F_{s_1}(t_0) = (\omega_z(t_0) \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} \tau E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau)$ with the **term** $(\omega_z(t_0))$, using $\omega_z(t_0) = O[\frac{1}{t_0}]$, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds.

Hence $|F_{d_s}(t_0)| \ll |F_{s_1}(t_0)|$ and $e^{\sigma t_0}|F_{d_s}(t_0)| \ll e^{\sigma t_0}|F_{s_1}(t_0)|$ and $e^{\sigma t_0}F_{s_1}(t_0)$ is the **dominant**

term in Case 2B, which increases exponentially as t_0 increases, due to the factor $\frac{e^{\sigma t_0}}{t_0}$. It is noted that the multiplication factor $e^{\sigma t_0}$ is taken from the equation for $F(t_0)$ in Eq. 75 (**Result 5.1.2.k**)

We see that the terms $F_{d_c}(t_0)$ and $D_{d_c}(t_0)$ in Eq. 75 have terms of the form $(\omega_z(t_0))^r$ where $r \geq 2$ and hence we can use arguments in above two paras and Result 5.1.2.j and Result 5.1.2.k, to show that these terms have **faster** fall-off rates of $O[\frac{1}{t_0^r}]$ and are **negligible**, compared to the term $F_{s_1}(t_0)$ which has a fall-off rate of $O[\frac{1}{t_0}]$, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds. (**Result 5.1.2.m**)

We use Result 5.1.2.j, Result 5.1.2.k and Result 5.1.2.m and see that, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds, $|F_B(t_0)|$ is **nearly equal** to $|\sin(\theta_{t_0})F_{s_1}(t_0)| > 0$ and hence $|F(t_0)| = e^{\sigma t_0}|F_A(t_0) + F_B(t_0)|$ is nearly equal to $e^{\sigma t_0}|F_B(t_0)|$ in Eq. 75, which approaches $e^{\sigma t_0}|\sin(\theta_{t_0})F_{s_1}(t_0)|$ which is of the order $O[\frac{e^{\sigma t_0}}{t_0}]$, using Result 5.1.2.k.

We see that $|X(t_0)| \ll 1$ in Section 5.2 and we can choose $|X(t_0)| \ll |F(t_0)|$ by increasing t_0 to $t'_0 \gg t_0$ and hence $F(t_0)$ does not cancel $X(t_0)$ in Eq. 72. Hence we see that $F_X(t_0) = F(t_0) + X(t_0)$ **cannot** equal zero in Eq. 72 and hence Statement F is **false** for Case 2B. (**Result 5.1.2.n**)

Hence Statement F is **false** for Case 2B and $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ **does not** approach a constant, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds and hence $\omega_z(t_0)t_0$ increases with t_0 , as t_0 increases, using Result 5.1.2.n.

Case 2C: We consider the specific case $\theta_{t_0} = \omega_z(t_0)t_0 = m\pi$ in Eq. 75 and we get $\sin(\theta_{t_0}) = 0$ and $\cos(\theta_{t_0}) = (-1)^m$ and hence $F(t_0) = e^{\sigma t_0}[(-1)^m F_0(t_0) + D_0(t_0) + (-1)^m F_{d_c}(t_0) + D_{d_c}(t_0)]$ in Eq. 75. (**Result 5.1.2.o**) We will show that $F(t_0)$ converges to a non-zero finite value, as t_0 increases.

Using Result 5.1.2.c, we see that the term $A_1(t_0) = (-1)^m F_0(t_0) + D_0(t_0) = \int_0^{t_0} E_0(\tau)((-1)^m 2(\cosh(2\sigma\tau) + 1) + e^{2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau$ and $A_1(t_0) = \int_0^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(2\cosh(2\sigma\tau) + 2 + e^{2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau > 0$ for even m and $A_1(t_0) = \int_0^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(-2\cosh(2\sigma\tau) - 2 + e^{2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau = \int_0^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(-e^{2\sigma\tau} - e^{-2\sigma\tau} - 2 + e^{2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau = -\int_0^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau < 0$ for odd m and hence $A_1(t_0)$ converges to a **non-zero** finite value for integer m , as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds, as shown in Section 5.3. (**Result 5.1.2.p**)

The term $A_2(t_0) = (-1)^m F_{d_c}(t_0) + D_{d_c}(t_0)$ in Result 5.1.2.o has fall-off rates of $O[\frac{1}{t_0^2}]$, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds, and **negligible** compared to $A_1(t_0)$, using arguments used in Result 5.1.2.e and Result 5.1.2.f. (**Result 5.1.2.q**)

Hence $F(t_0)$ nearly equals $e^{\sigma t_0}A_1(t_0)$, which converges to a **non-zero** finite value, which grows exponentially, using Result 5.1.2.o, Result 5.1.2.p and 5.1.2.q.

We see that $|X(t_0)| \ll 1$ in Section 5.2 and we can choose $|X(t_0)| \ll |F(t_0)|$ by increasing t_0 to $t'_0 \gg t_0$ and hence $F(t_0)$ does not cancel $X(t_0)$ in Eq. 72. Hence we see that $F_X(t_0) = F(t_0) + X(t_0)$ **cannot** equal zero in Eq. 72 and hence Statement F is **false**.

Case 2D: We consider the specific case $\theta_{t_0} = \omega_z(t_0)t_0 = (2m + 1)\frac{\pi}{2}$ in Eq. 75 and we get $\sin(\theta_{t_0}) = (-1)^m$ and $\cos(\theta_{t_0}) = 0$ and hence $F(t_0) = e^{\sigma t_0}[D_0(t_0) + (-1)^m(F_{s_1}(t_0) + F_{d_s}(t_0)) + D_{d_c}(t_0)]$ in Eq. 75. (**Result 5.1.2.r**) We will show that $F(t_0)$ converges to a non-zero finite value, as t_0 increases.

Using Result 5.1.2.c, we see that the term $D_0(t_0) = \int_0^{t_0} E_0(\tau)(e^{2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau > 0$ and converges to a **non-zero** finite value for integer m , as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds, as shown in Section 5.3. (**Result 5.1.2.s**)

The term $A_3(t_0) = (-1)^m(F_{s_1}(t_0) + F_{d_s}(t_0)) + D_{d_c}(t_0)$ in Result 5.1.2.r, has fall-off rates of $O[\frac{1}{t_0}]$, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds, and **negligible** compared to $D_0(t_0)$, using arguments used in Result 5.1.2.f and Result 5.1.2.g. (**Result 5.1.2.t**)

Hence $F(t_0)$ nearly equals $e^{\sigma t_0} D_0(t_0)$, which converges to a **non-zero** finite value, which grows exponentially, using Result 5.1.2.r, Result 5.1.2.s and 5.1.2.t.

We see that $|X(t_0)| \ll 1$ in Section 5.2 and we can choose $|X(t_0)| \ll |F(t_0)|$ by increasing t_0 to $t'_0 \gg t_0$ and hence $F(t_0)$ does not cancel $X(t_0)$ in Eq. 72. Hence we see that $F_X(t_0) = F(t_0) + X(t_0)$ **cannot** equal zero in Eq. 72 and hence Statement F is **false**.

5.2. $|X(t_0)| \ll 1$

We compute the **maximum** value of the absolute value of $X(t_0)$ in Eq. 68, for sufficiently large t_0 and $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$.

$$\begin{aligned} X(t_0) = & e^{\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^{-t_0} E_0(\tau)[e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1] \cos(\omega_z(t_0)(\tau - t_0))d\tau \\ & + e^{-\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^{-t_0} E_0(\tau)e^{-2\sigma\tau} \cos(\omega_z(t_0)(\tau + t_0))d\tau + e^{-\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^{-t_0} E_0(\tau) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)(\tau + t_0))d\tau \\ & + e^{\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^{-t_0} E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)d\tau + e^{-\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1) \cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (76)$$

We use $|f(t_0)| \leq \int |f_i(\tau, t_0)|d\tau$ where $f(t_0) = \int f_i(\tau, t_0)d\tau$ (link) and use $|\cos(\omega_z(t_0)(\tau - t_0))| \leq 1$, $|\cos(\omega_z(t_0)(\tau + t_0))| \leq 1$ and $|\cos(\omega_z(t_0)\tau)| \leq 1$ and $E_0(\tau) > 0$ for real τ . We combine first and fourth integrals and combine second and third integrals in Eq. 76 and rearrange as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} |X(t_0)| \leq & 2e^{\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^{-t_0} E_0(\tau)[e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1]d\tau + e^{-\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^{-t_0} E_0(\tau)[e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1]d\tau \\ & + e^{-\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^0 E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (77)$$

The second and third integrals in Eq. 77 converge given that the integrands have asymptotic exponential fall-off rate using Appendix C.3 and multiplied by the term $e^{-\sigma t_0}$, these integrals goes to zero, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds (**Result 5.2.a**).

We consider the first integral $I(t_0) = 2e^{\sigma t_0} \int_{-\infty}^{-t_0} E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau$ and substitute $\tau = -\tau$ and get $I(t_0) = 2e^{\sigma t_0} \int_{t_0}^{\infty} E_0(\tau)(e^{2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau$. (**Result 5.2.a.1**)

We see that $E_0(\tau)e^{2\sigma\tau}$ has an asymptotic minimum fall-off rate of $o[e^{-0.5|\tau|}]$ where $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$ (Details in Appendix C.3). Hence we write $|I(t_0)| \leq 2e^{\sigma t_0} K_I \int_{t_0}^{\infty} e^{-0.5\tau}d\tau = 2e^{\sigma t_0} K_I [\frac{e^{-0.5\tau}}{-0.5}]_{t_0}^{\infty} =$

$4e^{\sigma t_0} K_I e^{-0.5t_0} = K(t_0)$. (**Result 5.2.b**) The constant K_I is chosen as below.

It is noted that $K_I = \frac{E_0(t_0)(e^{2\sigma t_0} + 1)}{e^{-0.5t_0}}$ is chosen such that the integrand $e^{-0.5\tau}$ in above para, when evaluated at the lower limit t_0 and multiplied by the term K_I in the equation for $K(t_0)$, gives the **same** value $K_I e^{-0.5t_0}$, as the integrand $E_0(\tau)(e^{2\sigma\tau} + 1)$ in $I(t_0)$ in Result 5.2.a.1, when evaluated at the lower limit t_0 (**Note 5.2**).

For $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$, $|I(t_0)|$ has an asymptotic **minimum** fall-off rate of $o[e^{-(0.5-\sigma)t_0}]$ using Result 5.2.b and hence $|X(t_0)|$ goes to zero, using Result 5.2.a, Result 5.2.a.1 and Result 5.2.b, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds.

5.3. Derivation of Result A

In this section, it is shown that $I(t_0, r) = \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} (\tau)^r E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau$ converges to a non-zero and finite value, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds, for non-negative integer r and $-\frac{1}{2} < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$. Hence $(\omega_z(t_0))^r |I(t_0, r)|$ goes to zero, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds, for $\omega_z(t_0) = o[\frac{1}{t_0}]$ and $\omega_z(t_0) = O[\frac{1}{t_0}]$ and $r \geq 1$.

We see that $E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)$ is an absolutely integrable function, for $0 \leq |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$ given that it has exponential fall-off rates as $|\tau| \rightarrow \infty$. (Details in Appendix C.3 and Appendix C.4).

Hence $(\tau)^r E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)$ also has exponential fall-off rates as $|\tau| \rightarrow \infty$, and is an absolutely integrable function. Hence $I(t_0, r) = \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} (\tau)^r E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau < \infty$.

We see that $I(t_0, r) = \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} (\tau)^r E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau = \int_0^{t_0} (\tau)^r E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau + \int_{-t_0}^0 (\tau)^r E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau$. We substitute $\tau = -\tau$ in second integral and use $E_0(-\tau) = E_0(\tau)$ and get $\int_{-t_0}^0 (\tau)^r E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau = (-1)^r \int_0^{t_0} (\tau)^r E_0(\tau)(e^{2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau$. Hence $I(t_0, r) = \int_0^{t_0} (\tau)^r E_0(\tau)(e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau + (-1)^r \int_0^{t_0} (\tau)^r E_0(\tau)(e^{2\sigma\tau} + 1)d\tau$.

Hence $I(t_0, r) = 2 \int_0^{t_0} (\tau)^r E_0(\tau)(\cosh(2\sigma\tau) + 1)d\tau$ for **even** r and $I(t_0, r) = -2 \int_0^{t_0} (\tau)^r E_0(\tau) \sinh(2\sigma\tau)d\tau$ for **odd** r . Hence $I(t_0, r)$ is **non-zero** and finite, given that $E_0(\tau) > 0$ and the integrands in $I(t_0, r)$ are positive in the interval $0 \leq \tau \leq t_0$, for non-negative integer r . (**Result 5.3.1**).

As we increase t_0 to $t'_0 \gg t_0$, we see that $|I(t'_0, r)| > |I(t_0, r)| > 0$, using Result 5.3.1, given that $(\tau)^r E_0(\tau)(\cosh(2\sigma\tau) + 1) > 0$ and $(\tau)^r E_0(\tau) \sinh(2\sigma\tau) > 0$ for $0 \leq \tau \leq t_0$ (**Result 5.3.2**).

We can show that $(\omega_z(t_0))^r |I(t_0, r)|$ goes to zero, as t_0 increases to $t'_0 \gg t_0$, for $\omega_z(t_0) = o[\frac{1}{t_0}]$ and $\omega_z(t_0) = O[\frac{1}{t_0}]$ and $r \geq 1$. For **even** r , using Result 5.3.1, we see that $I(t'_0, r) = 2 \int_0^{t'_0} (\tau)^r E_0(\tau)(\cosh(2\sigma\tau) + 1)d\tau = \int_0^{t_0} (\tau)^r E_0(\tau)(e^{2\sigma\tau} + e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 2)d\tau + \int_{t_0}^{t'_0} (\tau)^r E_0(\tau)(e^{2\sigma\tau} + e^{-2\sigma\tau} + 2)d\tau = I(t_0, r) + J(t_0, t'_0, r)$. (**Result 5.3.3**)

Given that the integrand in $J(t_0, t'_0, r)$ has minimum asymptotic exponential fall-off rate of $o[e^{-0.5\tau}]$ using Appendix C.3, we get $J(t_0, t'_0, r) \leq K_I \int_{t_0}^{t'_0} e^{-0.5\tau} d\tau$, for sufficiently large $t'_0 \gg t_0$, where $K_I = \frac{(t_0)^r E_0(t_0)(e^{2\sigma t_0} + e^{-2\sigma t_0} + 2)}{e^{-0.5t_0}}$ is a constant chosen as in Note 5.2 in previous subsection. (**Result 5.3.4**)

We get $J(t_0, t'_0, r) \leq K_I \left[\frac{e^{-0.5r}}{-0.5} \right]_{t_0}^{t'_0} = -2K_I(e^{-0.5t'_0} - e^{-0.5t_0}) = 2K_I e^{-0.5t_0}(1 - e^{-0.5(t'_0 - t_0)})$. As we increase $t'_0 \gg t_0$, we see that $J(t_0, t'_0, r) \leq 2K_I e^{-0.5t_0}$ becomes smaller and smaller approaching zero and $I(t'_0, r) = I(t_0, r) + J(t_0, t'_0, r)$ **approaches** $I(t_0, r)$ in Result 5.3.1, which converges. Hence $I(t'_0, r)$ does not continue to increase with increasing t_0 . We get similar results for $I(t'_0, r)$ for **odd** r . Hence $(\omega_z(t_0))^r |I(t_0, r)|$ goes to zero, as t_0 increases to a larger and larger finite value without bounds, for $\omega_z(t_0) = o[\frac{1}{t_0}]$ and $\omega_z(t_0) = O[\frac{1}{t_0}]$ and $r \geq 1$. (**Result 5.3.5**)

6. Strictly decreasing $E_0(t)$ for $t > 0$

Let us consider $E_0(t) = \Phi(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t}] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}}$ in Eq. 1, where t is real, whose Fourier Transform is given by the entire function $E_{0\omega}(\omega) = \xi(\frac{1}{2} + i\omega)$. It is known that $\Phi(t)$ is positive for $|t| < \infty$ and its first derivative is negative for $t > 0$ and hence $\Phi(t)$ is a **strictly decreasing** function for $t > 0$. (Conrey, link 2, Pages 12-17, [8]). This is shown below. We take the term $2\pi n^2$ out of the brackets.

$$E_0(t) = \Phi(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t}] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 2\pi n^2 e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} [2\pi n^2 e^{4t} - 3e^{2t}] \quad (78)$$

We show that $X(t) = \frac{E_0(t)}{2}$ is a **strictly decreasing** function for $t > 0$ as follows.

- In Section 6.1, it is shown that the first derivative of $X(t)$, given by $\frac{dX(t)}{dt} < 0$ for $t > t_z$ where $t_z = \frac{1}{2} \log \frac{y_z}{\pi}$ and $y_z = 3.16$.
- In Section 6.2, it is shown that, $\frac{dX(t)}{dt} < 0$ for $0 < t \leq t_z$.

Hence $\frac{dX(t)}{dt} < 0$ for $t > 0$. Given that $2X(t) = E_0(t) = E_0(-t) > 0$ for $|t| < \infty$ (Details in Appendix C.5 and Appendix C.6), we see that $X(t)$ is strictly decreasing for $t > 0$ and $E_0(t) = 2X(t)$ is **strictly decreasing** for $t > 0$.

6.1. $\frac{dX(t)}{dt} < 0$ **for** $t > t_z$

We consider $X(t) = \frac{E_0(t)}{2} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \pi n^2 e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} [2\pi n^2 e^{4t} - 3e^{2t}]$ in Eq. 78 and take the first derivative of $X(t)$. We note that $E_0(t)$ and $X(t)$ are analytic functions for real t and infinitely differentiable in that interval. We compute $\frac{dX(t)}{dt}$ below and take the term e^{2t} out, in the last line

below.

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{dX(t)}{dt} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \pi n^2 e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} [8\pi n^2 e^{4t} - 6e^{2t} + (2\pi n^2 e^{4t} - 3e^{2t}) (\frac{1}{2} - 2\pi n^2 e^{2t})] \\
\frac{dX(t)}{dt} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \pi n^2 e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} [8\pi n^2 e^{4t} - 6e^{2t} + (\pi n^2 e^{4t} - \frac{3}{2} e^{2t} - 4\pi^2 n^4 e^{6t} + 6\pi n^2 e^{4t})] \\
\frac{dX(t)}{dt} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \pi n^2 e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} [-4\pi^2 n^4 e^{6t} + 15\pi n^2 e^{4t} - \frac{15}{2} e^{2t}] \\
\frac{dX(t)}{dt} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \pi n^2 e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} e^{2t} [-4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} + 15\pi n^2 e^{2t} - \frac{15}{2}] \quad (79)
\end{aligned}$$

We substitute $y = \pi e^{2t}$ in Eq. 79 and define $A(y)$ such that $\frac{dX(t)}{dt} = \pi e^{\frac{5t}{2}} A(y)$. [8]

$$A(y) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 e^{-n^2 y} [-4n^4 y^2 + 15n^2 y - \frac{15}{2}] \quad (80)$$

We see that $A(y) = 0$ at $y = \pi$ which corresponds to $t = 0$ given $y = \pi e^{2t}$ and $\frac{dX(t)}{dt} = \pi e^{\frac{5t}{2}} A(y)$, given that $\frac{dX(t)}{dt} = 0$ at $t = 0$. (**Result 6.1.a**) Because $X(t) = \frac{E_0(t)}{2}$ is an even function of variable t (Details in Appendix C.6) and hence $\frac{dX(t)}{dt}$ is an **odd** function of variable t .

The quadratic expression $B(y, n) = (-4n^4 y^2 + 15n^2 y - \frac{15}{2})$ in Eq. 80 equals zero at $y = y_r = \frac{-15n^2 \pm \sqrt{225n^4 - 120n^4}}{-8n^4} = \frac{(15 \pm \sqrt{105})}{8n^2}$ [8]. We see that the first derivative of $B(y, n)$ is given by $\frac{dB(y, n)}{dy} = -8n^4 y + 15n^2$ equals zero at $y = y_m = \frac{15}{8n^2}$. The second derivative of $B(y, n)$ given by $\frac{d^2 B(y, n)}{dy^2} = -8n^4$, is negative for all y and $n \geq 1$ and hence $B(y, n)$ is a **concave down** function for each n , which reaches a maximum at $y = y_m = \frac{15}{8n^2}$ and has zeros at $y = y_r = \frac{(15 \pm \sqrt{105})}{8n^2}$ and given the dominant term $-4n^4 y^2$ in Eq. 80, we see that $B(y, n) < 0$, for $y > \frac{(15 + \sqrt{105})}{8} = 3.1559$, for $n \geq 1$ and hence $B(y, n) < 0$ for $y > 3.16 = y_z$ and hence $A(y) < 0$ for finite $y > y_z$. Using $y = \pi e^{2t}$ and $\frac{dX(t)}{dt} = \pi e^{\frac{5t}{2}} A(y)$, we see that $\frac{dX(t)}{dt} < 0$ for $t > \frac{1}{2} \log \frac{y_z}{\pi} = t_z$ (**Result 6.1**). (concave down function)

We show in the next section that $\frac{dX(t)}{dt} < 0$ for $0 < t \leq t_z$. It suffices to show that $\frac{dA(y)}{dy} < 0$ for $\pi \leq y \leq y_z = 3.16$ and hence $A(y) < 0$ for $\pi < y \leq y_z = 3.16$, given that $A(y) = 0$ at $y = \pi$, using Result 6.1.a. [We use $y = \pi e^{2t}$ and $\frac{dX(t)}{dt} = \pi e^{\frac{5t}{2}} A(y)$ and $\frac{dX(t)}{dt} = 0$ at $t = 0$.]

6.2. $\frac{dX(t)}{dt} < 0$ for $0 < t \leq t_z$

It is shown in this section that $\frac{dA(y)}{dy} < 0$ for $\pi \leq y \leq 3.16$ and hence $A(y) < 0$ for $\pi < y \leq 3.16$ [8], given that $A(y) = 0$ at $y = \pi$. We take the derivative of $A(y)$ in Eq. 80 and take the factor n^2 out of the brackets in the last line below.

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{dA(y)}{dy} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 e^{-n^2 y} [-8n^4 y + 15n^2 + (-4n^4 y^2 + 15n^2 y - \frac{15}{2})(-n^2)] \\
\frac{dA(y)}{dy} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^4 e^{-n^2 y} [-8n^2 y + 15 + 4n^4 y^2 - 15n^2 y + \frac{15}{2}] = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^4 e^{-n^2 y} [4n^4 y^2 - 23n^2 y + \frac{45}{2}] \quad (81)
\end{aligned}$$

We examine the term $C(y, n) = n^4 e^{-n^2 y} (4n^4 y^2 - 23n^2 y + \frac{45}{2})$ in Eq. 81 in the interval $\pi \leq y \leq 3.16$ and show that $\frac{dA(y)}{dy} = C(y, 1) + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} C(y, n) < 0$, as follows.[8] We want the maximum value of $C(y, n)$ for each n and we consider the maximum value of positive terms and minimum value of absolute value of negative terms in the paragraphs below. (**Result 6.2.a**)

For $n = 1$, we see that $C(y, 1) = e^{-y} (4y^2 - 23y + \frac{45}{2}) = 4y^2 e^{-y} - 23y e^{-y} + \frac{45}{2} e^{-y} < 0$ in the interval $\pi \leq y \leq 3.16$ as follows. Given that $3.16^2 < 10$ and $\pi > 3.14$, in the interval $\pi \leq y \leq 3.16$, we see that $C(y, 1) < 4 * 10 e^{-3.14} - 23 * 3.14 e^{-3.16} + \frac{45}{2} e^{-3.14} = -0.3588 < -6e^{-3} = C_{max}(1)$ where $C_{max}(1)$ is the maximum value of $C(y, 1)$ in the interval $\pi \leq y \leq 3.16$, using Result 6.2.a.

$$C(y, 1) = e^{-y} (4y^2 - 23y + \frac{45}{2}) < -6e^{-3}, \quad \pi \leq y \leq 3.16 \quad (82)$$

For $n > 1$, in the interval $\pi \leq y \leq 3.16$, we can write $C(y, n)$ as follows, given that $\pi > 3.14$ and $3.16^2 < 10$ and the term $-23n^2 y < 0$ is omitted below, given that we want the maximum value of $C(y, n)$. We write the term $\frac{45}{2} < 4n^4 * 0.5$ and $e^{-0.14n^2} * 10.5 < 10$ for $n \geq 2$, using Result 6.2.a .

$$C(y, n) = n^4 e^{-n^2 y} (4n^4 y^2 - 23n^2 y + \frac{45}{2}) < n^4 e^{-\pi n^2} (4n^4 ((3.16)^2 + 0.5)) < 4n^8 e^{-3n^2} e^{-0.14n^2} * 10.5 < 40n^8 e^{-3n^2} \quad (83)$$

We want to show that $\frac{dA(y)}{dy} = C(y, 1) + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} C(y, n) < 0$ in the interval $\pi \leq y \leq 3.16$. Using Eq. 82 and Eq. 83, we write as follows. We multiply both sides by e^3 in the second line below.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dA(y)}{dy} &= C(y, 1) + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} C(y, n) < -6e^{-3} + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} 40n^8 e^{-3n^2} \\ e^3 \frac{dA(y)}{dy} &< -6 + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} 40n^8 e^{3-3n^2} \end{aligned} \quad (84)$$

We want to show that $e^3 \frac{dA(y)}{dy} < 0$ in the interval $\pi \leq y \leq 3.16$. We compute $\log(n^8 e^{3-3n^2})$ as follows. We note that $f(x) = \log x$ is a **concave down** function whose second derivative given by $-\frac{1}{x^2} < 0$ for $|x| < \infty$ and we can write $f(x) = \log x \leq f(x_0) + [\frac{df}{dx}]_{x=x_0} (x - x_0)$ using its **tangent line** equation. We see that $\frac{df}{dx} = \frac{1}{x}$. We set $x = n$ and $x_0 = 2$ and get $\log n \leq \log 2 + \frac{1}{2}(n - 2)$ below.

$$\begin{aligned} \log(n^8 e^{3-3n^2}) &= 8 \log n + (3 - 3n^2) \leq 8(\log 2 + \frac{1}{2}(n - 2)) + (3 - 3n^2) \\ \log(n^8 e^{3-3n^2}) &\leq 8 \log 2 + 4n - 5 - 3n^2 \end{aligned} \quad (85)$$

We note that $g(x) = 4x - 5 - 3x^2$ in Eq. 85 is a **concave down** function (concave down function), whose second derivative given by $-6 < 0$ for all x and we can write $g(x) \leq g(x_0) + [\frac{dg}{dx}]_{x=x_0} (x - x_0)$ using its **tangent line** equation. We see that $\frac{dg}{dx} = 4 - 6x$. We set $x = n$ and $x_0 = 2$ and get $g(n) \leq g(2) + [4 - 6x]_{x=2} (n - 2) = -9 - 8(n - 2)$ and write Eq. 85 as follows. We take the exponent e of both sides in the second line below.

$$\begin{aligned} \log(n^8 e^{3-3n^2}) &\leq 8 \log 2 - 9 - 8(n - 2) \leq 8 \log 2 - 1 + 8(1 - n) \\ n^8 e^{3-3n^2} &\leq e^{8 \log 2 - 1 + 8(1-n)} = 2^8 e^{-1} e^{8(1-n)} \end{aligned} \quad (86)$$

We substitute the result in Eq. 86 in Eq. 84 and simplify as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
e^3 \frac{dA(y)}{dy} &< -6 + 40 * 2^8 e^{-1} \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} e^{8(1-n)} \\
e^3 \frac{dA(y)}{dy} &< -6 + 40 * 2^8 e^{-1} * e^8 \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} e^{-8n} \\
e^3 \frac{dA(y)}{dy} &< -6 + 40 * 2^8 e^{-1} * e^8 \frac{e^{-8*2}}{1 - e^{-8}} \\
e^3 \frac{dA(y)}{dy} &< -6 + 40 * 2^8 e^{-1} * \frac{e^{-8}}{1 - e^{-8}} \\
e^3 \frac{dA(y)}{dy} &< -6 + 40 * 2^8 e^{-1} * \frac{1}{e^8 - 1}
\end{aligned} \tag{87}$$

We multiply Eq. 87 by $\frac{(e^8-1)}{6}$ and write as follows. The symbol \approx means "approximately equals".

$$e^3 \frac{dA(y)}{dy} \frac{(e^8 - 1)}{6} < -e^8 + 1 + 40e^{-1} * \frac{256}{6} \approx -2352 \tag{88}$$

We see that $e^3 \frac{dA(y)}{dy} \frac{(e^8-1)}{6} < 0$ in Eq. 88. Hence $\frac{dA(y)}{dy} < 0$ in the interval $\pi \leq y \leq 3.16$, given that $e^3 \frac{(e^8-1)}{6} > 0$ and $e > 2$. Given that $A(y) = 0$ at $y = \pi$ using Result 6.1.a, we see that $A(y) < 0$ in Eq. 80 , for $\pi < y \leq 3.16$ and $\frac{dX(t)}{dt} = \pi e^{\frac{5t}{2}} A(y) < 0$ in the interval $0 < t \leq t_z$. (**Result 6.2**)

In Section 6.1, it is shown that $\frac{dX(t)}{dt} < 0$ for $t > t_z$ (using Result 6.1). In this section, we have shown that $\frac{dX(t)}{dt} < 0$ for $0 < t \leq t_z$. Hence $\frac{dX(t)}{dt} < 0$ for $t > 0$.

Hence $E_0(t) = 2X(t)$ is a **strictly decreasing function** for $t > 0$ and strictly increasing for $t < 0$, given that $E_0(t) = E_0(-t) > 0$ for $t > 0$ (Details in Appendix C.5 and Appendix C.6).

7. Hurwitz Zeta Function and related functions

We can show that the new method is **not** applicable to Hurwitz zeta function and related zeta functions and **does not** contradict the existence of their non-trivial zeros away from the critical line given by $Re[s] = \frac{1}{2}$. The new method requires the **symmetry** relation $\xi(s) = \xi(1-s)$ and hence $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + i\omega) = \xi(\frac{1}{2} - i\omega)$ when evaluated at the critical line $s = \frac{1}{2} + i\omega$. This means $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + i\omega) = E_{0\omega}(\omega) = E_{0\omega}(-\omega)$ and $E_0(t) = E_0(-t)$ (Details in Appendix C.6) where $E_0(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t}] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}}$ and this condition is satisfied for Riemann's Zeta function.

It is **not** known that Hurwitz Zeta Function given by $\zeta(s, a) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(m+a)^s}$ satisfies a symmetry relation similar to $\xi(s) = \xi(1-s)$ where $\xi(s)$ is an entire function, for $a \neq 1$ and hence the condition $E_0(t) = E_0(-t)$ is **not** known to be satisfied [6]. Hence the new method is **not** applicable to Hurwitz zeta function and **does not** contradict the existence of their non-trivial zeros away from the critical line.

Dirichlet L-functions satisfy a symmetry relation $\xi(s, \chi) = \epsilon(\chi) \xi(1-s, \bar{\chi})$ [7] which does **not** translate to $E_0(t) = E_0(-t)$ required by the new method and hence this proof is **not** applicable to

them. This proof does not need or use Euler product.

We know that $\zeta(s) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{m^s}$ diverges for $Re[s] \leq 1$. Hence we derive a convergent and entire function $\xi(s)$ using the well known theorem $F(x) = 1 + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 x} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{x}} (1 + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi \frac{n^2}{x}})$, where $x > 0$ is real [4](link) and then derive $E_0(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t}] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}}$. In the case of **Hurwitz zeta** function and **other zeta functions** with non-trivial zeros away from the critical line, it is **not** known if a corresponding relation similar to $F(x)$ exists, which enables derivation of a convergent and entire function $\xi(s)$ and results in $E_0(t)$ as a Fourier transformable, real, even and analytic function. Hence the new method presented in this paper is **not** applicable to Hurwitz zeta function and related zeta functions.

The proof of Riemann Hypothesis presented in this paper is **only** for the specific case of Riemann's Zeta function and **only** for the **critical strip** $0 \leq |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$. This proof requires both $E_p(t)$ and $E_{p\omega}(\omega)$ to be Fourier transformable where $E_p(t) = E_0(t)e^{-\sigma t}$ is a real analytic function and uses the fact that $E_0(t)$ is an **even** function of variable t and $E_0(t) > 0$ for $|t| < \infty$ (Details in Appendix C.5) and $E_0(t)$ is **strictly decreasing** function for $t > 0$ (Details in Section 6). These conditions may **not** be satisfied for many other functions including those which have non-trivial zeros away from the critical line and hence the new method may **not** be applicable to such functions.

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7.1. Acknowledgments

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Appendix A. Derivation of $E_p(t)$

Let us start with Riemann's Xi Function $\xi(s)$ evaluated at $s = \frac{1}{2} + i\omega$ given by $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + i\omega) = E_{0\omega}(\omega)$. Its inverse Fourier Transform is given by $E_0(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} E_{0\omega}(\omega) e^{i\omega t} d\omega = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t}] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}}$ using Eq. 1.

We will show in this section that the inverse Fourier Transform of the function $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega) = E_{p\omega}(\omega)$, is given by $E_p(t) = E_0(t) e^{-\sigma t}$ where $0 < |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$ is real. We use $E_{p\omega}(\omega) = E_{0\omega}(\omega - i\sigma)$ below.

$$\begin{aligned} \xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega) &= \xi(\frac{1}{2} + i(\omega - i\sigma)) = E_{p\omega}(\omega) = E_{0\omega}(\omega - i\sigma) \\ E_p(t) &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} E_{p\omega}(\omega) e^{i\omega t} d\omega = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} E_{0\omega}(\omega - i\sigma) e^{i\omega t} d\omega \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

We substitute $\omega' = \omega - i\sigma$ in Eq. A.1 as follows. We get $\omega = \omega' + i\sigma$ and $d\omega = d\omega'$.

$$E_p(t) = e^{-\sigma t} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty - i\sigma}^{\infty - i\sigma} E_{0\omega}(\omega') e^{i\omega' t} d\omega' \quad (\text{A.2})$$

We can evaluate the above integral in the complex plane using contour integration, substituting $\omega' = z = x + iy$ and we use a rectangular contour comprised of C_1 along the line $z = (-\infty, \infty)$, C_2 along the line $z = (\infty, \infty - i\sigma)$, C_3 along the line $z = (\infty - i\sigma, -\infty - i\sigma)$ and then C_4 along the line $z = (-\infty - i\sigma, -\infty)$. We can see that $E_{0\omega}(z) = \xi(\frac{1}{2} + iz)$ has no singularities in the region bounded by the contour because $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + iz)$ is an entire function in the complex plane.

We use the fact that $E_{0\omega}(z) = \xi(\frac{1}{2} + iz) = \xi(\frac{1}{2} - y + ix) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} E_0(t) e^{-izt} dt = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} E_0(t) e^{yt} e^{-ixt} dt$, **goes to zero** as $x \rightarrow \pm\infty$ when $-\sigma \leq y \leq 0$, as per Riemann-Lebesgue Lemma (link), because $E_0(t) e^{yt}$ is a absolutely integrable function for real t (Details in Appendix A.1). Hence the integral in Eq. A.2 **vanishes** along the contours C_2 and C_4 . Using Cauchy's Integral theorem, we can write Eq. A.2 as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} E_p(t) &= e^{-\sigma t} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} E_{0\omega}(\omega') e^{i\omega' t} d\omega' \\ E_p(t) &= E_0(t) e^{-\sigma t} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t}] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} e^{-\sigma t} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Thus we have arrived at the desired result $E_p(t) = E_0(t) e^{-\sigma t}$. **Alternate** derivation of $E_0(t)$ and $E_p(t)$ are in Appendix B.1.

Appendix A.1. $E_y(t) = E_0(t) e^{yt}$ is an absolutely integrable function

We see that $E_0(t) > 0$ and finite for $-\infty < t < \infty$ (Details in Appendix C.5). Hence $E_y(t) = E_0(t) e^{yt} > 0$ and finite for all $-\infty < t < \infty$, for $-\sigma \leq y \leq 0$ and $0 \leq |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$ (**Result A.1.1**).

$E_0(t)$ has an asymptotic **exponential** fall-off rate of $o[e^{-1.5|t|}]$ (using Appendix C.3) and hence $E_y(t) = E_0(t)e^{yt}$ has an asymptotic **exponential** fall-off rate of $o[e^{-|t|}]$ (using $o[e^{-(1.5+y)|t|}]$), for $-\sigma \leq y \leq 0$ and $0 \leq |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$. Hence $E_y(t) = E_0(t)e^{yt}$ decays exponentially, at $t \rightarrow \pm\infty$. (**Result A.1.2**)

Using Result A.1.1 and A.1.2, we can write $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |E_y(t)|dt$ is finite and $E_y(t)$ is an absolutely **integrable function** (Details in Appendix C.4) and its Fourier transform $E_{y\omega}(\omega)$ goes to zero as $\omega \rightarrow \pm\infty$, as per Riemann Lebesgue Lemma (link).

Appendix B. Details of entire function $\xi(s)$

In this section, we will start with Riemann's Xi function $\xi(s)$ and take the inverse Fourier Transform of $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + i\omega) = E_{0\omega}(\omega)$ and show the result $E_0(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t}] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}}$ and $E_p(t) = E_0(t)e^{-\sigma t}$.

We will use the equation for $\xi(s)$ derived in Ellison's book "Prime Numbers" pages 151-152 which uses **the well known theorem** $1 + 2w(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{x}}(1 + 2w(\frac{1}{x}))$, where $w(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 x}$ and $x > 0$ is real. [4] (link).

$$\xi(s) = \frac{1}{2}s(s-1)\Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2}\right)\pi^{-\frac{s}{2}}\zeta(s) = \frac{1}{2}[1 + s(s-1) \int_1^{\infty} (x^{\frac{s}{2}} + x^{\frac{1-s}{2}})w(x)\frac{dx}{x}] \quad (\text{B.1})$$

We see that $\xi(s)$ is an entire function, for all values of s in the complex plane and hence we get an analytic continuation of $\xi(s)$ over the entire complex plane. We see that $\xi(s) = \xi(1-s)$ [4].

Appendix B.1. Derivation of $E_p(t)$ and $E_0(t)$

Given that $w(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 x}$, we substitute $x = e^{2t}, \frac{dx}{x} = 2dt$ in Eq. B.1 and evaluate at $s = \frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega$ as follows.

$$\xi\left(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega\right) = \frac{1}{2}[1 + 2\left(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega\right)\left(-\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega\right) \int_0^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} (e^{\frac{t}{2}} e^{\sigma t} e^{i\omega t} + e^{\frac{t}{2}} e^{-\sigma t} e^{-i\omega t}) dt] \quad (\text{B.2})$$

We can substitute $t = -t$ in the first term in above integral and simplify above equation as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \xi\left(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega\right) &= \frac{1}{2} + \left(-\frac{1}{4} + \sigma^2 - \omega^2 + i\omega(2\sigma)\right) \left[\int_{-\infty}^0 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{-2t}} e^{\frac{-t}{2}} e^{-\sigma t} e^{-i\omega t} dt \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \int_0^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} e^{-\sigma t} e^{-i\omega t} dt \right] \quad (\text{B.3}) \end{aligned}$$

We can write this as follows.

$$\xi\left(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega\right) = \frac{1}{2} + \left(-\frac{1}{4} + \sigma^2 - \omega^2 + i\omega(2\sigma)\right) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{-2t}} e^{\frac{-t}{2}} u(-t) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} u(t) \right] e^{-\sigma t} e^{-i\omega t} dt \quad (\text{B.4})$$

We define $A(t) = [\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{-2t}} e^{\frac{-t}{2}} u(-t) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} u(t)] e^{-\sigma t}$ and get the **inverse Fourier transform** of $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega) = E_{p\omega}(\omega)$ in above equation given by $E_p(t)$ as follows. We use dirac delta function $\delta(t)$.

$$\begin{aligned} E_p(t) &= \frac{1}{2}\delta(t) + (-\frac{1}{4} + \sigma^2)A(t) + 2\sigma \frac{dA(t)}{dt} + \frac{d^2 A(t)}{dt^2} \\ A(t) &= [\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{-2t}} e^{\frac{-t}{2}} u(-t) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} u(t)] e^{-\sigma t} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.5})$$

We compute the derivatives of $A(t)$ as follows. We note that $[A(t)]_{t=0+} = [A(t)]_{t=0-} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dA(t)}{dt} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{-2t}} e^{\frac{-t}{2}} e^{-\sigma t} [-\frac{1}{2} - \sigma + 2\pi n^2 e^{-2t}] u(-t) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} e^{-\sigma t} [\frac{1}{2} - \sigma - 2\pi n^2 e^{2t}] u(t) \\ \frac{d^2 A(t)}{dt^2} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{-2t}} e^{\frac{-t}{2}} e^{-\sigma t} [-4\pi n^2 e^{-2t} + (-\frac{1}{2} - \sigma + 2\pi n^2 e^{-2t})^2] u(-t) \\ &\quad + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} e^{-\sigma t} [-4\pi n^2 e^{2t} + (\frac{1}{2} - \sigma - 2\pi n^2 e^{2t})^2] u(t) + A_0 \delta(t) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.6})$$

We use $A_0 = [\frac{dA(t)}{dt}]_{t=0+} - [\frac{dA(t)}{dt}]_{t=0-} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2} (\frac{1}{2} - \sigma - 2\pi n^2 - (-\frac{1}{2} - \sigma + 2\pi n^2)) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2} (1 - 4\pi n^2)$.

We can simplify above equation as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2 A(t)}{dt^2} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{-2t}} e^{\frac{-t}{2}} e^{-\sigma t} [\frac{1}{4} + \sigma^2 + \sigma + 4\pi^2 n^4 e^{-4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{-2t} - 4\sigma \pi n^2 e^{-2t}] u(-t) \\ &\quad + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} e^{-\sigma t} [\frac{1}{4} + \sigma^2 - \sigma + 4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t} + 4\sigma \pi n^2 e^{2t}] u(t) + \delta(t) [\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2} (1 - 4\pi n^2)] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.7})$$

We use the fact that $F(x) = 1 + 2w(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{x}}(1 + 2w(\frac{1}{x}))$, where $w(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 x}$ and $x > 0$ is real [4], and we take the first derivative of $F(x)$ and evaluate it at $x = 1$ and get $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2} (1 - 4\pi n^2) = -\frac{1}{2}$ (Details in Appendix B.2) and hence **dirac delta terms cancel each other** in Eq. B.5 written

as follows using Eq. B.6 and Eq. B.7.

$$\begin{aligned}
E_p(t) &= \frac{1}{2}\delta(t) + \left(-\frac{1}{4} + \sigma^2\right)A(t) + 2\sigma\frac{dA(t)}{dt} + \frac{d^2A(t)}{dt^2} \\
E_p(t) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{-2t}} e^{\frac{-t}{2}} e^{-\sigma t} \left[-\frac{1}{4} + \sigma^2 + 2\sigma\left(-\frac{1}{2} - \sigma + 2\pi n^2 e^{-2t}\right)\right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{1}{4} + \sigma^2 + \sigma + 4\pi^2 n^4 e^{-4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{-2t} - 4\sigma\pi n^2 e^{-2t}\right] u(-t) \\
&+ \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} e^{-\sigma t} \left[-\frac{1}{4} + \sigma^2 + 2\sigma\left(\frac{1}{2} - \sigma - 2\pi n^2 e^{2t}\right) + \frac{1}{4} + \sigma^2 - \sigma + 4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t} + 4\sigma\pi n^2 e^{2t}\right] u(t) \\
E_p(t) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{-2t}} e^{\frac{-t}{2}} e^{-\sigma t} D(t, n) u(-t) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} e^{-\sigma t} C(t, n) u(t)
\end{aligned} \tag{B.8}$$

We cancel the common terms in Eq. B.8 and simplify above equation as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
C(t, n) &= -\frac{1}{4} + \sigma^2 + \sigma - 2\sigma^2 - 4\sigma\pi n^2 e^{2t} + \frac{1}{4} + \sigma^2 - \sigma + 4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t} + 4\sigma\pi n^2 e^{2t} \\
&\quad C(t, n) = 4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t} \\
D(t, n) &= -\frac{1}{4} + \sigma^2 - \sigma - 2\sigma^2 + 4\sigma\pi n^2 e^{-2t} + \frac{1}{4} + \sigma^2 + \sigma + 4\pi^2 n^4 e^{-4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{-2t} - 4\sigma\pi n^2 e^{-2t} \\
&\quad D(t, n) = 4\pi^2 n^4 e^{-4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{-2t}
\end{aligned} \tag{B.9}$$

We see that $D(t, n) = C(-t, n)$. Hence we can write Eq. B.8 as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
E_p(t) &= [E_0(-t)u(-t) + E_0(t)u(t)]e^{-\sigma t} \\
E_0(t) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C(t, n)e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t}]e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}}
\end{aligned} \tag{B.10}$$

We use the fact that $E_0(t) = E_0(-t)$ (Details in Appendix C.6) and $u(t) + u(-t) = 1$ and we arrive at the desired result for $E_p(t)$ as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
E_0(t) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t}]e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} \\
E_p(t) &= E_0(t)e^{-\sigma t} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t}]e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} e^{-\sigma t}
\end{aligned} \tag{B.11}$$

Appendix B.2. Derivation of $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2} (1 - 4\pi n^2) = -\frac{1}{2}$

In this section, we derive $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2} (1 - 4\pi n^2) = -\frac{1}{2}$. We use the fact that $F(x) = 1 + 2w(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{x}}(1 + 2w(\frac{1}{x}))$, where $w(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 x}$ and $x > 0$ is real [4], and we take the first derivative of $F(x)$

and evaluate it at $x = 1$.

$$\begin{aligned}
F(x) &= 1 + 2w(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{x}}(1 + 2w(\frac{1}{x})) \\
F(x) &= 1 + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 x} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{x}}(1 + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 \frac{1}{x}}) \\
\frac{dF(x)}{dx} &= 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-\pi n^2) e^{-\pi n^2 x} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{x}} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (2\pi n^2) e^{-\pi n^2 \frac{1}{x}} (\frac{1}{x^2}) + (1 + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2 \frac{1}{x}}) (\frac{-1}{2}) \frac{1}{x^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (\text{B.12})
\end{aligned}$$

We evaluate the above equation at $x = 1$ and we simplify as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
[\frac{dF(x)}{dx}]_{x=1} &= 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-\pi n^2) e^{-\pi n^2} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (2\pi n^2) e^{-\pi n^2} + (1 + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2}) (\frac{-1}{2}) \\
&\qquad\qquad\qquad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\pi n^2} (1 - 4\pi n^2) = -\frac{1}{2} \quad (\text{B.13})
\end{aligned}$$

Appendix C. Properties of Fourier Transforms

Appendix C.1. $E_p(t), h(t)$ are absolutely integrable functions and their Fourier Transforms are finite.

The inverse Fourier Transform of the function $E_{p\omega}(\omega) = \xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega)$ is given by $E_p(t) = E_0(t)e^{-\sigma t}$ (Appendix A). In Eq. 1, we see that $E_0(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t}] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} > 0$ and finite for all $-\infty < t < \infty$ (Details in Appendix C.5). Hence $E_p(t) = E_0(t)e^{-\sigma t} > 0$ and finite for all $-\infty < t < \infty$ and $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$.

It is shown in Appendix C.3 that $E_0(t)$ has an asymptotic **exponential** fall-off rate of $o[e^{-1.5|t|}]$ and hence $E_p(t) = E_0(t)e^{-\sigma t}$ has an asymptotic **exponential** fall-off rate of $o[e^{-|t|}]$ (using $e^{-(1.5-\sigma)|t|}$), for $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$. Hence $E_p(t)$ goes to zero, at $t \rightarrow \pm\infty$ and we showed that $E_p(t) > 0$ and finite for all $-\infty < t < \infty$ in the last paragraph. (**Result C.1.1**) Hence $E_{p\omega}(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} E_p(t) e^{-i\omega t} dt$, evaluated at $\omega = 0$ **cannot** be zero. Hence $E_{p\omega}(\omega)$ **does not have a zero** at $\omega = 0$ and hence $\omega_0 \neq 0$.

Given that $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + \sigma + i\omega) = E_{p\omega}(\omega)$ is an entire function in the whole of s-plane, it is finite for real ω and also for $\omega = 0$. Hence $E_{p\omega}(0) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} E_p(t) dt$ is finite. Using Result C.1.1, we can write $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |E_p(t)| dt$ is finite and $E_p(t)$ is an absolutely **integrable function** and its Fourier transform $E_{p\omega}(\omega)$ converges and goes to zero as $\omega \rightarrow \pm\infty$, as per Riemann Lebesgue Lemma (link).

Using the arguments in above paragraph, we replace σ in $E_p(t) = E_0(t)e^{-\sigma t}$ by 0 and 2σ respectively and see that $E_0(t)$ and $E_0(t)e^{-2\sigma t}$ are absolutely **integrable** functions and the integrals $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |E_0(t)| dt < \infty$ and $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |E_0(t)e^{-2\sigma t}| dt < \infty$.

Given that $E_p(t) = E_0(t)e^{-\sigma t}$ is an absolutely integrable function, its shifted versions are absolutely integrable and we see that $E_p(t+t_0)$ and $E_p(t-t_0)$ in Eq. 6 are absolutely integrable functions, for a finite shift of t_0 . (We substitute $t-t_0 = \tau$ and $dt = d\tau$ and get $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |E_p(t-t_0)| dt = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |E_p(\tau)| d\tau < \infty$

and hence $E_p(t - t_0)$ is an absolutely integrable function, given that $E_p(t)$ is absolutely integrable. Same argument holds for $E_p(t + t_0)$.

We see that $h(t) = e^{\sigma t}u(-t) + e^{-\sigma t}u(t)$ is an absolutely **integrable function** because $h(t) > 0$ for real t and $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |h(t)|dt = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h(t)dt = [\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h(t)e^{-i\omega t}dt]_{\omega=0} = [\frac{1}{\sigma-i\omega} + \frac{1}{\sigma+i\omega}]_{\omega=0} = \frac{2}{\sigma}$, is finite for $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$ and its Fourier transform $H(\omega)$ converges and goes to zero as $\omega \rightarrow \pm\infty$, as per Riemann Lebesgue Lemma (link).

Appendix C.2. Convolution integral convergence

Let us consider $h(t) = e^{\sigma t}u(-t) + e^{-\sigma t}u(t)$ whose first derivative given by $\frac{dh(t)}{dt} = \sigma e^{\sigma t}u(-t) - \sigma e^{-\sigma t}u(t)$ and $A_0 = [\frac{dh(t)}{dt}]_{t=0+} - [\frac{dh(t)}{dt}]_{t=0-} = -2\sigma \neq 0$, for $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$ and hence $\frac{dh(t)}{dt}$ is **discontinuous** at $t = 0$. The second derivative of $h(t)$ given by $h_2(t)$ has a Dirac delta function $A_0\delta(t)$ where $A_0 = -2\sigma$ and its Fourier transform $H_2(\omega)$ has a constant term A_0 , corresponding to the Dirac delta function.

This means $h(t)$ is obtained by integrating $h_2(t)$ twice and its Fourier transform $H(\omega)$ has a term $\frac{A_0}{(i\omega)^2}$ (link) and has a **fall off rate** of $\frac{1}{\omega^2}$ as $|\omega| \rightarrow \infty$. (**Result C.2**)

We see that $G(\omega', t_0)$ converges for real ω' (Eq. 19 and Eq. 22) and $G(\omega - \omega', t_0)$ also converges for real ω and both have a minimum fall-off rate of $\frac{1}{\omega^0} = 1$ as $|\omega| \rightarrow \infty$, given that inverse Fourier transform of $G(\omega', t_0)$ given by $g(t, t_0)$ converges. Using Result C.2, the integrand $G(\omega - \omega', t_0)H(\omega')$ in Eq. C.1 has a **minimum** fall off rate of $\frac{1}{\omega^2}$ as $|\omega| \rightarrow \infty$. Hence the convolution integral below converges to a finite value for real ω .

$$F(\omega, t_0) = \frac{1}{2\pi} [G(\omega, t_0) * H(\omega)] = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} G(\omega', t_0)H(\omega - \omega')d\omega' = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} G(\omega - \omega', t_0)H(\omega')d\omega' \quad (\text{C.1})$$

Appendix C.3. Exponential Fall off rate of $E_0(t)$, $E_p(t)$ and $x(t) = E_0(t)e^{-2\sigma t}$

We can write $E_0(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t}] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}}$ in Eq. 1 as follows. We take the term $2\pi n^2 e^{2t}$ out of the brackets below. In the term $e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}}$, we use Taylor series expansion around $t = 0$ for $e^{2t} = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2t)^r}{r!}$, given that e^{2t} is an analytic function for real t .

$$\begin{aligned} E_0(t) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 2\pi n^2 e^{2t} [2\pi n^2 e^{2t} - 3] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 2\pi n^2 e^{2t} [2\pi n^2 e^{2t} - 3] e^{-\pi n^2 (1+2t)} e^{-\pi n^2 (\frac{(2t)^2}{12} + \frac{(2t)^3}{13} \dots)} e^{\frac{t}{2}} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.2})$$

We take the term $e^{-2\pi t}$ out of the summation, corresponding to $n = 1$ and then take the term $2\pi e^{4t} e^{\frac{t}{2}} = 2\pi e^{\frac{9t}{2}}$ out and write Eq. C.2 as follows.

$$E_0(t) = 2\pi e^{-2\pi t} e^{\frac{9t}{2}} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 [2\pi n^2 - 3e^{-2t}] e^{-\pi n^2} e^{-2\pi(n^2-1)t} e^{-\pi n^2 (\frac{(2t)^2}{12} + \frac{(2t)^3}{13} \dots)} \quad (\text{C.3})$$

For $t > 0$, we see that the term corresponding to $n = 1$ in Eq. C.3 has an asymptotic fall-off rate of $o[e^{-1.5t}]$ (using $e^{-(2\pi-\frac{9}{2})t}$). The terms corresponding to $n > 1$ have higher fall-off rates, due to the term $e^{-2\pi(n^2-1)t}$.

Hence we see that $E_0(t)$ has an asymptotic fall-off rate of $o[e^{-1.5t}]$, for $t > 0$. Given that $E_0(t) = E_0(-t)$ (Details in Appendix C.6), we see that $E_0(t)$ has an **exponential** asymptotic fall-off rate of $o[e^{-1.5|t|}]$.

Similarly, $E_0(t)e^{-\sigma t}$ has an asymptotic **exponential** fall-off rate of $o[e^{-|t|}]$ (using $e^{-(1.5-\sigma)|t|}$) and $E_0(t)e^{-2\sigma t}$ has an asymptotic **exponential** fall-off rate of $o[e^{-0.5|t|}]$ (using $e^{-(1.5-2\sigma)|t|}$), for $0 \leq |\sigma| < \frac{1}{2}$.

The above results which show **exponential** fall-off rates for above mentioned functions, continue to hold, as $|t|$ increases to a larger and larger finite value, without bounds.

Appendix C.4. **Absolutely integrable functions**

We see that a real function $y(t)$ which is finite for all t and has an asymptotic falloff rate of $O[\frac{1}{t^2}]$ is an absolutely integrable function, given that $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |y(t)| dt = \int_{-\infty}^{-T} |y(t)| dt + \int_{-T}^T |y(t)| dt + \int_T^{\infty} |y(t)| dt$ is finite, for non-zero and finite T , because when we integrate the integrand $|y(t)|$ with order $O[\frac{1}{t^2}]$, we get the result $O[\frac{1}{t}]$, which is finite at the limit $t = \pm T$ and the result $O[\frac{1}{t}]$ is zero at the limit $t \rightarrow \pm\infty$. If $y(t)$ has an exponential asymptotic falloff rate, when we integrate the integrand $|y(t)|$ with order $O[e^{-A|t|}]$ for real $A > 0$, we get the result $O[\frac{1}{A}e^{-A|t|}]$, which is finite at the limit $t = \pm T$ and the result is zero at the limit $t \rightarrow \pm\infty$ and hence $y(t)$ is an absolutely integrable function.

Appendix C.5. $E_0(t) > 0$ for $-\infty < t < \infty$

For $0 \leq t < \infty$, we can show that $E_0(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f(t, n) > 0$ where $f(t, n) = [4\pi^2 n^4 e^{4t} - 6\pi n^2 e^{2t}] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} = 2\pi n^2 e^{2t} [2\pi n^2 e^{2t} - 3] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}}$ as follows.

The sum is positive because each summand $f(t, n)$ is positive for finite n , and each summand is positive because the term $2\pi n^2 e^{2t} - 3 > 0$ for all $t \geq 0$ and $n \geq 1$, given that $\pi > 3$ and $2\pi n^2 e^{2t} e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} > 0$ for $0 \leq t < \infty$ and finite $n \geq 1$. (**Result C.7.1**)

For $t = 0$ and $n = 1$, we see that $f(0, 1) = 2\pi[2\pi - 3]e^{-\pi} > 0$.

For $t = 0$ and for **each finite** $n \geq 1$, we see that $f(0, n) = 2\pi n^2 [2\pi n^2 - 3] e^{-\pi n^2} > 0$.

For $0 < t < \infty$ and for **each finite** $n \geq 1$, we see that $f(t, n) = 2\pi n^2 e^{2t} [2\pi n^2 e^{2t} - 3] e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}} e^{\frac{t}{2}} > 0$, using Result C.7.1.

As $n \rightarrow \infty$, $f(t, n)$ goes to zero, for $0 \leq t < \infty$ due to the term $e^{-\pi n^2 e^{2t}}$. We do summation over n and see that the sum of the terms $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f(t, n) > 0$, for $0 \leq t < \infty$.

Hence $E_0(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f(t, n) > 0$ for $0 \leq t < \infty$.

Given that $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + i\omega) = E_{0\omega}(\omega)$ is an entire function in the whole of s-plane, it is finite for real ω and also for $\omega = 0$. Hence $E_{0\omega}(0) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} E_0(t)dt$ is finite. We see that $E_0(t)$ is an analytic function for real t (Details in Section 1.1). Hence $E_0(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f(t, n) > 0$ is finite for $0 \leq t < \infty$.

Given that $E_0(t) = E_0(-t)$ (Details in Appendix C.6), we see that $E_0(t) > 0$ and finite for all $-\infty < t < \infty$.

Appendix C.6. $E_0(t)$ is real and even

We see that $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + i\omega) = E_{0\omega}(\omega) = E_{0\omega}(-\omega)$ (**Result C.8.1**) because $\xi(s) = \xi(1 - s)$ (link) and hence $\xi(\frac{1}{2} + i\omega) = \xi(\frac{1}{2} - i\omega)$ when evaluated at $s = \frac{1}{2} + i\omega$.

We take the Inverse Fourier transform of $E_{0\omega}(\omega)$ and use $E_{0\omega}(\omega) = E_{0\omega}(-\omega)$ from Result C.8.1 in the first line in Eq. C.4 and then substitute $\omega = -\omega'$ in the second line in Eq. C.4, as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} E_0(t) &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} E_{0\omega}(\omega) e^{i\omega t} d\omega = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} E_{0\omega}(-\omega) e^{i\omega t} d\omega \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} E_{0\omega}(\omega') e^{-i\omega' t} d\omega' = E_0(-t) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.4})$$

We see that $E_0(t)$ in Eq. 1 is real and $E_0(t)$ in Eq. C.4 is even and hence we have derived the result that $E_0(t)$ is a **real and even** function of variable t .

Appendix D. Properties of Fourier Transforms Part 1

Appendix D.1. Fourier transform of Real $g(t)$

In this section, we show that the Fourier transform of a **real** function $g(t)$, given by $G(\omega) = G_R(\omega) + iG_I(\omega)$ has the properties given by $G_R(-\omega) = G_R(\omega)$ and $G_I(-\omega) = -G_I(\omega)$. We use the fact that $g(t)$ is real and $\cos(\omega t)$ is an **even** function of ω and $\sin(\omega t)$ is an **odd** function of ω below.

$$\begin{aligned} G(\omega) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(t) e^{-i\omega t} dt = G_R(\omega) + iG_I(\omega) \\ G_R(\omega) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(t) \cos(\omega t) dt = G_R(-\omega) \\ G_I(\omega) &= - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(t) \sin(\omega t) dt = -G_I(-\omega) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.1})$$

Appendix D.2. Even part of $g(t)$ corresponds to real part of Fourier transform $G(\omega)$

In this section, we take the **even part** of real function $g(t)$, given by $g_{\text{even}}(t) = \frac{1}{2}[g(t) + g(-t)]$

and show that its Fourier transform is given by the **real part** of $G(\omega)$.

$$G(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(t)e^{-i\omega t} dt = G_R(\omega) + iG_I(\omega)$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g_{\text{even}}(t)e^{-i\omega t} dt = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2}[g(t) + g(-t)]e^{-i\omega t} dt = \frac{G(\omega)}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(-t)e^{-i\omega t} dt$$
(D.2)

We substitute $t = -t$ in the second integral in the last line of Eq. D.2. We use the fact that $G_R(-\omega) = G_R(\omega)$ and $G_I(-\omega) = -G_I(\omega)$ for a real function $g(t)$. (Details in Appendix D.1)

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g_{\text{even}}(t)e^{-i\omega t} dt = \frac{G(\omega)}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(t)e^{i\omega t} dt = \frac{G(\omega)}{2} + \frac{G(-\omega)}{2}$$

$$= \frac{1}{2}[G_R(\omega) + iG_I(\omega) + G_R(-\omega) + iG_I(-\omega)] = \frac{1}{2}[G_R(\omega) + iG_I(\omega) + G_R(\omega) - iG_I(\omega)] = G_R(\omega)$$
(D.3)